

The impact of CRM as an effective marketing strategy on customer satisfaction and retention in luxury retail: A case study of Ozio

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Abstract

Business organisations in the current competitive marketing scenario face significant challenges in keeping customers satisfied, controlling customers' intention to switch to competitors, and retaining their custom in the long-term. A similar situation is faced by firms in the fashion industry, such as Ozio, a company that specialises in luxury products and accessories. Therefore, the current research aims to investigate and analyse the impact of business strategies, especially marketing strategies such as 'relationship marketing' and 'CRM', marketing mix strategies and communication mix, sensory marketing, etc. on customer satisfaction and retention. The preliminary objective of the research is to review the existing literature and understand the underpinning theoretical models and frameworks related to marketing, customer satisfaction and retention. This is followed by the objective that intends to examine the importance of marketing strategies that favour customer retention and satisfaction in the luxury fashion sector. The subsequent objectives are to critically evaluate whether such marketing frameworks and business strategies help to mitigate the negative impact on customers, and to identify the positive and the negative influences of those marketing strategies on the business and customers perspectives. The last objective is to recommend how the negative influences of these marketing strategies can be overcome and how better customer retention strategies can be implemented.

Following the mixed approach to data collection, a survey was carried out by distributing closed-ended, structured questionnaires to 200 customers of Ozio. Additionally, qualitative data was collected by interviewing three marketing managers of the same company to gain an in-depth insight into the marketing strategies adopted to achieve higher customer satisfaction and retention.

The findings indicate that the marketing strategy of the company is based on relational perspectives, i.e. 'relationship marketing', and the company has a dedicated CRM. However, unsolicited sales calls, intrusive banner ads and pop-ups, and a lack of customer-centric behaviour often lead to negative customer perceptions. The marketers, on the other hand, find it difficult to customise the marketing mix according to the specific needs of different customer groups, and to control the spread of negative word-of-mouth communication fostered by customers.

Acknowledgement

It gives me immense pleasure and pride to submit this thesis, which is intended to understand the impact of CRM as an effective marketing strategy on customer satisfaction and retention in luxury retail through a case study of Ozio.

The entire journey while conducting this research was a challenging, yet a remarkable experience. The contribution of this research to enhance my knowledge base has been very significant

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The current competitive business environment in almost every sector of the economy faces stiff competition, changing business models, emerging technologies, price wars and consequently, changing consumer tastes and preferences (Helm and Gritsch, 2014). In such a changing business landscape, while acquiring customers is difficult enough, retaining loyal customers and keeping them satisfied is even more challenging for business organisations. Despite implementing the best business strategies, firms often fail to prevent the imitation of their business models and tactics by competing firms that are always looking to poach customers by offering better deals (Li and Tan, 2013). These competing firms also strategize their business and marketing policies to lure away customers by creating low switch-over costs. Therefore, the importance of designing business strategies that are effective, align with the business requirements, are innovative and not imitable by rival firms is essential.

Emphasising the importance of customer retention, Arnold et al. (2011) argue that it has a direct impact on enduring customer life-term value. This is a more gainful opportunity for companies that aim to chase long-term growth and business sustainability as compared to those seeking to safeguard themselves from market decline due to a constricting economy. Khan (2012) supports this viewpoint and asserts that the pressure on firms to retain their existing customers is largely fuelled by external market conditions, where the rate of customer acquisition is low. Qi et al. (2011) argue that customer retention is crucial when customer loyalty is on the decline, while the sales cycle tends to intensify the existing business environment. Losing even a single customer to competitors in such a business environment would have a crucial impact on the firm's profitability, growth and overall sustainability.

A firm which is able to identify customer needs, wants and desires, and sells products and services accordingly is one that fundamentally addresses the issue of satisfaction. The customer base is a dynamic concept, as the new customer acquisition process is affected by customers' market exit and changes in their purchase frequencies. Products and services, therefore, are continuously changing their branding strategies, altering the product specifications or changing

their patronage in order to address the needs of the customer, which in turn affects their market size. The forces of increasing competition, product maturing, shrinking markets and aggressive marketing strategies are increasing the intensity of the challenges for firms. Many firms have resorted to a defensive marketing strategy in order to acquire new customers, reduce customer exit and increase customer satisfaction levels. However, the strategies with which firms adjust their marketing expenses to defend their market position and retain their position in the customer's perceptual map are important for the CRM function. Marketing strategies are increasingly deploying both offensive and defensive methods in order to justify their return on investment economically and retain their customer base.

The firm's view of customer dissatisfaction as discomfort with their existing product or service range reaches a level where the purchase decision or consumption activity is postponed by a customer. The general belief is that customer satisfaction can be restored, but only if the company puts CRM in place, deploys SERVQUAL to improve service quality to plug the gaps and convert dissatisfied customers using a retention strategy. Economically, this has a substantial impact on firms' profits and causes resources to be stretched in order to regain their position or realign products or services to appeal to the customer segments.

The literature review in this research was conducted in the form of a critical discussion that reveals insights into the underpinning theories that already exist in the academic domain. The review was carried out to establish a clear link with the purpose of the research question that the thesis intends to resolve. Underpinning theories and conceptual frameworks under review were derived from journal articles, books, and research papers accessed from academic databases such as Google Scholar. Using an exploratory research design, an informal enquiry was undertaken from different sources to gain knowledge of the concepts relating to relationship marketing, CRM, service quality including the SERVQUAL model, and their application in luxury fashion retail. The concept of brand, luxury fashion brand and factors affecting luxury fashion brands were also reviewed to some extent. In addition, theoretical debates relating to 'push and pull' marketing, marketing mix, sensory marketing, customer satisfaction and retention were also carried out. The underpinning theories and models of customer satisfaction, such as the Kano model, the American customer satisfaction index model, and Hirschman's exit and voice theory were conducted in the context of the topic under study. Finally, the impact of relationship marketing strategy, especially CRM, on customer satisfaction is discussed based on the theoretical literature, as well as empirical studies conducted by previous researchers and published in the academic domain. A comprehensive

review of the literature helps to gain a preliminary knowledge of CRM and related concepts, but additionally, apparent gaps the literature are highlighted, based on which the research questions and objectives are formulated. The impact of CRM on customer satisfaction and retention in the luxury fashion brand sector is the main knowledge gap that requires further investigation and accordingly, primary research has been undertaken in that vein.

1.2 Background to the study

The earliest works of customer satisfaction emerged with the research of Oliver (1980), Churchill and Surprenant (1982), Bearden and Teel (1983), and then further branching off to the service quality dimension (Parasuraman and Zeithaml, 1988). The journey of the research into customer satisfaction also led to an analysis of the customer retention strategies which have been at the forefront of the emerging service-oriented companies. The implication of the manager's actions through those strategies which impacts customer satisfaction elements, as well as the retention strategies, often focus on the customer's judgement to switch brands, which is a reflection of disconfirmation of their expectation set with that of the service provider. Thus, the issue of competitive marketing or improving the standards as per customer tastes need to build capabilities within an organisation.

The emergence of customer retention strategies came into force to eliminate the 'once acceptable' service to be improved or be aligned to new customer tastes and trends. The improvement process led to the discovery of the relationship of the satisfaction element, which was first highlighted by Fornell and Wenerfelt (1987, 1988) where the process of the complaint-handling process evolved towards customer retention strategies. Later, studies gradually emerged in the linking of customer behavioural intentions. The emphasis was, however, on how the management-created systems and ability to understand the service attributes link to the new level of customer expectation sets (Boulding et al., 1993). Bolton and Drew (1991) have researched the change in customer attitudes towards the service or product offerings and measured their effect. Out of all the research, the PIMS data analysis by Buzzell and Gale (1987) is the most acceptable. However, there is another angle of research which has become important here, as relationship marketing and transactional marketing both seemed to benefit the managerial strategies in dealing with the CRM thrust area, as one is long-term while the other is short-term in nature.

Diller (2000) outlines that CRM needs to emphasise relational marketing through the use of seven key principles: information, individualisation, investment, interactivity, integration, intention and selectivity. The emphasis of CRM as a capital asset leads companies to align their resources towards a more focussed approach and to prioritise social bonding through personalisation aided by technology. The strengthening of those bonds with the customer leads to the creation of a dedicated marketing systems approach to deliver the value which the customer is seeking. Some authors want to align these towards regaining the trust factor that has its solutions in the finding of the gaps through customer satisfaction in the CRM and providing solutions to retain them in the new context of the changed business situations context.

The context of customer retention plays a dynamic and a crucial role in the company's marketing strategy, where the strategies which work are repeated patronage of manager operationalised in a different manner. Although it is not a successful model for many other sectors, where the question of customer loyalty and repeat purchases are often sought as an indicator, it has been linked to the changed customer behaviour and attitude towards the same product or service. Customer satisfaction forms the lead point as it is more behavioural in nature and stresses the operations of the marketing function to miss the quality factors in defining the CRM domain while selling the product or service. There are variables in the perceived product or service that the customer expresses as dissatisfaction, which leads to a negative relationship quality over time. Though it is an emotional response, the structural aspect of the product or service not meeting the customer expectation setting is the crucial issue and is resolved with the introduction of a service quality framework (SERVQUAL).

However, the commitment of the customer from the CRM angle shows that the capability of firms to address issues to realign infrastructure and resources in a responsive continuum helps to bridge the gaps. The structural alignment in the product or service shows how companies redesign their CRM as a marketing instrument, which alters the customer's perception of the value or benefits perceived into a trust-based transaction (Wilson, 2012), though this change of service delivery hinges upon how the company perceives the changed needs of consumers and realigns the resources to deliver the new service. Failing to do so leads to the company to not address the emerging issues of grievance handling and discontentment arising from the relationship quality, which in turn results in non-fulfilment by the company of the promised fulfilment.

1.2.1 Background of the Ozio fashion brand

Ozio, was established as a luxury retail store in 1998 in Beirut, Lebanon by Nawal Tafech. This was followed by opening of other stores in Lebanon and Turkey. Ozio has further plans to open stores in Egypt and Dubai. The entrepreneur has 20 years of experience in retail and working in different stores which helped to establish this luxury brand. Ozio works within a financial model that implies growing the business and increasing sales while moving forward and opening new stores in various other countries such as the Middle East.

Ozio was built not through traditional marketing or advertising but through human experience. The entrepreneur believes that that experience can come to life only if people are proud, if they respect and trust the green apron and the people they are representing. The equity of the brand is defined by the quality of the merchandise but also, most importantly; by the relationship that the marketing personnel associate have with the customers. Ozio's priorities are to ensure that a customer feels valued, appreciated, and respected.

Ozio's mission is to create the kind of excitement that provides differentiation and separation in the marketplace. It believes in promoting innovation that is relevant, usable, and core to the company culture.

1.3 Research rationale

Internationalisation and competition are ever-increasing, and all companies and sectors are facing a highly challenging task to attract new customers and retain them. In this context of business, the customer plays a central role in deciding the profitability and sustenance of these organisations (Sharp, 2013). With different competitors competing with differential pricing, product characteristics and quality-based differentiation, it is the responsibility of every organisation to engage and retain their current customer base for the long-term (Parvatiyar, 2012). One of the factors that can help in retaining these customers is by meeting their expectations with a brand promise and by ensuring that they are satisfied with the product and services portfolio (Barbara, 2013). The better satisfaction level of the consumers, the better their retention rates towards the brand loyalty levels. All these show the importance of customer retention in CRM strategy and the importance of customer satisfaction as the two unique facets that can help an organisation to sustain and develop in the global arena (Woodcock, 2015). With all these issues at hand, every organisation tends to formulate marketing strategies that help to maintain a relationship with the customer (Auld, 2010). These marketing strategies have

an effect on the communication, value-enhancing services and the commitments which the organisation provides (Roberts-Holmes, 2012). When the relationship with the customer is strong, an organisation can forecast better sales and profits in its business. On the other hand, if they fail to meet the changing demands of the customer expectation set, this impacts the level of profitability. This erodes the customer base and even customer retention strategies fail to prevent the customer switching to a competitor's brand. Failure to address these issues affects the customer's satisfaction rate (Woodcock, 2015).

The following is the research analysis and the study of the impact on these marketing counterstrategies and their impact on customer satisfaction and retention rate. In this regard, some of these organisations fail to formulate the expected marketing strategies to the target customers, leading to poor or bad reputation. This is again studied through this research, where the negative influences imposed by failed marketing strategies are analysed and the strategies are conceived to overcome those negative influences.

1.4 Problem statement

The concept of marketing has evolved from a sales-driven, transactional approach to a relational strategy (West et al., 2015). The buzzwords in the area of the marketing literature is found to be customer equity, which is customer-driven, and life-term customer value. Retail brands with customer databases were the first to shift into this paradigm; banks, insurance companies, construction, rental providers and hospitality, for example. Fashion brands also stepped up into this direction and based their price premium on the charisma and eminence of their own names, i.e. on their brand equity (Theng et al., 2013). One such luxury brand, L'Oréal, initiated its CRM programme in mid-2000, backed by its database and trained customer care professionals. Over the last decade, luxury brands have started to place increasing importance on a relationship marketing strategy supported by CRM benefits to achieve lifelong customer value, thereby advancing the development of the social prestige of their brand names (Zhan, 2016).

According to Hennigs et al. (2015), luxury fashion brands possess a distinct asset, the use of which helps them to foster customer relationships, as they usually possess their own distribution outlets. The question arises why then, ahead of the services that align with this outlet experience, luxury brands require developing CRM capabilities; do they need to reinvent

or redesign the CRM model because they serve luxury customers, or follow the usual steps to develop a simple CRM system, such as mapping the multiple customer touchpoints, developing a strategic segmentation for clients, personalising client relationships by way of engagement, or maintaining a calendar of actions for their major client base?

Luxury brands such as Louis Vuitton, Cartier, Prada and Gucci have been able to accomplish outstanding worldwide growth due to their heritage, brand reputation and prestige and above all, due to their continuous flow of creations and magnificence (Atwal and Williams, 2017). Yet these brands face several challenges in consistently keeping their customers satisfied, maintaining high switch-over costs, and retaining those customers to run their business sustainably. Similar to usual fashion brands such as fast fashion, luxury fashion brands worldwide are subject to increased competitive intensity, with the emergence of premium brands working consistently to enhance their products and image, thereby giving birth to 'new luxury' (Rasul, 2017). This is a threat to the conventional luxury image maintained by classical luxury brands that are compelled to implement innovative tactics to satisfy customers and gain their life-term loyalty. From a different perspective, contemporary customers have changed in terms of their shopping patterns, buying habits, repeat purchase and reliance on brands with an age-old brand reputation (Tak et al., 2017). Contemporary customers who love luxury tend to divide their expenses between the emerging range of fashion brands, which can be luxury and non-luxury, or even mass-market brands such as Mango, Zara and H&M.

Atwal and Williams (2017) argue that, endowed with superior brand equity, luxury fashion brands in the current market scenario cannot simply wait for customers to visit their brick-and-mortar stores or websites but need to effectively compete to gain a fair market share. This requires developing effective marketing strategies, especially relationship marketing built upon CRM capabilities, that can engage customers, build trust and facilitate customer satisfaction, in turn leading to customer retention. In this context, customer retention has become crucial in dealing with the excursionist new form of luxury customers, who may or may not be price-sensitive, yet who are quality-conscious and aspire to purchase something new in terms of product and service quality (Shen et al., 2017). This applies to luxury brands such as Ozio, who need to weave a tighter relationship with their customers, find a way to exhibit how they are distinct and be capable of offering something new. Therefore, developing result-oriented CRM policies is necessary for luxury brands, as luxury is inherently linked to a direct relationship with clients.

The problem for the firm side is that they tend to show an inability to understand that customer dissatisfaction is an emotional response and the company's insufficiency to redesign a product or a service which is demanded by the customer's needs. The other side of evolving customer needs and a static response of company product portfolio or service that no longer serves the customer shows inflexibility of the company to change and adapt.

All of this leads to an increase in the number of active customer complaints, or passive customers quietly leaving the company and switching to other brands which meet their needs. The failure of the company to capture the exit voice of the customer that is labelled as a dissatisfied customer affects the profitability of the company. The very aspect of a product or service not matching the customer's needs and expectation set is also a show of management not being competitive enough and not looking outwards and inwards to bring a change within. They also ignore the parameters which is causing the dissatisfaction, believing that weakly-dissatisfied customers of the company will not affect its profits; however, ignoring them leads to resorting to a higher cost retention strategy for each customer.

1.5 Research aim

The aim of the current research is to investigate and analyse the impact of CRM on customer retention and satisfaction in the current competitive business environment. The aim is also to contribute to Ozio's management in terms of strengthening its CRM capabilities by eliminating the inherent weaknesses in its current CRM so that it achieves higher customer satisfaction and retention.

1.5.1 Research objectives

- To evaluate the underpinning business strategies, customer retention and customer satisfaction models, thereby gaining knowledge by a thorough review of the existing literature
- To examine the importance of marketing strategies, especially CRM, that favour customer retention and satisfaction in Ozio
- To critically evaluate the marketing frameworks and business strategies that help to mitigate the negative impact on customers of Ozio
- To identify the positive and negative influences of marketing strategies on the business and customers perspectives in Ozio

- To recommend how the negative influences of these marketing strategies can be overcome and how better customer retention strategies can be implemented in Ozio

1.5.2 Research questions

Q1) What is the importance of marketing strategies that favour customer retention and satisfaction?

Q2) What are the marketing frameworks that align with suitable luxury business strategies favouring customer retention and satisfaction?

Q3) How far do such marketing frameworks and business strategies help to mitigate the negative impact on customers?

Q4) What are the positive and negative influences of the marketing strategies on the business and customers perspectives?

Q5) How can the negative influences of these marketing strategies be overcome, and better customer retention strategies be implemented?

1.6 Brief methodology

The methodology that has been followed in conducting this research is the philosophical standpoint of pragmatism, i.e. the pragmatist worldview followed by the researcher. Pragmatism is backed by the abductive approach in integrating quantitative and qualitative data collection. The philosophical worldview of positivism and the deductive approach is aligned with the quantitative data collection, while interpretivism backed by the inductive approach helped to follow qualitative data collection.

Quantitative data was collected using a customer survey and a structured questionnaire as the instrument. Questionnaires were distributed online to 200 customers of Ozio to understand their perceptions about the luxury brand's marketing strategies, CRM, sensory marketing and the effectiveness of these strategies in rendering exceptional service to ensure retention of their life-long custom. On the other hand, qualitative data was collected by interviewing three marketing managers of Ozio using open-ended questionnaires as the instrument. The customers

for the survey were selected through simple random sampling to ensure unbiased selection, while the marketing managers were sampled through the convenience sampling process.

1.7 Scope of the study

The research scope is wide, as the challenge of collecting the primary research data from the sample size is time-consuming, while the option to reach out to those who prefer fashion, perceive themselves as fashionistas, those who are fashionable are the possible target customers for the primary research survey.

1.8 Outline of chapters

The first chapter outlines the fundamentals of customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction, and the marketing strategies utilised in order to boost CRM in order to retain a customer. The research rationale is set out along with the research aim, objectives and questions. The research also identifies the problem areas and the scope it has to justify the aims and objectives.

The second chapter defines customer satisfaction theories, retention theories, factors and issues causing them and the relevance of each to the fashion retail industry. These theories and models form the underpinning discussion base which is aligned towards the research topic, and the key variables are identified.

The third chapter looks at the manner in which the research methodology outlines the stages of the research by defining the approach, design and philosophy. It also states the primary and secondary research methods, data collection strategy, sample size and sampling strategy.

The fourth chapter concerns the interpretation of the data and discusses the findings, which are illustrated in the form of graphs. The outcomes of the research found in this chapter are then linked with the previously conducted research, models and theories to justify whether they have been tested or not.

The fifth and final chapter of the research consolidates the final outcomes towards the conclusion and discusses the findings by proving the final aims and objectives of the research.

1.9 Summary

The introductory chapter has introduced the topic and has narrated an issue which has been present in the industry and how it gained momentum to be included as a research rationale. The aims and objective have been formulated to give a direction to the research title and the background discussion has also helped to formulate the research problem and research objectives. This moves on to the discussion of key variables such as customer satisfaction in the next chapter and how CRM is affected by retention strategies. This chapter has also provided a roadmap for the entire study from the start of the thesis to the concluding part.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.0 Introduction

This chapter carries out a critical review of the existing theories and conceptual frameworks related to business strategy, customer satisfaction and customer retention. Initially, the theoretical concept of business strategy is explained with the help of key definitions by Porter (1996) and other authors. Since the current research emphasises the importance of business strategies for customer satisfaction and retention, the literature narrows down to focus on strategies that underpin customer management. Therefore, the shift from a transactional marketing strategy to relational marketing, and more specifically 'relationship marketing', is discussed. In the context of relationship marketing, a comprehensive review of the concept of customer relationship management (CRM) is carried out by discussing the various perspectives associated with it. The importance of CRM as a marketing strategy to manage and nurture customer relationships, as a philosophy and as a process is also dealt with. In the online business domain, the concept of electronic customer relationship management (eCRM) as a relationship management strategy is critically discussed along with an illustration of the emerging concept of social-CRM. The integration between social media platforms and CRM is considered more of a business strategy to engage customers, observe their activities, understand their behaviour and tailor the marketing mix, product and service offerings accordingly, in order to keep them satisfied and strengthen the retention process.

The next part of the literature review moves on to discuss the theoretical concept of customer satisfaction, with key reference to expectancy disconfirmation theories, equity theories and attribution theories. To gain a broader understanding of customer satisfaction in the marketing field, consistency theories such as the assimilation theory, the contrast theory, assimilation-contrast theory, and the disconfirmation theory of customer satisfaction, along with the concept of customer dissatisfaction are also examined. The models of customer satisfaction measurement are subsequently dealt with in order to explain how the extent of customer satisfaction could be measured as a result of the business strategies implemented. Therefore, the importance of service quality – the SERVQUAL model and its dimensions -is elaborated upon. Since the SERVQUAL model is largely associated with industries specialised in the

services sector, the Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS) tool is reviewed by focusing on its importance for measuring product quality and its impact on customer satisfaction. Going deeper into the model, the importance of product quality and its dimensions, similar to the service quality, is also emphasised. Other customer satisfaction measurement models, such as the Kano Model and the ACSI Model (American Customer Satisfaction Index) are also discussed in detail. The Hirschman exit and voice theory are also reviewed in order to emphasise loyalty as the core factor in the interaction between customers' voice and exit, wherein loyalty helps to push back exit and make the voice more effectual.

The concept of customer retention and its importance is reviewed by examining the influential factors that help to retain customers, such as service quality, customer loyalty, trust and switching costs. 'Three Level Customer Retention Strategies' as a conceptual model is discussed to explain the various levels in the customer retention process. This is followed by a discussion of the importance of competitive strategy, retention and regain management in the arena of customer retention. Finally, the literature review focuses on a discussion of the importance of customer satisfaction and retention in the fashion industry. In addition, the importance of re-positioning as a business strategy in the fashion brand segment and its impact on CRM is discussed, with reference to the key academic literature that currently exists. Finally, a critical discussion of the concept of sensorial marketing and its relevance to the fashion industry is also presented. Consequently, gaps in existing studies are identified and areas for further investigation are identified.

2.1 Brand /Luxury Fashion Brand

According to Keller (2003), a brand may be defined as,

“...a name, term, design or symbol, or a combination of these elements, which intends to indicate the goods and services of an individual seller or a group of sellers and signify their differences from those of the competitors.”

A brand provides both tangible and intangible benefits - both symbolic and practical - which could be visible or invisible under circumstances that are economically feasible for a company. A brand may also be considered to be *“...a signature of a continuously transformed, creative process that may yield different products.”* Keller et al. (2011) assert that products and services

may arrive, live and fade away, yet brands endure. The steadiness of this innovative action gives meaning to a brand and reflects its characteristics and its content.

A comprehensive review of the existing literature indicates that a universally accepted definition of what comprises a 'luxury brand' does not exist; for instance, the American Marketing Association does not include a specific definition of the terms 'luxury', 'luxury marketing', or 'luxury brand' (Okonkwo, 2016). So far, researchers across a range of disciplines have exerted efforts to define the term 'luxury brand', but currently, there is no clear consensus. Even though few semiotic scholars mention that there are specific 'codes of luxury' that appear to be consistent across various disciplines, several challenges exist in formulating a definition of 'luxury brand', especially because luxury is a relative concept (Giovannini et al., 2015) and the views of what comprises luxury have been debated over time (Atwal and Williams, 2017). Kapferer and Valette-Florence (2016) add that previous studies are characterised by a lack of precision about the definition, measurement and operationalisation of brand luxury. This observation aligns with previous arguments of researchers to compose an accurate definition of a luxury brand. Ko et al. (2017) argue that the definition and measurement of the concept of luxury is highly subjective, even if luxury is not an intrinsically subjective construct.

Researchers such as Tynan et al. (2010) indicate that the definition of a luxury brand should meet three main criteria. First, a luxury brand should be defined on the basis of a sound theoretical foundation. Second, the definition should be broadly applied to luxury brands in common, rather than only a subset of products or services or a particular category of products (example, automobiles, fashion); and thirdly, the conceptual definition should be operationalised in a manner that makes it possible for the construct 'luxury brand' to be measured.

Cavender and Kincade (2014) define a luxury brand as customer perceptions of products with superior quality, high price, extraordinariness, rarity, aesthetics and an elevated extent of non-functional associations. Seo and Buchanan-Oliver (2015) consider a luxury brand as premium products and services that provide pleasure to users as a fundamental benefit, and associate with customers in an emotional manner. Researchers such as Esmaeilpour (2015) and Okonkwo (2016) consider luxury as something that goes beyond a characteristic or a range of attributes. These authors theorise luxury, not in terms of its attributes, but what it does in three core areas: subjective (individual), objective (material), and collective (social). The objective

aspect comprises of exquisite craftsmanship, superior functionality and extraordinary performance. The subjective aspects link to the consumer's personal hedonic value, while the collective dimension is the brand value as signalled to others (Cheah et al., 2016; Cristini et al., 2017; Roy et al., 2018).

Culminating in a range of definitions, the characteristics of a luxury brand can be summarised as something that (i) maintains a premium image; (ii) is aligned with superior quality; (iii) creates unique brand associations that are intangible in nature; (iv) are drivers of luxury brand equity that include symbols, logos, and packaging; (v) has controlled distribution; (vi) has premium pricing; (vii) has secondary associations with celebrated personalities and events; (viii) whose competition is broadly defined; (ix) has cautiously administered brand architecture; and (x) lawful safeguards its trademarks.

2.2 Fashion luxury brand

Within the luxury offering, there exists a wide range of luxury categories that are ever-expanding. Chandon et al. (2016) indicate the presence of four fundamental categories of luxury items, namely fashion (couture, accessories, and ready-to-wear items), cosmetics and perfumes, jewellery and watches, and wines and spirits. However, other products and services such as tourism, hotels, automobiles, home furnishings, private banking and airlines in their premium offerings are also categorised as luxury (Ko et al., 2016).

According to Hwang (2013), conceptualisation of luxury is characteristically drawn from either the perspective of consumption or from being applied as a device for product branding. The extant literature explains the concept of luxury consumption, specifically with regards to having a symbolic function that works at an individual and a collective level (Okonkwo, 2016; Ajitha and Sivakumar, 2017; Salem and Chaichi, 2018). Therefore, luxury is recognised in relation to its function as a status symbol, in terms of its psychosomatic value, and as a consumption experience that is highly complex and strongly fitting to an individual's self-concept (Kapferer et al., 2017). Tak et al. (2017) indicate that from a product perspective, luxury fashion brands are often defined in relation to their exotic quality, exclusivity, distinctiveness, rarity, high transaction value and craftsmanship.

Amatulli et al. (2016) categorise six core attributes of a luxury fashion brand that are mainly drawn from the strong, long-drawn influence of French luxury heritage brands. Based on the Italian model, Amatulli et al. (2016) analyse Domenico De Sole and Moore's strategy for

Gucci's repositioning as an authentic fashion brand in the luxury segment. These authors recognise elements that necessitate cautious management to develop and generate a successful luxury brand. Even though the authors indicate that Gucci's approach can be applied universally, they assert that Gucci offers an extensive account of developing a luxury brand. The model designed by Okonkwo (2016) describes ten fundamental characteristics of a flourishing fashion luxury brand. Even if Okonkwo does not consider this as a specific model, the author insinuates that the model provides an in-depth analysis of luxury fashion brand management.

Within the proposition of luxury, the concept of a brand, particularly brand name and brand identity, are considered central. Burns et al. (2016) explain that a luxury fashion brand calls for a well-defined, clear and relevant marketing strategy and that this strategy should be designed to develop the brand presence and global reputation of the brand and to leverage brand status and awareness. In conjunction with the brand concept, several other attributes or features are acknowledged as critical for creating a luxury fashion brand, including product or fabric quality, design attributes, elegance and innovation, and craftsmanship (Dion and Borraz, 2015; Chihab and Abderrezzak, 2016; Ko et al., 2016). Atwal and Williams (2017) argue that iconic products are characterised by exclusivity, authentic and unmatched quality which are aspirational in nature, and often exemplify the brand DNA or the brand signature, as they help to depict the values and personality of its creators. Ko et al. (2017) point out that the appointment of a high-end fashion designer helps to enhance the appeal of fashion products, and ultimately elevates their significance in an existing fashion market. Even though it has been acknowledged earlier that overt price positioning does not essentially equate to positioning of luxury, there exists consensus among authors that luxury fashion products characteristically entail a premium price discrepancy relative to other products surrounded by the same category (Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2016; De Angelis et al., 2017; Tak et al., 2017).

Janssen et al. (2017) point out that the sensation of scarcity or exclusivity adds to the appeal of luxury fashion brands. Brand managers can sustain brand exclusivity through advertising, distribution control, endorsement, premium pricing, and by coming up with a limited-edition range. The atmosphere and services that luxury fashion brands offer is identified as crucial aspects of the luxury proposition (Janssen et al., 2017). Meanwhile, Kapferer et al. (2016) point out that luxury stores are acknowledged as cathedrals for shopping that make use of superior architecture to express a sense of magnificence and reflect the shopping experience for the

wealthy class. Han et al. (2017) argue that the luxury context and brand experience are exhibited in the flagship store, which is identified as a major outlet usually located in a capital city and maintaining the full assortment of the merchandise of a luxury fashion brand. These luxury fashion stores generally require considerable financial outlay and are considered central to the marketing communication process of a brand and its reputation as a support for the wholesale business. Burns et al. (2016) argue that company-owned stores in the luxury fashion sector allow companies to manage customer experience at point of sale (POS). Atwal and Williams (2017) consider superior customer services as crucial in the luxury fashion consumption experience and assert that in the area of retail fashion, branding is more about branding the experience in the retail store than from the actual consumption of the luxury product. The consumption experience of a fashion brand offers insight into the brand way of life (lifestyle) by transforming it into a reality (Han et al., 2017; Prentice and Loureiro, 2018). In addition to control of the consumer experience, Makkar and Yap (2018) regard the significance of controlling the manufacturer, especially within licensing agreements, to make sure that positioning of a luxury brand is not compromised.

2.3 Factors affecting luxury fashion brands

There are many factors which contribute to the luxury brand being accepted in a given market. For fashion in particular, the user segment perceives not only quality within the brand, but they also link their purchasing power to a superiority effect that others cannot afford (Taube and Warnaby, 2017). Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) explain that luxury brands are aspirational products for most of the population, and those consumers who can buy such brands and are real owners join an exclusive club. It is evident that the amount of attention luxury brands gain from the population helps market surveys in customer-centric analyses. It has been argued the very intent and motivation of the customer to aspire to purchase such brands is based on the 'old aristocracy' and 'new money' factors (Esmailpour, 2015; Ali et al., 2016; Tong et al., 2018).

In a world which is shifting towards capitalism and where societies are becoming increasingly consumerist, end users are shaping markets across geographical boundaries with changing aspirations that are linked to affordability (Han et al., 2017). The rise in income the world over has fuelled luxury consumption and its aspirations are now based on psychological factors (Taube and Warnaby, 2017). Thus the economic condition of the country, the change in the outlook of new generations over old and that of the prospective buyer, the influence of social

surroundings, ideas of self-esteem and self-actualisation and environmentally-based exposure to the fashion sector, have all resulted in the development of new markets that fashion brands in the luxury segment are fast tapping into (Janssen et al., 2017; Jain, 2019). Asian countries with consistent GDP growth and Middle Eastern markets are the major demand sectors when compared to the western matured markets in terms of new areas of demand. Meanwhile, the factors affecting the luxury brand are reviewed in the following section of this chapter.

2.3.1 Exposure and association

According to Kim et al. (2012), the association of the consumer to a normal brand and brand awareness leading to luxury fashion can be either direct or indirect. The exposure to luxury fashion brands in physical world visibility is accentuated by its luxury fashion brands store exclusivity and its visual advertisements (offline and online) which are often fuelled by the mediator brand (nearest brand) that the consumer currently uses. The aspiration level of owning a current brand and the elements of perceived quality of a fashion luxury brand, coupled with celebrity association, impacts individual consciousness levels (Esmailpour, 2015; Eom and Seock, 2017; Salem and Chaichi, 2018). They are also a part of a new consumer's influencer at the POS (point of sale) and a mediator of imparting a higher level of luxury brand consciousness that meets the brand equity dimensions. It has been found that consumers affected by brand exposure are likely to probe deeper into the luxury brand as part of the information search process (Thakur and Kaur, 2016; Eom and Seock, 2017). This is a test of perceived quality of luxury, the brand name amidst other luxury fashion brand competitors, and attempts to identify the brand association within society (celebrities, own social circle). These help to create confirmatory behaviour for new consumers, working as an impetus to their decision sets to consider luxury fashion brands in their buying criteria (Pinto and Yagnik, 2017). These new consumers also accept that the luxury fashion brand offers a uniqueness that links to their own personal identity, carries a brand persona which is different from the rest, and meets the personal aspiration and status consumption to affect the motivation levels and purchasing intentions (Choi et al., 2016). Luxury brands target consumers in a collectivist culture, as it helps them in markets such as China to influence with niche products to help them to become recognised (Giovannini et al., 2015; Zhang and Cude, 2018).

2.3.2 Reference groups

The uniqueness of the consumer's exposure to brands has been found to occur mostly through reference groups (Godey et al., 2016). Reference groups form the single most important factor for the initiation of the consumer to the world of fashion. This issue for luxury fashion brands works only when users and non-users are able to physically or digitally access the luxury fashion store as a part of shopping experience (Kembau, 2015; Wu et al., 2015; Han et al., 2017). The change in the socialising pattern and conversation from WOM (word of mouth) in face-to-face conversations and eWOM (electronic word of mouth) in online conversations between known and unknown members of a community fuels the luxury brand discussion (Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2016; Charoennan and Huang, 2018). This community, which is comprised of like-minded customers, who endorse luxury fashion and can afford to wear, is a sign of exclusivity. Similarly, luxury fashion brands are also adopting a brand community strategy, for example with Cartier to endorse in 2008, Burberry in 2009 to promote the launch of the new line of the season (Schivinski and Dabrowski, 2016; Charoennan and Huang, 2018). Therefore, organisation-customer marketing communication is amplified with the communities of existing and prospective buyers (Godey et al., 2016). The influencer in these reference groups that are mostly closed groups often falls into the trap of 'buying frenzies', as most of the luxury items produced are limited in number. Essentially, all the members try to extract the maximum information about the rarity of luxury fashion designs, the item appeal in a fashion season and contemplate the demand-pull created by the luxury fashion brand's worth (Tak et al., 2017). Their purchase motives are therefore influenced by the luxury fashion discussions online and offline or at the store outlet or at a luxury fashion show event, all of which are precursors to the availability and exclusivity of the new launch of a new season (Tak et al., 2017; Gautam and Sharma, 2017; Henninger et al., 2017). The difference in the exclusivity of being a member of a community that endorses luxury fashion brands easily filters into the high street fashion brands that compel the non-user to opt for high-end luxury fashion brands as an act of allegiance to social conformance to group likings.

2.3.3 Purchase environment

According to Goworek et al. (2016), one of the key factors that influences the consumer's attention is the purchase environment. While initially luxury brands have been found to avoid direct communication, niche segment offerings seclude consumers from the mass consumption brands and acceptance of the famous expensive brands happens over a period of time (Ki and

Kim, 2016; Eom and Seock, 2017; Roy et al., 2018). The high price of a luxury fashion brand is in no way a barrier for the new customer. This is a transition of a mass marketing endorser shifting towards luxury brands. Bain and Company (2010) found that in addition to offering product line-up, the luxury segment also offers services to complement customer ownership. This heightens their expectation set that in reality makes purchasing intent favourable towards the luxury fashion brand. While instead of assisting as an influencer, Alexander and Contreras (2016) report that new customers found salespeople in luxury brand retailers to be rude, intimidating and unhelpful. Again, in shopping malls, the visibility and strategic positioning of a luxury brand attracts new consumers by working on the 'rarity' factor, superiority of luxury fashion positioning and its presence against the competition (Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2016; Brun, 2017; Roux et al., 2017; Eom and Seock, 2017).

The luxury fashion environment focuses on customer exclusivity and customer experience and keeps one item with a reserve price to create heightened interest (Opiri and Lang, 2016). The exclusivity of single piece of luxury fashion which has been sold off to a buyer and the prospect of an item being manufactured on request adds to consumer excitement. Feedback regarding trials of luxury fashion by store executives relating to the fit and look factor helps to secure the doubts of insecurity in a prospective buyer's mind (Alexander and Contreras, 2016; Henninger et al., 2017). The retail interiors of luxury fashion outlets are typically outbursts of opulence that are classic in design and that are ageless and timeless. This is a core element which makes the ordinary high street brand lacking all of these factors.

2.3.4 Purchasing motivation

The previous discussion has shown how these three factors initiate the non-user of a luxury fashion brand to understand the luxury fashion brand culture and the process of being in the league of the 'luxury fashion brand community'. All the inputs at various stages create a feel-good factor which aids the final purchase motivation levels. However, the limited items produced by luxury fashion brands, reserved price and price-on-request all heighten the luxury brand equity for the first-time buyer, as it is different from the normal brand purchase process (Bezzaouia and Joanta, 2016; Godey et al., 2016; Roy et al., 2018). The motivation from the customers' point of view is to impress others and sustain the hierarchy of needs to purchase a luxury fashion item for themselves (Pinto and Yagnik, 2017). Arrigo (2018) argues that the need to purchase, however, is dependent on a number of factors, as even though the purchase motivation is linked to social standing, owning a limited luxury fashion item amidst other

buyers is in itself a competition. Undoubtedly, celebrity endorsements are positive influences and provide a boost towards owning limited luxury item in a competitive social environment (Ryding et al., 2017; Arrigo, 2018). Although luxury items are heavy purchases, reflecting status in a societal context, the consumer's understanding of luxury brand comprises similar elements of cognitive dissonance (Parker and Wang, 2016; Loureiro et al., 2018). At times when trying on an outfit does not fit the personal expectations of the mental imagery of the luxury fashion brand, many buyers are likely to experience guilt and abort the purchase at the POS.

The implications of the above discussion show that luxury fashion brands need to market items strategically, as per seasons. This is important, as the penetration of social media and consumers using as a part of their daily lifestyle as an alternate communication channel has expedited their decisions. The opportunities for luxury fashion brands' online and offline customers help to create a pull to a fashion show launch, as the customers' communication online in a community is rapidly influencing each participant's decision in that community (Ki and Kim, 2016; Henninger et al., 2017). The demand factors within consumers are obtaining an information boost through the sharing of opinions for a market where the product availability is limited to every growing segment of aspirants is an irony due to lack of interactivity of luxury fashion brands in this open communicative world.

2.4 Concept of business strategy

Business strategy, as defined by Porter (1996), refers to progressing through defensive and aggressive actions to achieve a reasonable position in an industrial sector in order to effectively deal with competitive forces that impact business operations, and to conduct activities with the aim of securing a major return on investment (ROI). In precise terms, strategy relates to making choices between an available set of alternatives or options. Ghemawat (2016) points out that strategies are ways to maintain a competitive advantage through the investment of resources required to develop the key competencies and capabilities to achieve superior long-term performance. Organisations make use of business strategy to respond to the changing environmental landscape, as it helps to integrate the resources to counter external forces. Strategy incorporates the key actions undertaken by the organisation, the content of such a strategy, its timing, intensity and various processes that help to decide and implement actions

(Johnson, 2016; Anwar and Hasnu, 2016). This issue is important, as luxury brands need to create space in the market, target the customer segment and be effective in order to create a viable business model in the long run. Typically, luxury fashion brands use fashion shows to launch and showcase their new products.

An effective business strategy involves a pattern of actions that examine the strengths and weaknesses of the organisation, as well as the opportunities and threats involved. It evaluates whether the organisational resources are capable of producing the best competitive advantage and it persistently interacts and adapts to the external business environment (Kourdi, 2015; Chen et al., 2016; Parnell, 2016). An appropriate business strategy is aimed at defining clear long-term goals and illustrates the economic and non-economic objectives that create value for key stakeholders. Casadesus-Masanell and Ricart (2010) argue that effective business strategies are consistent, coherent and cohesive in nature and tend to combine and unify the different organisational levels and functions to facilitate the organisation's continuity (Bentley et al., 2014; Ghemawat, 2016). This is particularly pertinent for luxury fashion brands, as an increasing number of fashion start-ups are looking to find new ways to impact the customer's senses and create an impact on the ownership urge in fashion shows that exhibit the latest creations for a particular season. This is likely to create worldwide demand for luxury fashion brand items from that season. Hence, for every season, an effective business strategy is needed to continue building and engaging customer interest.

Strategy may be defined as an interactive and a complex process involving the integration of the organisational resources and actions that help to mobilise the overall organisation, wherein individual resources may not sufficiently produce added value for the organisation, and synergistic integration of resources could help to generate sustained competitive advantage (Spender, 2014; Cortimiglia et al., 2016). Meanwhile, competitive edge is achievable if the business activities fit with the organisational resources and strengthen one another. This fit must incorporate reinforcement of activities, consistency and 'optimisation of efforts', implying appropriate co-ordination and exchange of information across those activities (Chen and Jermias, 2014; Anwar and Hasnu, 2016). A strategy that involves fit is the outcome of an intricate and complex network of interrelationships in which the entire system is considered more vital than the standalone parts that it is composed of (Anwar and Hasnu, 2016). However, Porter (1994) argues that when business activities harmonise with each other, counterpart firms will derive less benefit through imitation unless they are able to effectively match the entire system.

The idea behind implementing a business strategy in luxury fashion brands is to build a strong and loyal customer base. For that reason, strategies must be focused on creating customer value, which in luxury fashion brands is the rendering out of the world experience a differentiated business strategy to make an unforgettable impact on the memory through owning a luxury fashion brand. Customers occupy a central position in designing a strategy and therefore, the basis of any strategy is a customer-based one. Zhu et al. (2015) focus on the idea of ‘total customer responsiveness’ and stress the importance of a collaborative, value-based, flexible and innovative element of a customer-focused organisation. The concept of a ‘customer-driven’ luxury fashion brand was also introduced wherein the management must know how to think like consumers, map the enquiries for a season, understand colour preference in different festivals/seasons, foster continuous learning, be entrepreneurial and be innovative and flexible in incorporating new technology in service delivery (Chen and Jermias, 2014; Saleem et al., 2015). These authors also consider business strategy to be directed towards fulfilling customers’ needs and persistently generating and delivering superior value to them.

A business strategy, therefore, must be to create customer value which requires an in-depth understanding of the customers’ needs and personalisation of service. It also requires luxury fashion brands to define what characteristic attributes consumers would need or expect in the products and services being offered by the company (Wirtz et al., 2016; Cortimiglia et al., 2016). The issue for a luxury fashion brand customer requires deeper examination of their needs and expectations and those needs should be incorporated into the luxury brand design strategy to enhance their extent of satisfaction. Understanding customer needs requires setting up a collaborative and continuous relationship that helps to access information on a regular basis. Pagani (2013) explains that access to regular and current information about customer needs and preferences creates higher depth about fashion trends in seasons and therefore facilitates defining and continuously redefining the luxury business strategy.

Listening to the customer’s voice is not only about understanding their varied needs and demands but also considering their predispositions, moods, cultural orientation, behaviour, current expectations, both currently and those in the future (Kotler et al., 2015; Saleem et al., 2015; Anwar and Hasnu, 2016). Listening also involves trying to comprehend what is unspoken or tacit and identifying the features of the luxury fashion brand which impacts the user’s persona. It is the connect of self-actualisation of a motivated customer who uses luxury fashion brand that is crucial here. Listening helps leaders and designers of the luxury fashion brand organisation to explore new dimensions and design product offerings and out-of-this-world

experiential services that could deliver the best value to fashion-conscious consumers. However, this requires setting up a formal relationship with customers based on loyalty-patronage and to link luxury fashion brand design from a conceptual viewpoint, with customer self-esteem that impacts the marketing. In the literature, it is termed as '**relationship marketing**' (Spender, 2014; Ghemawat, 2016; Kantan and Darma, 2017; Sheth, 2017).

The selection of customers and building a solid customer base that engages in repeat purchases encompass an analysis of the key factors that influence customers' buying decisions. Different customers tend to have different discernment of needs, value and wishes, and segmenting customers accordingly is also an important business strategy backed by an operations strategy (Chen and Jermias, 2014; Kourdi, 2015, Evans et al., 2017). Moreover, the choice that different customers have is also a critical strategic factor, and selecting specific customer segments explains the way in which an organisation can create value for target audiences using IT. The selection of those customers should fit the goals and capabilities of the organisation, as in the luxury segment it concerns a select few and is not about mass marketing. Organisations that align their business strategies, capabilities, culture and systems with the needs of the customer requirements are in a better position to serve and satisfy their customers' needs and stimulate them to be loyal to the company or brand (Wirtz et al., 2017; Cortimiglia et al., 2016; Sheth, 2017).

A business strategy, therefore, must be focused upon capturing new customers and retaining the old; addressing those needs can be satisfied through the provision of superior value, achieving repeat use of the products and services and gaining customer loyalty. Achieving customer loyalty is crucial because loyal customers generate a significantly higher profit as compared to newer ones as a result of an emotive connection with the luxury brand. Long-term customers being loyal are generally easy to manage through the patronage, as in luxury fashion customers are less price-sensitive and are likely to add value to the new trends or dimensions of the business, such as accessories business foraying (Zhu et al. 2015). Moreover, loyal customers tend show their reassuring faith in the luxury fashion brand. Business strategies that aim for higher profitability rather than generating value for their customers, are more likely to fail due to poor customer relationships, thereby increasing customer complaints and dissatisfaction. Therefore, the business strategy for value creation in luxury fashion brands rests on experiential level engagement sessions with customers and which must be difficult for the luxury fashion competitors to imitate. It is also about unwritten rules and emotive bonding

towards luxury fashion brands as a response to the business strategy of engaging the prospective target population that the fashion houses have built over a period of time.

2.5 Relationship marketing

An examination of the literature indicates that relationship marketing, in going further than the traditional marketing concept, has brought a paradigm shift in the area of marketing, wherein the long-recognised transactional orientation has given way to customer management (Aka et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2016; Payne, and Frow, 2017). Meanwhile, earlier researchers such as Gronroos (1994) state that the relational marketing standpoint, in actuality, is older than the transactional viewpoint and dates back to the history of trade and commerce. Gronroos (1999) also infers that the idea of managing and sustaining the relationship with customers is not a new phenomenon, even though the formal notion of ‘relationship marketing’ has only been relatively recently introduced by academic researchers and marketing professionals.

Contrary to the above belief, other researchers indicate that the scholarly attention in the relationship facets of customer management has grown over the last two decades (Triznova et al., 2015; Gummerus et al., 2017). The conventional perspective considers relationship marketing to be relevant and important to industrial and services sectors. For instance, business to business (B2B) relationships are identified as relatively more enduring and stable and to demonstrate adaptation to the key requirements of the other party. The adaptations in the marketing environment act as structural bonds and serve as crucial investments in a relationship which is often difficult to recover when the relationship has broken down.

In the case of service sectors, face-to-face, two-way interactions between the customers and the service providers help in the development of social bonds. In this context, the relational perspective of luxury fashion marketing fits well, where companies have greater opportunities to gain long-term customer occupancy with personalisation, offer better means of customer satisfaction, promote customer loyalty and achieve economic benefits (Rizan et al., 2014; Skarmeas et al., 2016). However, these conventional claims regarding relationship marketing have been questioned by earlier researchers who designed an empirically tested taxonomy of the prevailing marketing practices, known as the CMP (contemporary marketing practices) model (Raggio et al., 2014; Santouridis and Veraki, 2017). This framework was developed to support the idea that relational marketing aspects can be adopted by any type of firm, irrespective of its size or industry. The framework or model identified five core forms of

marketing, out of which, network marketing, interaction marketing database marketing and e-marketing were considered to have dynamic relational elements (Dilberović, 2016; Madhovi and Dhliwayo, 2017). However, this does not apply to luxury fashion marketing strategies.

In contrast, ‘transactional marketing’, as the fifth form of the framework, was found to be extensively practised in manufacturing rather than service-oriented companies, and in business-to-consumer (B2C) segments, rather than business-to-business (B2B) firms. In actuality, the CMP framework of marketing confirms the universality of the relational customer management approach throughout all business environments, such as business-to-consumer, business-to-business, manufacturers and service providers (Rodriguez et al., 2015). As a strategic approach to relationship marketing, a philosophy, a tool, or a technology, the concept of customer relationship management has gained much importance in the contemporary business world (Zhang et al., 2016; Payne and Frow, 2017; Gummesson, 2017). Therefore, the current literature narrows down to a discussion of the concept of customer relationship management from various perspectives and as a business strategy that helps to satisfy customers and retain them in the long run.

2.6 Customer relationship management

The emergence of CRM dates back to the late 1990s, with the increasing prominence of information technology vendors and practitioners. Often, customer relationship management is illustrated by technology-backed customer solutions such as sales force automation (Demo, 2014; Hayley, 2016). However, in the literature, the terms ‘relationship marketing’ and ‘customer relationship management’ are frequently used interchangeably. To clarify this, Verhoef and Lemon (2013) point out that CRM is mainly used in the context of technological solutions and is often identified as ‘information-enabled relationship marketing’. CRM is also explained as an offspring of the practice of relationship marketing based on the relational philosophy of marketing, although further investigation in its relational aspects still needs to be undertaken.

2.7 Differing views of the CRM concept

As regards the definition of CRM, neither researchers in the academic domain nor marketing professionals in real life business enterprises are in consensus with what constitutes CRM. It is viewed from a process perspective, strategic perspective, technological perspective, as well as a philosophical perspective (Bhat and Darzi, 2016; Rahimi, 2017; Shokohyar et al., 2017).

However, the strategic perspective of CRM is the most widely discussed topic in the academic literature and this viewpoint has also gained prominence in the last few years.

Customer relationship management can be defined as the art of customer acquisition and customer management with the aim of maintaining long-term relationships with them (Hassan et al., 2015). It is also referred to as the integration of crucial elements such as people, business processes and technology (such as information technology and information systems) to acquire target customers, build and nurture relationships with them and to retain them (Hassan et al., 2015; Thakur and Workman, 2016). As a business tool, Verhoef et al. (2010) states that engagement in CRM is more than just a professionally developed website but is also the need to contend with competitors and maintain competitive advantage. CRM also serves as touchpoints between the company and its customers through email, the internet, face-to-face marketing, call centres and kiosks, and all of this helps to maximise interaction with customers to gain a 360-degree view (Andajani, 2015; Rahimi, 2017).

CRM is mainly considered as a strategy in the marketing domain, and hence, the strategic-based definition is important to consider. CRM is therefore defined as a process that includes technological and human factors to build and generate the best customer relationships in order to strengthen value, customer satisfaction and loyalty (Carmen and Marius, 2016; Zouaoui et al., 2016). In addition, Ahearne et al. (2012) refer to CRM as an advanced level of strategic marketing adopted by an organisation to foster customer acquisition, relationship management, and thereby retention, to generate long-term value and profitability. Meanwhile, Saarijärvi et al. (2013) consider CRM as a strategy that helps to capture data to understand customer requirements and expectations and to develop marketing capabilities to sustainably manage sales, marketing operations and service procedures.

CRM is also referred to as a set of strategies that promote interactive customer relationships and facilitate a deeper understanding of their current and future requirements in order to deliver customised and personalised products and services. As a customer-focused strategy, CRM not only helps to acquire new customers, but also helps to keep existing ones satisfied and combines technology with management to promote long-term customer relationships (Alamgir and Shamsuddoha, 2015; Rahimi, 2017). As a central element to managing customer relationships, CRM provides the necessary tactics to deal with customer-related issues and makes the business environment more interactive for the purpose of facilitating an increased number of transactions (Reimer and Becker, 2015).

Business organisations such as luxury fashion brands intending to implement a CRM often face a dilemma as to what constitutes customer relationship management. Often, marketers relate CRM with an informative database of its customers or a promotional incentive such as a loyalty card scheme, while others consider it to be a contact-centre or a helpdesk. In many cases, CRM is related to data warehouse population or embarking on data mining. Others regard CRM as an e-commerce solution built upon the use of internet technology or a relational database (San-Martín et al., 2016; Mukerjee et al., 2017). Hence, a lack of an appropriate definition and understanding of the CRM concept can result in the failure of a CRM framework, especially if CRM is narrowly viewed from a technological perspective or identified on a fragmented basis. CRM largely impacts the way a business organisation - whether B2C or B2B - perceives, accepts and implements CRM practices. Moreover, from a strategic perspective, customer relationship management is not merely an IT solution implemented to attract and develop a customer base. The issue for luxury fashion branding and marketing is partially appropriate however, as a client database is essential to build relationships, but using information management systems requires a commercial understanding and awareness of the luxury brand environment of customer value in a multichannel context, as well as superior quality fulfilment of operations and experiential services (Alamgir and Shamsuddoha, 2015; Pedron et al., 2016; Rahimi and Kozak, 2017).

Therefore, from the strategic standpoint, Verhoef et al. (2010) define CRM as a strategic approach associated with the formation of enhanced stakeholder value, by building and nurturing appropriate relationships with customers and key customer segments. It integrates the functions of IT with relationship marketing strategies to generate value-based, long-term and profitable customer relationships and relationships with other stakeholders. As a holistic framework, CRM also provides increased opportunities to marketers for the utilisation of user data and information obtained from customers to understand their needs, tailor marketing strategies accordingly, and to co-create value. Reimer and Becker (2015) elucidate that this necessitates the use of CRM or eCRM to better understand the luxury fashion target market segment customer mindset and influence their decisions at an emotive level. Hence, this CRM continuum based on the strategic approach can be demonstrated with the help of the diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CRM continuum

(Source: Wahlberg et al., 2009)

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2.8 CRM as a process perspective

The process perspective of CRM considers it to be a set of business processes that are well-coordinated for nurturing customer relationships to achieve loyalty and long-term retention. Saarijärvi et al. (2013) explain CRM as systematic customer relationship management across different parts of the organisation, emphasising the creation of customer value, providing value and enhancing the level of customer interaction. CRM is also comprised of various communication channels, loyalty and provides different forms of services that help to strengthen customer loyalty and, consequently, retention (Kocoglu and Kirmaci, 2012). As a process-driven strategy, CRM facilitates face-to-face marketing and helps to gain better clarification of customer preferences, particularly with luxury fashion brands that aim to maintain customer interest with the main goal of customer retention.

According to Cho and Fjermestad (2015), as a business process, CRM helps to correlate and regulate organisational activities that are significant enough to be ingrained reliably. However, devising strategies to influence long-lasting impressions and memories helps luxury brand to be in 'top of the mind' recall. Most luxury fashion brands personalise their contact with customers using a CRM database to provide a meaningful experience for all the customers associated with the fashion business. By implementing CRM and its components, companies with luxury fashion brands may effectively control operating costs and can also personalise their approach or invitation, communication pattern and its intensity, in order to foster better interaction with the customer, and to utilise CRM data in marketing functions to take appropriate decisions for optimising customer value and support (Bai and Qin, 2016; Wang

and Kim, 2017; Cambra-Fierro et al., 2017). This can also help to generate a customer-centric data warehouse and to mine an exact list to prepare a communication strategy to articulate the process approach that considers CRM to be a customer-centric. This issue is important for luxury fashion brands, as every existing client requires an invitation to the new season launch in order to continue the interest levels in the dynamic continuum. CRM in luxury fashion branding is a part of a comprehensive business process that helps the company to provide timed and personalised customer services in real time and minimises customer dissonance factors (Kocoglu and Kirmaci, 2012).

As a holistic business process, CRM makes use of selection, filtering and analysis of customer information (like purchasing habits, frequency, volume of purchase, average price of purchase) to gain a comprehensive view of the nature of its luxury brand customers. For luxury brands that issue limited editions containing the rare factor, with incidence of price on request for special launches, banking on CRM is a critical strategy to filter out prospective purchasers. The use of customer intelligence at every stage of communicating the company's clear vision to the stakeholders is critical for its growth and also for serving the global market using the luxury brand demand analysis across different cultural markets (Hennigs et al., 2014; Thakur and Workman, 2016; Krämer et al., 2017). The process-based view of CRM, therefore, mainly perceives customer relationship management as a systematic IT-based approach to stimulate luxury fashion customer loyalty and consequently to retain customers by controlling their switchover intention (Thakur and Workman, 2016; Bhat and Darzi, 2016; Wang and Kim, 2017).

2.8.1 eCRM as a relationship management strategy

The concept of eCRM is that it goes beyond the traditional customer-centric CRM, as it helps to enhance the capabilities of the front office by way of back office functions. It also helps the organisation to widen its potential for self-service by the end-user through personalised interaction using internet applications (Choudhury and Harrigan, 2014; Yu et al., 2015; Hamid et al., 2019). The use of eCRM helps the firm to achieve its goals and gain competitive advantage in the competitive luxury brand market. eCRM also helps to enhance interaction with luxury brand customers, develop emotive relationships and enjoy personalisation of the opportunities. The use of eCRM helps to identify the different needs of different customers and help to strategize with counter-response communication to keep them satisfied by offering

customised luxury fashion products and/or on-demand services which align with a customer's specific needs (e.g. wedding ensemble) (Pradana et al., 2017).

In developed countries such as the USA, retail firms that have implemented eCRM are more likely to achieve higher customer satisfaction scores as compared to maintaining traditional communication methods with customers (Papaioannou et al., 2014; Krämer et al., 2017; Cambra-Fierro et al., 2017). Providing higher satisfaction has also helped these organisations to develop stronger relationships with customers of luxury fashion, and to motivate them to request more personalised attention, offers and rich experiential services, personalised offers, and ultimately, choose to make repeat purchases and exhibit higher loyalty (Bhat and Darzi, 2016; Giri et al., 2019).

Awasthi and Sangle (2012) consider the importance of eCRM from a different perspective and emphasise after-sales services as a crucial stage that significantly impacts customer satisfaction. A robust eCRM offers a multi-channel communication to luxury fashion brand customers, where they can express their thoughts on an emotional plane about competition and luxury fashion perceptions, issues and complaints and notify the marketing personnel of the firm. It also provides fast access to information, easy navigation of the luxury fashion brand company website, better search capabilities and well-designed customer complaint management systems (Milovic, 2012). Customers seeking after-sales services such as product return, replacement, giving feedback about their purchase experiences, or experience with the luxury fashion brand product and/or luxury fashion brand service, placing subsequent orders, etc. find eCRM to be more effective. Yu et al. (2015) argue that effectiveness of the after-sale service with personalisation of luxury fashion brand is most dominant for gaining customer trust, in regard to the reliability of the firm's services, providing a solution to their problems in real-time, engaging them into long-term relationships, and thereby improving retention capabilities.

2.8.2 Social-CRM as a business strategy

Customers in the contemporary business era are making use of the 'social-web' in order to connect and communicate with other customers, share experiences and information relating to products, services and brands. The extensive growth of social platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn and others, and their wide acceptance among the masses, has resulted in a shift of power from marketers to consumers (Elena, 2016; Wittwer et al.,

2017). Compared to traditional CRM and eCRM capabilities, social-CRM is an integration of social media tools and CRM software that has facilitated the use of social media for business purposes (Farhan et al., 2017). Therefore, the implementation of social-CRM for a firm is considered to be more of a business strategy rather than a database for managing information or a platform for delivering customer services.

Researchers such as Wittwer et al., (2017) and Wang and Kim (2017) consider social-CRM to be a philosophy and a business strategy backed by the use of technology and information systems and designed with the main aim of engaging customers through collaborative interaction. This offers reciprocally beneficial value to both the customer and the firm in a reliable and transparent business context. Social-CRM has significant potential for business organisations in the luxury fashion brand sector, as it helps to connect and interact within the realm of social networks of similar customer types. It also enhances the quantity and quality of interaction with key stakeholders such as customers, investors, suppliers, etc. and strengthens the brand loyalty of luxury fashion brands (Wittwer et al., 2017; Wang and Kim, 2017; Girchenko et al., 2017).

Social-CRM makes use of socially accepted collaborative technology which helps to deliver higher customer value while resolving complex business problems associated with customer management. It helps organisations to monitor customers' activities on social media, observe their behaviour, identify the areas of satisfaction or dissatisfaction, trace the conversations customers have between themselves and subsequently captures information about the changing customer needs, expectations and market trends (Choudhury and Harrigan, 2014). Therefore, key information is accessed directly from the customers in real-time rather than conducting formal research, such as customer surveys for the luxury fashion brand aspiration segment. Customer engagement is one of the unique features of social-CRM which is usually absent in traditional CRM/eCRM applications (Rodriguez et al., 2015) The use of social media automatically encourages luxury fashion brand customers to maintain their account on social platforms and, for instance, carry out social activities about the launch of season-based luxury fashion brands line-up.

To engage luxury fashion brand customers, luxury fashion brand firms often organise online social forums, discussion boards, contests and other similar activities that assemble customers online, i.e. social media users on a common platform (Lehmkuhland Jung, 2013). This provides opportunities for the luxury fashion brand customers of the firm to put forward their ideas to

seek and provide consultation and get their doubts clarified, thereby engaging with others as well as the firm. Firms are also able to track the behaviour of the most active luxury fashion brand customers or those expressing positive views about the luxury fashion brand, engage them, and incentivise them to be luxury fashion brand advocates. These customers acting as brand advocates have a higher tendency to spread positive word-of-mouth recommendations for the luxury fashion brand, often acting as opinion leaders, recommending others to choose the brand among a set of available alternatives, thereby exhibiting their brand loyalty (Kubina and Lendel, 2015a). Such brand advocates who have turned into brand loyalists strengthen the process of customer retention for the luxury fashion brand without the firm incurring any financial costs.

2.9 Critical analysis of social-CRM

According to Quinton (2013), the concept of social-CRM is important for fashion, as the consumer's self-concept and 'look good' factor in their social circle is an outward manifestation. Social-CRM is extremely relevant and important for the consumer who loves fashion brands and for the firms who manufacture them. This is a link between the two

entities - the customer and the luxury fashion brand - in a digital platform that provides impetus to exchange the elements of fashion in the social circle while both of them are playing the brand game (Harrigan and Miles, 2014). The pre- and post-purchase stages that the consumer passes through have found a more expressive medium and are inexpensive with faster-higher reach that social-CRM is able to render. The traditional model of the luxury fashion brand business has been partially eclipsed by social-CRM, as the immediacy of the technology enables the power of information for luxury fashion brand consumers and fashion retailers. This assists the flow of information across groups that meets the search information criteria and results in faster decision-making towards mental preparedness towards the fashion brands.

The free-flowing social-CRM is preferred by fashion firms as a fashion launch of new items or a seasonal launch is shared, talked and bought by consumers.

Figure 2: Free-flowing social-CRM

(Source: Harrigan and Miles, 2014)
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restrictions.

Fashion companies are gradually improving the logistics and supply chain towards social-CRM integration into their existing operations. Marolt et al. (2015) argue that customer interfacing in a social media network is helping to align their retail store and online operations simultaneously. The total process in fashion has become faster and customer-initiated, as a single purchase made by the customer post-fashion show creates a direct impact on the marketing lists, stock check at multiple points, fashion data modelling, operations KPI integration, mining and predictive systems about the seasonal variation in demand (Malthouse et al., 2013). Thus, social-CRM has been an enabler which provides optimisation models to the fashion brands and therefore, they are mostly popular with globally dispersed fashion labels which have GSCM (global supply chain management,) supplying items from one part of the world to other for luxury fashion brand showcasing in fashion shows.

The use of social media networks by the consumer post-purchase helps fashion companies to conduct a sentiment analysis which is integrated with the company's CRM system (Küpper et al., 2014). All of this renders more agility and increased visibility to the fashion manufacturing and consumption that is value-added. Real-time consumer actions result in multiple functions and entire business system taking automated decisions after analysis of the data. However, too much data is now being generated in eCRM, as websites, social media sites and social media networks are all tracing consumers' online behaviour (Harrigan et al., 2015). Although it is not

intrusive, this social-CRM system is able to map the luxury fashion brand consumer behaviour and preferences using cluster tools and to filter the relevant data.

The fashion marketing function is increasingly trying to combine its online and store-based behaviour to create pleasurable experiences. This omni-channel distribution presence (offline-physical and online-ecommerce) is a revolution in retailing that affects the customer experience (Ahmad et al., 2015). The omni-channel approach integrates both online and offline marketing strategies to provide a seamless shopping experience for customers.

This new approach testifies that customer engagement and CRM do not stop at just buying the product alone. It is amplified in the customer's social circle from a luxury fashion brand perspective and through experiential marketing that starts the moment the customer makes a purchase. Fashion firms wanting to reduce the risk of overproduction and underproduction are therefore increasingly reliant on the software mapped through their entire production and supply chain and retailing process (Ananda et al., 2015; Yoon and Sims, 2016). These insights with mobility across social networks are helping fashion firms to extract data for CRM that helps to build a connection with the brand and the customer's unique journey of experience shared on social media. This activity is one of the key game-changers in an online world and is creating business agility, increasing the forecasting power of fashion manufacturing brands, making the business systems more robust and assisting in measured decisions based on the social-CRM data (Ananda et al., 2015). There are suites available from software firms such as Microsoft Dynamics CRM online that offers marketing and communication facilities to be more agile. Nordstrom in the US and Burberry in the UK have implemented social-CRM in their company operations, integrating the end-to-end functions.

2.10 Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a construct that has gained much attention in the literature, particularly in the area of consumer behaviour. Customer satisfaction is a complete assessment of a product or service over a specific time period as an outcome of the experience that a consumer has after purchasing and consumption (Isac and Rusu, 2014). Terpstra and Verbeeten (2014) refer to the term as the customer's response towards an accomplishment based on the consumption of a product or service, or judgment about any of its characteristic attributes that provide a pleasurable level of fulfilment. At the same time, Radojevic et al. (2015) indicate that customer

satisfaction reflects the psychological state of contentment or discontentment, which is a feeling arrived at after a customer compares their expectations with their perceptions of the product or service performance. On the other hand, Zboja et al. (2016) emphasise customer dissatisfaction and defines a dissatisfied customer to be one whose expectations are ahead of the actual service interaction outcome. Meanwhile, a satisfied customer is considered to be an individual who feels delighted if the service interaction outcome either matches or exceeds their expectations.

Customer satisfaction comprises of two rudimentary positions, namely cumulative satisfaction and transaction-specific satisfaction. In this conceptual context, cumulative satisfaction is referred to as the consumption experience of a consumer over a prolonged time period with regards to a specific product or service. Meanwhile, Khan (2012) states that transaction-specific satisfaction assumes satisfaction to be the customers' overall assessment of their personal experience and response towards the service encounter, transaction or episode. To gain an in-depth understanding of the concept of customer satisfaction, several of the dominant and most widely accepted customer satisfaction theories are reviewed in subsequent sections of this chapter.

2.11 Customer satisfaction theories

A review of the existing literature indicates the presence of several theories that explain the process through which individuals as consumers tend to form satisfaction judgments. The theories of customer satisfaction may be categorised into three specific groups, namely:

- Expectancy disconfirmation theories
- Equity theories, and
- Attribution theories

According to Isac and Rusu (2014), the expectancy disconfirmation theory assumes that satisfaction judgements are formed by consumers through product/service evaluation. There are four different psychological theories that conceptually explain the impact of expectancy, and a few of the prominent theories are critically reviewed in this chapter. However, first it is be important to understand how 'satisfaction' is measured from the customer's perspective.

The core of the process of satisfaction is the comparison of what a consumer actually expects from a product/service, and this process is conventionally depicted as the ‘confirmation/disconfirmation’ process. The process is sequential in nature and starts with the customer’s expectations before buying and/or consuming a product and/or service, followed by its actual consumption and thereby experience with that product/service (Pizam et al., 2016). This experience generates a level of perceived quality. If the perceived performance of the product/service is moderately less than the anticipated performance, it will result in ‘assimilation’. Meanwhile, performance (perceived) will tend to be adjusted upward to balance expectation. In the same scenario, if perceived performance is far below customer expectation, the result will be ‘contrast’, and any deficit in the perceived performance will be overstated.

Figure 3: Satisfaction Function

As illustrated in Figure 3, the satisfaction function lies between expectations and perceived quality. When the performance of the product/service exceeds customer expectations, satisfaction tends to increase, albeit at a diminishing rate. Here disconfirmation increases when the perceived performance of the product or service falls below expectations.

Terpstra and Verbeeten (2014) elucidate that the determination of satisfaction is through subjective elements (fulfilling customer expectations, emotions and desires) and not objective elements (product and/or service attributes). As applied to the fashion industry, a range of studies have been conducted to identify the attributes that the customers consider important for satisfaction. Some of these factors are associated with customer relationships, customer service, staff behaviour, complaint management, price, fabric quality and service quality.

2.11.1 Consistency theories of customer satisfaction

Consistency theories indicate that lack of consistency between ‘what the customer actually expects from a product performance’ and ‘what has actually derived’ results in some degree of tension (Pizam et al., 2016). In an attempt to alleviate this tension, a consumer will try to make some adjustments either in the perception of the actual performance of the product/service, or expectations regarding the same (Pizam et al., 2016). Under the domain of the consistency approach to customer satisfaction, four underpinning theories have been proposed:

- Assimilation theory
- Contrast theory
- Assimilation-contrast theory
- Disconfirmation theory of customer satisfaction

2.11.2. Assimilation theory of consumer satisfaction

The basis of the assimilation theory of consumer satisfaction is the dissonance theory, wherein the latter hypothesises that consumers are involved in a cognitive comparison between their expectations of the product/service and perceptions about its performance. This perspective of the customer’s post-usage product evaluation has been integrated into the concept of customer satisfaction to propose the assimilation theory (Terpstra and Verbeeten, 2014).

The assimilation theory posits that consumers tend to evade dissonance by way of adjusting their perceptions to align them more closely with their expectations. Moreover, consumers are also capable of decreasing the tension arising out of the inconsistency between their expectations and actual performance of the product, either by deforming the expectations so that it matches with the perceived performance, or by increasing the satisfaction level by minimising the comparative significance of the disconfirmation experienced.

The assimilation theory is subject to several criticisms put forward by critics such as (Terpstra and Verbeeten, 2014). These authors argue that the theory assumes there is a correlation between customer expectations and customer satisfaction but fails to explain how disconfirmation of a particular expectation results in either satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

2.11.3 Contract theory of customer satisfaction

According to Isac and Rusu (2014), contrast theory also provides an alternative perspective of the consumer’s post-usage product evaluation process that was explained by the assimilation

theory. Contrast theory is built upon the idea of expanding the divergence between a consumer's own attitudes on the one hand, and the attitudes exhibited by the opinion statements on the other. Assimilation theory claims that consumers tend to reduce the disparities between their expectations and actual product performance. However, the contrast theory posits that a surprise effect takes place, resulting in the exaggeration of the discrepancy (Radojevic et al., 2015).

The contrast theory of customer satisfaction also holds that any divergence of experience from prior expectations will be overstated in the line of a discrepancy. For example, if the advertising message communicated by a fashion retailer raises expectations through promises, and later on the consumer experiences moderately less than what was promised in the advertisement, the related product/service will be discarded as fully unsatisfactory (Oh and Kim, 2017). In contrast, under-promises made in the advertisement but over-delivering in actuality will result in positive disconfirmation and will most likely be exaggerated (Oh and Kim, 2017).

Although the contrast theory of customer satisfaction is supported in the area of the literature related to marketing, the theory actually envisages customer reactions rather than reducing dissonance. The consumer will be likely to amplify the discrepancies between expectations and the actual product performance. Moreover, there hardly exists any empirical studies that test the validity of the claims made by the contrast theory in actual practice.

2.11.4 Assimilation-Contrast theory of customer satisfaction

The Assimilation-Contrast theory posits that if the performance of a product/service is within the range of consumer's acceptance, even if it falls short of expectations, the consumer will likely disregard the discrepancy. Consequently, assimilation will be activated, and the consumer will deem the performance as acceptable. In this context, Reimer and Becker (2015) note that the theory is conceptualised as yet another way of explaining the key relationship between the variables that the disconfirmation model encompasses. The Assimilation-Contrast theory integrates both the assimilation and the contrast approach to conceptualising consumer satisfaction (Cao et al., 2016). The theory also explains satisfaction to be a function of the degree of the divergence between the expected product performance and the perceived product performance. With regards to the assimilation theory, it posits that the consumers will be likely to assimilate or adjust the disparity in perceptions regarding product performance to align it with preceding expectations, but only if the divergence is comparatively low (Khan, 2015).

The Assimilation-Contrast theory of customer satisfaction explains that both the assimilation and the contrast ideologies can be made applicable to the study of customer satisfaction.

Figure 4: Assimilation-Contrast theory of customer satisfaction

Similar to the other theories of customer satisfaction, the Assimilation-Contrast theory is not free from scholarly criticism. For instance, the integration of, most specifically, reconciliation between the ‘contrast’ and the ‘assimilation’ approaches is methodologically flawed (Zboja et al., 2016). In addition, the attempts made to test this theory empirically in real-life organisations have produced mixed results.

2.11.5 Disconfirmation theory of customer satisfaction

According to Lankton and McKnight (2012), the disconfirmation theory of customer satisfaction posits that satisfaction is associated with the size and direction of the experience of disconfirmation that takes place as a consequence of comparing performance standards against prior expectations. Emphasising this theory, Liao et al. (2011) state that satisfaction is the customer’s response towards the fulfilment of a product or service. The author also explains satisfaction to be a judgment or verdict that the product or service attributes, or the entire

product or service, have delivered, or are delivering an enjoyable degree of fulfilment relating to its consumption, together with levels of under-or over-fulfilment.

Figure 5: Disconfirmation theory of customer satisfaction

(Source: Liao et al., 2011)
Content redacted due to
copyright restrictions.

Liao et al. (2011) suggest that the disconfirmation theory is the most popular and dynamic theory of customer satisfaction, based on the proposition that satisfaction is the outcome of the direct experience that a consumer has with the product or service and occurs when perceptions are matched against performance standards (expectations).

2.12 Customer dissatisfaction

The issue of retention evolves when there is a failure of the promised delivery and the consumer faces the reality of the negative side of customer satisfaction. The satisfaction continuum also has a darker side of the operations as their performance of the company fails to meet the customer expectation sets which leads to bad user experience (Berezina et al., 2016). Satisfaction has been defined in terms of an outcome of a process, cognitive evaluation, affective evaluation, connotative elements, and from the viewpoint of general fulfilment of

needs. The literature on dissatisfaction, however, tries to link the one-dimensional element of whether the absent factors of satisfaction assist in leaning towards the dissatisfaction scale.

Cameron et al. (2016) have tried to understand the intensity of dissatisfaction by linking it to the operational outcome. Thus, 'completely dissatisfied', 'very dissatisfied' and 'dissatisfied' are the ratings towards the expression of the emotional responses towards a situation that has not met consumer expectations. However, it has been rather difficult to define dissatisfaction in the same way that the satisfaction arena has been quite comprehensively defined (Pizam et al., 2016). However, some authors propose that even dissatisfaction has three components: an effective response - which has a definitive focal point - and that the event happens at the determined time. The research outlines that the feeling of dissatisfaction is more profound in terms of response or how the customer feels. Consumers are likely to express their experience of being angry, furious or cheated with the strongest responses to a failure or service or a product not meeting their set of expectations (Kumar, 2016; Ibrahimi et al., 2016). More muted responses are feeling bored or simply not being interested, which the customers state in order to discontinue any existing relationship with the brand. Dissatisfaction can start before the satisfaction process has even started and this then stays with the consumer for a longer duration, fostering the negativity which tries to escape out of the customer's mind (Kumar, 2016; Ibrahimi et al., 2016; Javed and Cheema, 2017).

2.13 Models of customer satisfaction measurement

2.13.1 SERVQUAL model

Service quality, according to Parasuraman et al. (1985), is referred to as the global assessment of overall service excellence. It is also defined as the level of service that helps to meet or exceed customer expectations. Service quality, unlike the quality of products, may not be measured objectively; instead, it needs to be measured subjectively. Service quality, as observed by the customer, comprises of three dimensions, namely the functional dimension (the process of service delivery), technical (service outcomes generated for the customer) and image (company image built in the customers' mind) (Gronroos, 1984). Considering these customer perspectives in the retail business environment, the functional dimension exemplifies how retail store personnel communicate with customers during their store visit. On the other

hand, the technical part of service demonstrates how effectively the customer problems and issues are resolved or how well customer complaints are handled.

According to Lehtinen and Lehtinen (1991), service quality may be defined in their different elements, i.e. (i) physical quality, (ii) interactive quality, and (iii) corporate image quality. Physical quality is associated with the tangible elements of service, while interactive quality is about the nature of service-related interaction between the customer and service providers, including the effectiveness of communication between them. The third dimension refers to the service provider's image in the mind of existing and potential customers.

Another model of service quality propounded by Parasuraman et al. (1985,) and known as SERVQUAL, was initially studied in various service sectors such as long-distance communication, motor repairs, banking and credit card services, etc. According to Parasuraman et al. (1988), the 'SERVQUAL' instrument is widely applicable to a range of service industries as a means of measuring customer satisfaction. However, it is also used by organisations specialising in selling products but who maintain a service-dominant logic in their marketing-mix strategies. The SERVQUAL model includes a 22-item scale designed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) and addresses several dimensions of service quality categorised into tangibility, reliability, assurance, responsiveness and empathy.

The SERVQUAL model conceptualises that the measurement of service quality is achieved by understanding the gaps between customer expectations of the rendered service and their discernment about the actual service performance. The first dimension, **tangibility**, relates to the physical attributes linked to the service encounter, such as the physical locations, surroundings, the interior design, cleanliness, appearance of the employees, etc.

Reliability refers to the ability of the service provider to deliver dependable services that are precise, consistent and perform according to customer expectations (Parasuraman et al. 1988). The firm should be capable of delivering the right service from the very first time the customer requires it, and on an ongoing basis. **Responsiveness** is about the willingness of service personnel to provide fast and timely services to the customer. **Assurance** refers to the varied features that make the customer feel confident about the service offerings. This necessitates customer-facing employees such as the front-line staff to be knowledgeable and adequately trained to provide prompt answers to the customer's queries. **Empathy** is about the firm's eagerness to provide customised services to the customer in accordance with their specific requirements.

Figure 6: Gap model of Service Quality

(Source: Parasuraman et al., 1988) **Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.**

Customer satisfaction with the service quality is measured by comparing customer expectations with customer discernment of the actual performance of services. If the customer perceptions exceed customer expectations, the services are considered as excellent. Meanwhile, if customer perceptions are equal to customer expectations, the services are categorised as good. Finally, if the customer expectations go beyond perceptions, the services are regarded to be bad.

Previously, several studies were carried out by researchers to measure customer satisfaction using a service quality model such as SERVQUAL. Parasuraman et al. (1988) found that each of the SERVQUAL elements – tangibility, reliability, assurance, responsiveness, and empathy - positively impact customer satisfaction and inferred that service quality was a critical factor to keep customers satisfied. Parasuraman et al. (1988) used the SERVQUAL model to study the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction and found that service quality was a forecaster of the level of customer satisfaction, and each of the dimensions had a significant impact on customer satisfaction.

Although the SERVQUAL concept is a generally accepted model for measuring service quality, it has been criticised on methodological and conceptual grounds. The use of expectations as a standard comparison construct has been criticised by Parasuraman et al. (1988), who argue that expectations are vibrant in nature and are subject to change in accordance to the consumption situation and experiences of the customers. Moreover, the

applicability of the SERVQUAL elements in different service settings is questionable and repeat studies carried out by researchers have failed to advocate the five-dimensional factor structures as originally proposed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) in their conceptualisation of the model.

The SERVQUAL model is appropriate for purely service-oriented companies, whereas retail firms provide both products and services to the customers simultaneously. Other researchers such as Ravichandran (2010) also find the SERVQUAL model to be unsuitable for studying service quality provided by firms in the retail industry. As a result, an explicit quality measurement tool for measuring services was designed by Dabholkar et al. (1996), known as the Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS).

2.13.2 Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS)

According to Dabholkar et al. (1996), the measures designed to study the quality of services in a pure service setting such as SERVQUAL are not compatible when used to measure the service quality for retail firms. The Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS) model helps to measure five different dimensions of service quality of a store and takes into account a total of 28 items. Out of these, eleven are borrowed from SERVQUAL while the remaining ones are items developed by conducting qualitative research. The main dimensions of the RSQS model are (i) physical aspects; (ii) reliability; (iii) personal interaction; (iv) problem solving; and (v) policy.

In the RSQS model, Dabholkar et al. (1996) incorporate the aforementioned dimensions in the form of a structured hierarchy (see Figure 7). Each dimension in the model is further subdivided into more understandable elements explaining the meaning of each one. Physical aspects represent the layout of the store, aesthetics, interior decoration, comfort, space to move around and tidiness, etc. Reliability relates to the competency of the employees to fulfil promises and deliver the right service performance from the outset. Personal interaction is about the behaviour and attitude of the service personnel, such as being polite, courteous, friendly, and being able to instil confidence in the customer. Problem-solving relates to the approach undertaken by the firm to help customers in the context of exchange, returns, and complaints in a satisfactory manner. Policy refers to the set of rules that are designed to provide

convenience to the customer, such as flexible operating hours, easy payment options, ease of merchandise exchange and return, parking space availability, etc.

Figure 7: The Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS)

(Source: Dabholkar et al., 1996) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

The RSQS model has been widely used by researchers in various retail settings in different industrial sectors and the measurement scale is valid for a retail store environment. While measuring service quality is important in the retail store environment, equally as important is the measurement of the quality of the products (Culiberg and Rojsek, 2010) and hence, the following section reviews the concept of product quality. In a retail store environment such as high street fashion stores, the importance of both service quality and product quality are considered necessary for customer satisfaction.

2.13.2.1 Product quality

Product quality refers to the extent to which a product is able to meet the customer's needs and expectations. The product-based approach perceives quality from an economic perspective and

considers any variation in quality to affect differentiation (Friederichsen and Bendig, 2016). While a product is an important constituent of the marketing mix, product quality is considered to be the characteristic attribute of this element that determines the consumer's intention to choose or avoid a product. As a crucial ingredient for firms to earn competitive advantage, product quality is often maintained throughout the entire product development process in order to enhance its performance and consequently achieve higher customer satisfaction (Choi et al., 2016; Friederichsen and Bendig, 2016).

Product quality is considered to be the basis of strategic advantage, implying that improvement in product quality motivates existing customers to purchase more, repeat those purchases and also recommend the product/brand to others (Jiang et al., 2016). In this context, product image is more important than physical characteristics when it comes to customer retention. While maintaining superior product quality is important, it is also crucial to develop superior service quality in terms of customer service and relationships in order to enhance the brand image of the product. Customers not only perceive the quality of the products to be superior, but also appreciate the associated service attributes which help them to evaluate their overall experience with the product usage, satisfaction and the intention to be loyal to the brand.

Emphasising the search properties of a product, Trentin et al. (2012) consider traits such as colour, size, smell, style, fit and price. Search properties are explained to be those product characteristics and service features that customers prefer to compare and evaluate before making the final purchase. In addition, Lee and Shin (2014) elucidate that products have higher search qualities relative to services, with more qualities of credence. Credence qualities are the characteristic features of a product that can be difficult to differentiate, even after product consumption. Meanwhile, experience properties are the characteristic attributes that can only be assessed by the customer after use and actual consumption.

2.13.2.2 Product quality dimensions

Garvin (1984) conceptualise eight different product quality dimensions and categorise them as (a) features; (b) performance; (c) conformance; (d) reliability; (e) serviceability; (f) durability; (g) aesthetics; and (h) perceived quality.

Product features refer to the characteristics and attributes of the product that complement its core functionality. Performance is about the basic operating characteristics and usability of the product as evaluated by the end-user. Reliability, in the context of a product, is defined as the

product's potentiality of performance without failure over a prolonged time period (Sebastianelli and Tamimi, 2013). In other words, it is the dependability of the product that it is able to perform according to the confirmed specifications and promises made by the provider. Durability is the measure of the functional product life and refers to the extent of use derived by a customer until it depreciates and needs replacement. Conformance refers to the extent to which the physical characteristics of the product, its performance, and the output derived to meet the design specifications (Sebastianelli and Tamimi, 2013). In the area of product quality, serviceability refers to the speed, ease and proficiency of product repair. Aesthetics is the description of the product appearance, taste, feel, smell, etc. which relate to individual preferences of each customer. Performance quality refers to the distinctiveness of the product based on a brand name, image, and/or advertising that can be subjectively evaluated.

According to the claims made by Karipidis (2011), product quality is a strategic concept that governs or helps marketers control the product design development along with its characteristics or options. Developing the product design, however, requires setting up strategic objectives as part of a business strategy to bring improvements to the product, processes, and the services associated with it. Emphasising the importance of product quality, Hassan and Shaharudin (2011) link two important elements with its usability, as 'form' and 'function'. While the product form representing the external features such as shape, size, colour, weight, and packaging is important, more important is its function as an intrinsic quality such as performance. Trentin et al. (2012) explain the form to be the impression and image that a customer has about a product, while function is closely associated with its usefulness and performance.

After reviewing the RSQS model, it can be inferred that maintaining both service quality and product quality in a retail store environment is crucial for achieving increased customer satisfaction and for facilitating their intention to make repeat visits. It is also evident that both, product quality and service quality have distinct dimensions, even though dimensions such as 'reliability' are common in both, emphasising the importance of product/service dependability. The next section in this chapter conducts a critical review of the Kano model as a model of customer satisfaction measurement.

2.13.3 Kano Model

Based on Herzberg's satisfaction and dissatisfaction dimensions, Kano et al. (1984) proposed a model that has elements of product development elements (see Figure 8). This model provides an insight into understanding the five types of customer requirements across the product or service sectors that need to be considered in order to be competitive. The purpose of the model is to show how each of these five universal elements help to generate satisfaction and dissatisfaction. In the model, there are two categories that 'add value' and two categories which 'detract from value', while another creates 'new value' (Turisová, 2014; Rotar and Kozar, 2017). It is designed to understand the customer's own needs, a mechanism which helps firms to prioritise their developments that affect the satisfaction and loyalty, termed as 'Kano analysis'.

According to Lin et al., (2015) and Rotar and Kozar (2017), the Kano Model helps to measure customer satisfaction by categorising the attributes based on how customers perceive them and the impact on their satisfaction. The Kano Model conceptualises three categories of attributes, namely (i) basic/expected attributes, (ii) spoken or performance attributes, and (iii) delight and surprise attributes.

Figure 8: Kano Model

(Source: Adapted from Kano et al., 1984)

The basic/expected attributes relate to the fundamental attributes that can be delivered in the usual course of business activities by the firm. The performance attributes are identified to be the customer expectations that are expressed by the end users, while the delight attributes reflect those elements that go beyond customer expectations (Kano et al., 1984).

The Kano Model can be used to measure the level of customer satisfaction against their perceptions of the performance of attributes. This model also assumes that customer satisfaction may not always be relative to how functional the product and/or service is. Alternatively, this implies that higher quality may not necessarily result in higher customer satisfaction for all the product or the service attributes.

The model posits that three types of fundamental requirements influence the satisfaction level of consumers. These fundamental requirements are, (i) must-be requirements, which if not met, will lead to extreme customer dissatisfaction; if these requirements are taken by the customer as granted, their accomplishment would not increase the satisfaction level; (ii) one-dimensional requirements are the specific demands that the customer has, i.e. the higher the fulfilment level, the higher the likelihood of customer satisfaction and vice versa; (iii) attractive requirements encompass the product and/or service criteria that tend to have the utmost influence on the customer's satisfaction level with a given product. With reference to the Kano model, Bonacorsi (2010) explains that additional attributes are identified as questionable attributes, indifferent attributes, and reverse attributes.

Must-be quality: The requirements which the customer expects to be in a product or service are called the 'must-be quality'. A poor performance by companies in this respect leads to customer dissatisfaction; conversely, if accompany meets the customer expectation set by conforming to the requirements, then the customer response is neutral. They are essential and core to the process and the price of these features must be built into the product. The first and most important aspect of the Kano model, is the key factor which results in innovation into the existing threshold quality of the process (Turisová, 2014; Chen, 2015; Rotar and Kozar, 2017).

One dimensional quality: These are attributes which result in the satisfaction of the customer and which if not met, will lead to dissatisfaction. It is a performance attribute that is a blend of skill, knowledge and ability, and job performance as the output. Companies prioritise these to strategize and link them to the performance model, where better performance is equated to the improved customer satisfaction logic. However, it is only when customers discuss 'how much' the intensity, their needs or gaps are understood. The product or service is then weighted in

terms of product function, the value received by the customer and the willingness of the customer to pay for the product or service (Bricci et al., 2016). Conversely, the price the customer pays is linked to the performance attribute, as prioritisation matrices are used to determine which of those quality elements is providing the greatest returns on customer satisfaction.

Attractive quality: This is defined as those attributes which achieve the satisfaction of the customer but when not fulfilled, they do not cause dissatisfaction (Tontini and Silveira, 2007). This is the excitement attribute, as it has not previously been perceived by the customer. However, it is up to them to discover the excitement attribute in the product or service. The author states it is an unknown need which is enlightened and creates a significant customer delight factor in return. The more the customer uses it, the more the excitement builds a competitive advantage for the company against its competitors. This actually triggers wants and needs in the mind of the consumer and is a powerful method to deliver any attribute to the customer.

Indifference quality: These attributes refer to those aspects of the product or service that are neither good nor bad or which fail to evoke either any customer dissatisfaction or satisfaction. Customers classify them as a part of the product design or service process at the default level.

Reverse quality: These are the attributes which are explained as a higher degree of high-quality product or service that leads to dissatisfaction. This is where customers are not happy with a feature-rich product or service that is too complex and therefore affects its usage and leads to difficulty.

Thus, the model identifies those **necessary elements**, the absence of which results in customer dissatisfaction, while conversely, their presence does not increase the satisfaction level. There are also **enthusiasm factors**, which increase satisfaction levels when present but do not cause dissatisfaction if absent (Slevitch and Oh, 2010). The final aspect is the performance factors that can swing both ways towards satisfaction or dissatisfaction depending on the product or service performance that either reaches or fails the customer expectation set.

Satisfaction drivers terminology^[2]

Author(s)	Driver type 1	Driver type 2	Driver type 3	Driver type 4
Herzberg et al. (1959) ^[3]	Hygiene	Motivator		
Kano (1984) ^[4]	Must-be	Attractive	One-dimensional	Indifferent
Cadotte and Turgeon (1988) ^[5]	Dissatisfier	Satisfier	Critical	Neutral
Brandt (1988) ^[6]	Minimum requirement	Value enhancing	Hybrid	Unimportant as determinant
Venkitaraman and Jaworski (1993) ^[7]	Flat	Value-added	Key	Low
Brandt and Scharioth (1998) ^[8]	Basic	Attractive	One-dimensional	Low impact
Llosa (1997, ^[9] 1999 ^[10])	Basic	Plus	Key	Secondary

Bleuel (1990) finds that there is no similarity between satisfaction and dissatisfaction drivers, while several authors conclude that dissatisfaction sources may or may not be the opposite for causing the satisfaction drivers. Thus, for every product or service, there are a different set of factors which can be analysed through a different angle; one to identify the satisfiers and the other for dissatisfiers. Unyathanakorn and Rompho (2014) carried out research where respondents typically cited the positives and negatives independently and none of them had any relationship that could be established. The application of marketing systems has been extended to capture these indicators separately and manage the framework of a complaint about a company in order to manage the customer's dissatisfaction level. Although complaints handling is not a substitute for achieving customer satisfaction, it is a process of an audit tool to reduce complaints and cognitive dissonance.

2.13.4 ACSI (American Customer Satisfaction Index) Model

The ACSI model is a strategic business framework that can be customised according to organisational requirements for the purpose of gaining competitive advantage. The model is an accurate and dependable predictor of customer spending and as a consequence, the resulting corporate earnings (Lee et al., 2016). The model includes a set of equations that associate (i) customer expectations with (ii) perceived quality and (iii) perceived value to customer satisfaction. In addition, customer satisfaction is associated with the benefits and outcomes as illustrated by customer loyalty and advocacy for the company, measured by tolerance towards price, retention, and the extent of customer complaints or referrals.

Deng et al. (2013) elucidate that for most firms, repeat customer visits or re-purchases are crucial for business profitability and consequently essential for financial performance. Firms, therefore, integrate ACSI with their financial information, and the net worth of the existing

customer base considered as long-term assets becomes calculable. The elements included in the ACSI model encompass customer expectations, where customers integrate their experiences with the offerings and information regarding it via previous usage or experience, communication, an advertisement about the same, and word-of-mouth promotions from other customers (Deng et al., 2013). Customer expectations also tend to influence the quality assessment and anticipation (from their pre-purchase viewpoint) regarding the performance of the product or service.

2.14 Hirschman's exit and voice theory

The economist Albert Hirschman (1970) explained that in a case of duopoly where neither the firm is actively encouraging complaints, the use of defensive strategy in complaints management is helpful. The author deployed a mathematical model to find out the market structure and found that over a period of time, complaints management helps to increase the company's market share. He examined the list of dissatisfaction types and intensities over a period of time to find that those are the customer wants. According to microeconomics, exit is a power market mechanism correction force that happens when the company fails to meet the customer expectation set. The author stated that customer withdrawal or a shift in buying choices is a punishment for the company, as exits cause revenues to shrink. Those firms which have limited customers can identify them more readily, as they are sensitive to each customer exit.

Thus, an exit is economic activity, while the voice of the customer is a more political perspective. Where a company does not pay heed to customer complaints or requests, this does not affect the market but ignoring them from the firm's perspective is a cost to the company that needs a retention strategy. Firm-level 'alert' or 'inert' customers show that inert ones are the source of voice (non-existing customers) expressing concern for those have already exited. This theoretical construct shows the interplay of customer choices to express opinion or voice concern. Voice does not involve a loss of revenue until the consumer decides to exit, so in fact it is a chance for the company addressing the concern to ensure it is fixed (Allen, 2014; Chisholm et al., 2016).

The value of customer dissatisfaction translates to certain types of demands which indicate a newer prototype and a different need and market segment is created. This is also a different

type of customer variety, which in a non-growth market leads to less competition, as the total number of customers in the population remains the same (Kaufman, 2014). Kaufman (2014) cites that affective discomfort of a customer increases to strength when the purchase consumption process by the consumer returns insufficient return when compared to the relative resources spent. The consumer usually spends time, money and energy to derive a utility value, but deteriorating experiences over a period of time forces them to switch to other brands. The author states that the value of complaints is immense, as attending to them leads to satisfaction being restored instead of exit though compensation needs to fuel the return behaviour of the dissatisfied customers. The faltering company need to realise the cost of switching to be compensated, as the customer is likely to repurchase if their demands are met. Hirschman's exit and voice theory supports the offensive and defensive marketing strategy tenets, as companies need to change their approach of strategy and use it as communication device in order to align the firm towards consumer demand trends (Allen, 2014; Chisholm et al., 2016).

2.15 Impact of marketing strategies on customer satisfaction

A strategy may be referred to as a set of plans or an action plan that helps a firm to accomplish its specific goals and objectives in a particular time period. Marketing strategy, therefore, involves a tactical plan of action regarding how a firm intends to pursue its goals and accomplish its marketing objectives (Al-Hersh and Saaty, 2014; Bramulya et al., 2016; Edeling and Fischer, 2016). It is also defined as a process that incorporates the strategic analysis of the business environment and an understanding of the competitiveness of the organisation (Al-Hersh and Saaty, 2014). In addition, marketing strategies also involve identifying the external and internal factors that affect the business units, projecting the changing business trends and formulating strategies to respond to such changes (Aka et al., 2016; Sun and Price, 2016). Marketing strategies allow firms to contemplate the available resources for optimal business opportunities with the intention of increasing sales and sustaining their competitive advantage.

Based on this statement, marketing strategy can also be explained as an organisational strategy that integrates its overall marketing goals into a singular extensive plan. The most important perspective of marketing strategy is that it incorporates designing corporate level strategies as well as business unit strategies (Rizan et al., 2014; Kumar, 2016). Marketing strategies also incorporate the design of fundamental and long-term marketing activities of a firm that embraces its strategic direction, as well as the formulation, assessment and finalisation of marketing-oriented tactics that help to pursue the organisational goals and marketing

objectives. These strategies are mainly directed towards meeting the short-term and long-term objectives of the firm, including customer satisfaction which occupies the primary goal of any organisation.

A review of the literature indicates that the terms ‘corporate strategy’ and ‘marketing strategy’ are often used interchangeably. However, corporate strategy comprises those actions undertaken by the top management in determining the purpose, scope, mission and vision of the organisation, along with the actions and resources needed to accomplish the business objectives (Baines et al., 2011). Meanwhile, marketing strategy relates to a narrow construct of the corporate strategy and includes the actions that help a firm to compete in a particular business setting and position itself among its rivals.

2.16 Types of marketing strategies

Different organisations implement different types of marketing strategies and design, develop and adapt them according to the unique business environment in which they operate. The current literature explores and discusses a few of the core marketing strategies that impact the level of customer satisfaction in a given business environment.

2.16.1 Push marketing strategies

Push strategy in marketing relates to the development of marketing processes that originate from the firm and move towards the market. In this context, the firm invents, designs and introduces a product or service that attempts to find its own buyers; therefore, the firm sustains its supply (Shaw, 2012). The usual tactics for product sales in push strategy involves a company making attempts to sell merchandise to customers directly via its own outlets, showrooms or stores and conducting negotiations with retailers to push the sales or establish point-of-sale (POS) displays (Pantano and Viassone, 2014). These retailers are often endorsed with special incentives for maintaining enhanced visibility of the products through product displays.

A general example of this marketing strategy is observed in department stores selling a perfume range. The manufacturer of the perfume range would offer incentives to the owner of the department store to push its products at a certain price to its customers. This marketing technique is particularly beneficial for novel brands that are not well established or where a new range of products within a given brand requires aggressive promotions. For most

consumers, visiting a store and being introduced to a product is their preliminary experience with that product, and they would be unlikely to ask for it if they did not know it existed. This strategy is mainly concerned with short-term sales (Baker, 2014). From a manufacturer's perspective, establishing distribution channels, hiring middle-men, brokers or retailers is important to stock the product and make them easily available to consumers. Pantano and Viassone (2014) argue that the push strategy works especially well for lower value products such as fast-moving consumer goods, which are of everyday use and for which consumers regularly visit retailers to purchase them. Moreover, a push marketing technique is suitable for items which require consumers to make a purchase decision at the point of sale rather than postponing the decision for the future.

The basis of an application for push strategies is a stable environment, wherein corporate processes (such as communication and information flow) could be successfully reiterated (Quirke, 2017). The competitiveness of push strategies is based on accrued experiences, which are developed by repeating similar marketing activities in a timely manner and on a broad range of activities which are made possible by a stable context which helps to organise the business and exploit the market. In the case of push strategy, economies of scale and benefits of experience can be accomplished to develop rigid, yet competitive cost structures, particularly when competitors are not in a position to implement the same strategy.

2.16.2 Pull marketing strategies

Pull strategy, on the other hand, is a marketing process that initiates from the market and moves towards the firm (Shaw, 2012), thereby following the opposite approach. In this case, supply is requested by demand and pulled out of the firm. The need to design and introduce a new product is stimulated from the market and this emerges in response to the pull action of demand (Pantano and Viassone, 2014). Usual sales techniques in this marketing strategy include promotions through mass media, advertised sales promotions and word-of-mouth referrals. From the perspective of a business, this form of marketing endeavours to perpetuate brand loyalty and ensure repeat customer purchase, i.e. customers availing the product and/or service repeatedly (Kotler et al., 2015). Pull marketing is undertaken in the form of marketing campaigns using extensive advertising for making the brand and its related products a household name.

Quirke (2017) considers both push and pull strategies to be alternatives, as both are based on two different market presumptions (the demand characteristics and characteristics of the

financial system of competition, and supplier system) that necessitate varying resources and capabilities from firms. Baker (2014) insinuates that push techniques presume comprehensive knowledge of the market, the needs of key stakeholders (competition and demand) and of their dynamics. This subsequently facilitates advance planning of those corporate activities required to carry out process-oriented steps to product realisation that allow a firm to accomplish superior commercial outcomes. In the case of pull strategy, the firm is incapable of building extensive market knowledge and knowledge about its competitors, which are typified by dynamism and changeability of their needs and actions (Smilansky, 2017). Therefore, Kotler et al. (2017) argue that planning commercial activities is very risky and difficult to carry out for a prolonged time period. These authors assert that the environment for the implementation of pull marketing tactics is an unstable context, wherein the same commercial processes may not be repeated successfully.

Figure 9: Push and pull marketing

(Source: Pantano and Viassone, 2014) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Corporate competitiveness is not established based on the development of inflexible cost structures that are progressively reduced with time, and the competitive forces of pull marketing rest in their capabilities to respond to the existing market. Pantano and Viassone

(2014) point out the competitiveness of pull marketing strategy lies in its potential to respond to the changing demand before the existing market competition, and this is applicable both to material flows as well as communication and information flows.

According to Smilansky (2017), products or brands that define their customers use push marketing to push their products to the masses through distributors or retailers, for instance fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) that involve simple consumer decision-making. However, in the case of **luxury fashion brands**, the company attempts to pull consumers towards the product or brand with the assurance of belonging to a distinctive community. Luxury endorses human emotions in alignment with pleasure, recognition and self-elevation rather than 'prevention' emotions built around problem-solving or reduction of risk (Atwal and Williams, 2017).

2.16.3 Market dominance strategy

Market dominance strategy makes every effort to place the product and/or service of the company ahead of other available brands. Using this marketing strategy, a firm strategizes to achieve market dominance by offering differentiated products, price cuts or services that exceed customer expectations (Yang and Chao, 2017; Blevins et al., 2017). These marketing strategies are directed towards leading the existing market or to challenge the current market leader. Organisations within the market dominance strategy are able to categorise themselves in accordance with their market share.

Those companies following this marketing strategy can be classified into four explicit areas, namely market leaders, followers, challengers and those holding a niche market. A leading company usually has the potential to hold and control the largest market share of a particular product and/or service (Palmer et al., 2014; Parker and Wang, 2016). The marketing objectives of such a company incorporate the expansion of its overall market share, continuously increasing its market share and protecting its present market position. On the other hand, a market follower strives to imitate the products and services of the market leader that possesses the highest market share. In doing so, the follower makes strategies that attempt to lure away customers of the market leader and increase its own customer base by offering almost identical goods and services at a competitive price that is either similar or lower than that of the leader (Palmer et al., 2014; Parker and Wang, 2016; Santouridis and Veraki, 2017).

A market challenger incorporates marketing strategies that are intended to attack both the market leader and the followers operating in the same market. Firms following market challenger tactics are usually aggressive and may implement disruptive strategies that are difficult to resist (Patterson, 2016; Wahyuningtyas et al., 2017). Market challengers target market conditions such as the vulnerability of the leaders or followers and attempt to attract their unsatisfied customers, adapt to better technology and attack rivals through aggressive promotional strategies. They may also likely to expose the market needs that the leaders fail to serve or recognise a shift in the customer segment to be served in a different way.

A firm pursuing the market challenging strategy often makes use of an offensive strategy, while market leaders employ a defensive marketing approach. The former could attack their opponents by identifying their weaknesses and could try to match their pricing, advertising, product and segmentation strategies in an aggressive manner- known as a front attack. The market challenger could also penetrate into those markets where the opponents' products and/or services have not made the highest impact- known as a flank attack. In this context, Paswan et al. (2011) explain that a roundabout assault strategy of a firm following the market challenger approach is the bypass strategy. Whereas the market challenger could be involved in strategizing how to capture a greater market share and achieve a dominant position, the market leader focuses on increasing strength by using its own resources to develop an unconquerable reinforcement around the market share (Paswan et al., 2011; Patterson, 2016; Kanten and Darma, 2017). The market leader could also extend its supremacy to unexploited markets through brand proliferation, superior customer services, product diversification and investing in corporate social responsibility to enhance its brand image (Baines et al., 2011). Soyoung and Jongeun (2011) point out that companies inhabiting a market niche target the smaller market segment where the customers can be satisfied without confronting the rival firms. Such firms are, however, involved in research and development (R&D) programs to identify the gaps, whereas the opponents assign resources to ensure higher customer satisfaction.

2.16.4 Marketing mix strategy

The marketing mix comprises of elements such as the product, price, place and promotions, while the extended mix incorporates the service-dominant logic such as people, process and physical evidence. The marketing mix is used as a conceptual framework by firms, particularly senior marketing managers, to make marketing decisions in terms of configuring the mix to

satisfy the varying needs of their customers (O’Cas and Heirati, 2015). Marketing strategy is associated with designing an appropriate marketing mix which helps firms to offer the right product at the right price in the right place in order to satisfy the varying customer needs (Wongleedee, 2015; Festa et al., 2016). The choice of the right product, right price and right place/distribution must, however, be supported by attractive advertising and promotions by making use of the right marketing mix. In this context, Schultz and Dev (2012) explain that the term ‘right’ is perceived as the customers’ response to the most appropriate product and/or service. Therefore, in order to design the right marketing mix, firms need to offer products with the right attributes, combined with the right price, i.e. distributed or made available at the right price, and also need to make the target segments aware of the available offerings using the right promotional techniques.

Firms in the contemporary business environment lay key emphasis on the extended marketing mix to strengthen their marketing strategy. **The process** involves strengthening the systems followed to help the firm in delivering the products or services smoothly (Chumaidiyah, 2013). The transaction process, operational process and the entire value chain system are strengthened to add value to the services offered. **The people** factor involves maintaining a well-trained staff to serve customers and treating them as the most valuable form of social assets. The people factor also involves valuing the customers, engaging them, understanding their needs and expectations, and designing the marketing mix accordingly to fulfil the same (O’Cas and Heirati, 2015; Festa et al., 2016). **Physical evidence** involves the overall layout and design of the organisational premise, store facilities, ease of movement, ambience, neatness, etc. In the case of online businesses, the website needs to be attractive, navigable, easy to use and informative, with a safe payment gateway that maintains security of the customers’ personal and financial data (Azeem and Sharma, 2015; Abril and Rodriguez-Cánovas, 2016).

In addition to the marketing mix elements, firms adapting the marketing mix strategy could also involve the integration of 4C’s of marketing, namely the customer solution, convenience, cost and communication (O’Cas and Heirati, 2015; Festa et al., 2016; Goworek et al., 2016). Communication effectiveness refers to meaningful interaction, formal or informal, between buyers and sellers in a timely manner. It keeps the customers updated regarding any arrivals, offers, discounts, or similar other promotions effectively and conveniently using the most appropriate communication channels (Schultz and Dev, 2012). This is a more customer-focused strategy which involves offering a seamless solution to customers by way of tailoring the products and services that suit their needs at a competitive price, making them available at

places where they can conveniently access them and fostering two-way communication, such as the use of social media (Wongleedee, 2015; Festa et al., 2016; Rios, 2016)

2.16.5 Innovative marketing strategy

Innovative marketing strategy involves maintaining a higher differentiation or cutting-edge technology that is difficult for others to imitate. It is an advanced marketing action plan to foster advancement in technology through investment in superior research and development programs (Zeriti et al., 2014). An innovative marketing strategy could involve market disruption, wherein the firm introduces a new product or service that has matchless features that competitors cannot copy. For instance, the launch of the innovative iPhone with its different versions by Apple was an innovative marketing strategy that received extensive customer advocacy and disrupted the mobile phone industry worldwide. Innovative marketing strategies could also involve the incorporation of new technology in the existing business model, such as the use of RFID (radio frequency identification) (Persaud and Azhar, 2012). Ramaseshan et al. (2013) argue that innovation in marketing strategies is usually brought in the service capabilities, i.e. by strengthening the quality of services delivered to the customers. Digital marketing trends such as the use of big data, Social-CRM, Internet of Things (IoT) and mobile marketing through smartphone apps are a few of the innovations that have revolutionised the current marketing landscape and their use have resulted in higher customer satisfaction (Nufer, 2013).

2.16.6 Market development and expansion strategy

Market development and expansion strategies relate to marketing approaches intended to achieve higher market growth. As explained by Bang and Joshi (2012), market expansion incorporates four types of growth strategies, namely horizontal integration, diversification, vertical integration and strengthening of growth strategies. Horizontal integration is a marketing strategy that incorporates activities to reduce costs, enhance market power, share resources and implement sales promotions to sell more of the same products. Vertical integration involves strategies to gain access to distribution channels (downstream), seize upstream profit margins and control cost of transportation (Bang and Joshi, 2012). Diversification incorporates the development of new products internally, acquisition of smaller firms, investment into new product licensing and the formation of new partnerships with other firms to share resources, mitigate risks and facilitate knowledge transfer and technology

knowhow (Bang and Joshi, 2012; Palmer et al.,2014; Blevins et al., 2017). Intensification strategy is a market development and growth strategy that involves market penetration to reach more customers, satisfy their needs, achieve their loyalty and retain them by delivering superior long-term value.

2.17 Impact of marketing strategies on customer satisfaction

Marketing strategies play a significant role in fostering customer satisfaction in almost every industrial sector and thereby gaining customer loyalty. Marketing strategies adopted by the firm are directly correlated to customer satisfaction by meeting their needs, demands and expectations (Patterson, 2016; Pizam et al., 2016; Edeling and Fischer, 2016). However, the extent of customer satisfaction depends on how effectively the marketing strategies are utilised by the firm after identification of those customer needs. The development of appropriate marketing strategies, however, involves careful market research to identify the external and internal business environment that could affect the firms' strategies (Bramulya et al., 2016). The use of external marketing research can be carried out using macro-environmental tools such as Porter's five forces, Porter's diamond model, Pestle framework, etc. to understand the market forces that impact the business. In order to evaluate the internal business conditions the use of situational analytical models such as SWOT, value chain analysis, etc. can be utilised (Sun and Price, 2016; Bramulya et al., 2016; Kanten and Darma, 2017). These marketing strategies must be directed towards maintaining a strategic fit, i.e. designing strategies that could align with needs of the external market and the internal resources and capabilities available.

Marketing strategies, however, must consider the customer's needs and expectations, the existing business situation, competitors' position, technological shift and changing business trends (Rizan et al., 2014). For instance, in the current age of digitalisation, digital marketing strategies are aimed at integrating the features of both online and offline marketing to establish an omni-channel strategy that offers a seamless purchase experience to customers. Such a shift in the marketing approach is actually a change embraced by firms to add superior value to the service delivery and exceeding customer expectations, leading to customer delight (Rizan et al., 2014; Abril and Rodriguez-Cánovas, 2016; Edeling and Fischer, 2016). Developing digital

marketing requires the firm to make extensive use of internet technology and digital platforms, such as social media, emails, search engine marketing and other eCommerce tools.

2.17.1 Marketing strategies in the case of luxury fashion

According to Okonkwo (2016), as regards to the marketing strategies of fashion brands, the current market scenario forces the consumer to change their perception about a brand and subsequently their decision-making process. Luxury fashion consumers are increasingly shifting from novelty and the rarity value of purchasing a luxury fashion item towards a more holistic experience in the pre-buying experience (Okonkwo, 2016; Amatulli et al., 2016). Particularly where the aspect of touch and feel is important to test the workmanship, luxury fashion brands showcase their products in own-label stores and arrange glitzy product launches that draw consumers toward experiential marketing (Okonkwo, 2016; Amatulli et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2017). This is a shift from the product and the shopping experience which is available physically and now also available online (e.g. Louis Vuitton, Burberry). Fashion-shows with ‘out of the world’ experiences in ‘Victoria’s Secret’, a woman clothing line, has drawn guests from all over the globe. This extremely popular event is now transmitted live on television due to its popularity. Though fashion events are for the select few, designer fashion companies use it as a launch platform to spread customer awareness. This creates consumer awareness for that customer segment, which is often geographically diverse, and located in various countries, and yet wants to avail itself of the new season designer outfit information from the luxury brand (Okonkwo, 2016; Rios, 2016; Goworek et al., 2016; Sanchez Torres et al., 2017).

Kim (2012) argues that in a luxury fashion brand, e-commerce and social media have more of social media shares to build awareness in its selective community of consumers which acts as a visual ‘word-of-mouth’ recommendation. It heightens consumer interest through internet shares and repeated exposure as the online social media platform upgrades to newer technologies of playing videos to replicate the physical event of the fashion launch experience. All of these affect the modality of the consumer’s purchase intentions, especially when luxury fashion brands are embracing technology faster in order to create innovation and creativity in IT to showcase the brand (Parker and Wang, 2016; Chegini et al., 2016). As the old retail model of luxury fashion is dying fast, leadership strategies in fashion marketing and branding are relying on increasing instances of repositioning the same luxury fashion brand online (Sashi, 2012). This is a predominant route that luxury fashion brands are undertaking, in order to form close relationships with consumers. Luxury fashion brands are different and specialist, and to

retain that heritage brand ethos and the pressure to adopt a new media platform in order to have greater reach is a dilemma that is leading fashion brands to reposition the brand (Goworek et al., 2016; Amatulli et al., 2016; Sanchez Torres et al., 2017).

2.18 Impact of CRM on customer satisfaction

According to Peelen et al. (2009), the key motivation for a business organisation to implement CRM is to track the behaviour of its customers and gain deeper insights into their tastes, experiences and evolving needs. The use of this information helps companies to design and introduce superior goods and services that meet customer expectations. Becker et al. (2009) clarify that customer knowledge has definite features that make it an increasingly complicated form of knowledge. For instance, customer knowledge can be obtained from multiple sources and channels and may reflect several contextual meanings. Long et al. (2013) consider customer knowledge in the current business environment to be very dynamic, due to the fact that it is subject to rapid change.

CRM applications make possible organisational learning by allowing companies to understand the consumer's buying behaviour across multiple touchpoints and transactions through different communication channels (Chuang and Lin, 2013). For instance, multinational companies such as American Airlines and Fedex have implemented IT-based CRM systems to develop the customer interface and gain access to useful customer knowledge. These companies have also adopted a combined set of tools and functionalities provided by dominant software vendors to accumulate and store comprehensive customer knowledge. Firms deploying CRM tools are in a superior position to leverage the extensive and most up-to-date customer knowledge and experience into processes meant for customer support (Chuang and Lin, 2013). These firms are more likely to be aware of the data management issues relating to the instigation, maintenance and cessation of the customer relationship. This kind of familiarity helps them to maintain competitive advantage by leveraging the accumulated customer data to tailor their offerings according to customer profiles. Customised product and service offerings delivered to customers without having them to notify about their needs and expectations lead to higher customer satisfaction by adding superior value to such offerings (Rodriguez and Ajjan, 2014).

CRM applications help companies to collect and make use of customer information through two different mechanisms. Firstly, it makes it possible for the customer service representatives to access and record key data about each of the customer transactions. After capturing such data, it can be screened and transformed into customer knowledge based on information processing mechanisms and the company policies (Steel et al., 2013). Customer knowledge and information captured from multiple service encounters can be accessed by the company to respond to various customer needs in different phases. Secondly, companies can also share the stock of customer knowledge with customers, which facilitate the latter to serve them by describing their expectations relating to the service needs and its delivery (Steel et al., 2013). This is the process of allowing customers to select their desired service features, thereby allowing the company to be familiar with the changing customer needs and adapt their service capabilities accordingly.

Considering the importance of CRM applications for customer satisfaction, Long et al. (2013) note that such applications help to satisfy customers in three different ways. Firstly, CRM makes it possible for companies to customise their product and service offering according to the specific needs of each customer. CRM provides customer information across multiple customer interactions and this information can be processed to identify their hidden patterns. Consequently, firms can customise their offering to be provided to individual customers or customer group, and this adds to the perceived quality of goods and services. Shaonand Rahman (2015) explain that perceived quality is one of the most crucial determinants of customer satisfaction; they imply that CRM has an indirect impact on customer satisfaction by affecting the perceived quality.

Secondly, on top of augmenting the perceived quality of the company's offerings, CRM allows the company to enhance the dependability of the customers' consumption experiences by making possible accurate, and timely dispensation of customer orders and/or requests (Shaonand Rahman, 2015). In addition, it facilitates the effective management of customer accounts in a smoother way. Thirdly, CRM applications enable companies to manage and nurture the relationship with customers more effectively and efficiently across the different phases of relationship commencement, continuation and termination. This facilitates effective administration of customer relationship, which is crucial for managing customer satisfaction and consequently, customer loyalty.

Rahimi and Kozak (2017) perceive the contribution of CRM for customer satisfaction in the realm of relationship marketing. The authors elaborate that CRM implementation helps a firm to build and maintain long-term customer relationships, rather than focusing on a 'one-off' transactional approach. CRM helps firms to maintain a holistic platform for managing customer information, their likes and dislikes, purchase history, payment options, complaints log, and overall behaviour based on which customer-centric marketing strategies can be designed and delivered to achieve maximum customer satisfaction. Repeat follows-ups with customers by requesting them to participate in activities such as customer satisfaction surveys helps the firm to engage customers as well as identify the pain areas that obstruct customer satisfaction (Rahimi and Kozak, 2017). Therefore, CRM helps firms to shift their marketing approach from a transactional perspective to a relational perspective, while keeping the customer engaged, thereby gaining access to useful data, both in terms of quality and quantity, and tailor marketing strategies to fit the varied needs of the customers and customer groups.

This aspect of CRM is important for **luxury fashion brands**, as the legacy of luxury fashion brands need to project the same control and inertia in capturing the customer base affinity towards the brand in the digital plane (Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Reicher and Szeghegyi, 2015). This is a particular challenge, as events and digital presentations are perceived differently by consumers when compared to just the product (Hennigs et al., 2015). Each existing customer is, therefore, tries to link their valued relationship by scanning the seasonal offering and, experience a buying experience which separates the brand from the ordinary. The deployment of IT linking to event-based customer experience is like shifting away from the product to experience continuum in order to show its leadership as a luxury brand in a fashion world that faces competition (Park and Kim, 2015; Kejmar and Stefansson, 2017; Abu Qdairi, 2018). Consumers are adjusting their perception and attitudes are being repositioned as luxury brands are repositioning themselves to market-led changes (Kejmar and Stefansson, 2017; Abu Qdairi, 2018). The consumer is processing information differently and is responding to the changing ways of marketing communication. Hence, the external market-based structural changes and the process of marketing communication becoming digital is affecting consumer perception and taking their ability to gather information to a new level.

2.19 Customer retention

Customer retention involves those strategies implemented by firms to ensure that the customers do not develop switch-over intentions to rival companies. Customer retention is crucial for business because it helps to maintain a loyal customer base that avails the firm's products and/or services for the long-term through repeat purchases (Degbey, 2015). Jeneffa and Kaliyamoorthy (2014) point out that such customers also act as brand advocates and recommend the firm/brand to other consumers, thereby serving as sources of advertising for its products and services.

According to Dabija et al. (2014), the longer a customer stays with a company, the more utility is generated. This utility is the result of a range of factors associated with the time spent by the customer with the firm, including the higher preliminary cost of attracting and acquiring a new customer, the increase in the number and value of purchases, and the spread of positive word-of-mouth recommendations.

Customer retention encompasses the steps that an organisation takes to control customer defection. A successful customer retention process should begin with the very first contact a firm has with a potential consumer and persist all the way through the entire lifetime of the customer relationship (Sun et al., 2014; Tamuliene and Gabryte, 2014; Degbey, 2015). Customer retention is crucial for business organisations operating in a competitive market because the cost of new customer acquisition is significantly higher than the cost of sustaining the relationship with existing customers. Therefore, it is considered more economical to retain a loyal customer as compared to acquiring a new one.

A review of the literature indicates that 'service quality' and 'customer satisfaction' are the most dominant concepts that explain why customers switch over to other companies. Even if the customers are satisfied, companies must design strategies to retain them. Moreover, it may be likely that some unsatisfied customers may not choose to defect because they may not anticipate receiving improved service quality from other companies (Stathopoulou and Balabanis, 2016) Hence, customer satisfaction is perceived to be a crucial indicator of customer retention, but customer satisfaction may not always ensure that customers will be retained (Tamuliene and Gabryte, 2014; Degbey, 2015; Kumar and Reinartz, 2016).

Customer retention is a function of a range of variables, namely convenience, choice, income, and price. In the field of customer retention, the literature also establishes a correlation between customer loyalty and business profitability (Viljoen and Roberts-Lombard, 2016). The

outcome of reduced customer retention costs and accomplishment of zero defection of loyal customers is inevitable. However, Wilson et al. (2012) state that in the services domain, the loyalty factor stands valid when customers possess various options to select from. As such, business organisations need to identify why customers tend to stay with the company and must not presume that it is a positive, cognisant choice. This is due to the fact that rivals may lure away customers by offering attractive offers when the latter experience incidents of dissatisfaction. The business organisation must also conduct ongoing research and redesign customer retention strategies to identify the factors that enhance the rate of customer retention (Tamuliene and Gabryte, 2014; Viljoen and Roberts-Lombard, 2016).

2.20 Influential factors of customer retention

The increasing competitiveness in the retail clothing industry is forcing firms to focus on building long-term customer relationships. The process of retaining customers is crucial for clothing firms because of the shorter product lifecycle, which results the need to introduce new designs frequently due to changing fashion trends (Viljoen and Roberts-Lombard, 2016; Alshurideh, 2016). Hence, customers who are loyal to a particular firm/brand may switch over to a near competitor offering trendier fashion at a competitive price and making products available on the shelves in real-time. Wilson et al. (2012) argue that a firm's capability to acquire and retain potential customers is not associated with its products and/or services but is associated with the manner in which it serves its existing clients, delivers value, keeps them satisfied and creates its own reputation within the competitive landscape. Several of the main factors identified from a review of the literature that influence customer retention are discussed in the subsequent sections of this chapter.

2.20.1 Service quality

Quality refers to the value that the customers derive from a particular product or service. Quality is the end-user's overall consciousness of the comparative inferiority or pre-eminence of the products and/or services consumed. Service quality, in this context, refers to the function of the variances between expectations and actual performance of the product and/or service along the quality dimension.

Service quality is considered to be crucial for service differentiation and the ability of a firm to maintain a competitive edge by retaining loyal customers (Wilson and et al., 2012) and gaining a larger market share. Delivery of superior service quality helps to build and uphold long-term customer relationships and sustenance in the current competitive marketplace, and consequently increases customer retention (Wilson et al., 2012; Han and Hyun, 2015). Differentiated and excellent service quality translates into constructive customer behavioural intent and this in turn, results in customer retention.

2.20.2 Customer loyalty

Customer retention involves offering customers more than what they expect and hence, exceeding customer expectations to achieve their loyalty for the firm/brand. Customer loyalty can be created by providing higher value to customers, rather than aiming for profit maximisation (Kumar and Reinartz, 2016). Loyal customers possess characteristic attributes and exhibit repeat purchase behaviour, are less sensitive to the price increases and are willing to advocate the brand to potential consumers. Customer loyalty is, therefore, at the heart of retention, as less loyal customers are more likely to switch over to other companies or brands as compared to loyal ones. An inability on the part of the firm to create loyal customers by building long-term relationships implies operating with a discrete transaction that is one-off (Tripathi, 2014; Tamuliene and Gabryte, 2014; Kumar and Reinartz, 2016). Therefore, academic discussions on customer retention in the literature are largely dominated by customer discounts and loyalty programmes. Nevertheless, Zhang et al. (2016) indicate that the customer's intention to repeat-purchase, as a characteristic feature of a loyal customer, is fostered by providing superior customer services and a well-administered formal and informal communication system.

Customer loyalty is predominantly linked to a customer's eagerness to continue with the relationship; nevertheless, their switching behaviour is found to have a direct impact on loyalty (Lin and Bennett, 2014). The concept of loyalty is also perceived in different ways on the basis of consumer behaviour and the nature of the product and/or service being provided to the end-users (Lin and Bennett, 2014; Liat et al., 2014; Nyadzayo and Khajehzadeh, 2016). For instance, a bank customer will tend to be loyal to the bank as long as the account is maintained with the bank and may withdraw his/her loyalty once the need to maintain the account is not there. However, the customer may still be loyal to the same bank by recommending family and friends or other consumers to the bank by spreading positive word-of-mouth recommendations.

In relation to loyalty, it is often debated that service quality and customer satisfaction have a significant impact on customer retention (Khan and Fasih, 2014; Liat et al., 2014; Nyadzayo and Khajehzadeh, 2016; Jiang et al., 2016).

The more repeatedly a customer purchases from the same company, the more loyalty increases. A loyal customer will be inclined to pay more for the company's offerings and show less sensitivity to tactical discounts and therefore, will be more profitable for the company as compared to those who are attracted to it by sales promotions and special offers.

Luxury fashion brands replicate power, affluence and conspicuous sections of the fashion market (Gentina et al., 2016). Therefore, the psychosomatic meaning of loyalty and customer satisfaction of luxury fashion towards consumers needs to be addressed (Gentina et al., 2016; Choi et al., 2016). Lin and Bennett (2014) have designed a loyalty framework that includes three attitudinal constituents that posit four types of loyalties exhibited by luxury fashion consumers, namely affective, cognitive, connotative and action loyalty. The loyalty model applied in the context of luxury fashion indicates that at some point of the affective-cognitive-connotative chain, consumers tend to cross the verge from low to high consumer resilience due to their trust towards the luxury brand. Trust is positively related to the consumers' loyalty towards the luxury fashion brand.

2.20.3 Trust

Trust refers to the level of dependability that one party (the buyer) ensures to the other party (the seller) in the exchange relationship (buying for money). Trust in the academic literature is defined as the consumer's belief that the products or services provided by the company are reliable (Rasheed and Abadi, 2014). Consumers should also have confidence that their long-term interests will be served by the provider. The greater the level of trust in the service provider, the stronger the commitment towards the relationship and subsequently the greater the possibility of customer retention (Martínez and Rodríguez del Bosque, 2013). Customers who have a better experience with a firm/brand/ service provider in terms of the product or service quality, availability, usage and disposal are more likely to be satisfied and subsequently exhibit higher loyalty. This automatically leads to higher customer retention, as loyal customers have a higher tendency to make repeat purchases and exhibit low turnover intention. Atwal and Williams (2017) point out that customers of luxury products such as luxury fashion have

increased trust towards brands that emerge from economically advanced nations that are reputed for their production convention in the fashion sector, for instance Italian fashion.

2.20.4 Increasing switching costs

Increasing customer loyalty implies that the retentiveness of customers has increased. Loyalty is inherent to a customer and can be changed if there is a shift in their own value system (Jin et al., 2016). Customer retention can be subject to manipulation by the service provider through the offering of appropriate incentives. Yet again, even though inherent loyalty is usually stable in the short run, it can change with the experience of the customer and market familiarity for the firms, especially the catastrophic ones (Jin et al., 2016; Okonkwo, 2016). Hence, it is imperative for firms to conduct customer segmentation on a strategic basis as often as it is economically viable.

Given that the intrinsic customer loyalty is present, their activities may be affected by external stimuli such as incentives, such as product characteristics, price and economic switching costs, communication approach and relationship management (Sekhon et al., 2014; Rasheed and Abadi, 2014; Jiang et al., 2016). Despite the fact that the inherent loyalty of end-users may not be imparted, the external stimuli lie within the service provider's locus of control. These instruments can be manipulated by the service provider to accomplish the required actions from individual customers and customer groups.

Customer retention is a result of the fact that they are motivated to stick with the current provider. Customer retention is made possible with the integrated impact of two key forces; the intrinsic intensity of loyalty of customers and the external stimuli as incentives (Cossío-Silva et al., 2016). Customers are subjected to these forces by way of product attributes, price and pecuniary costs of switching, communication and advertising.

2.21 Three levels of customer retention strategies

Berry and Parasuraman (1991) and Zeithalm and Binter (1996) have proposed a conceptual framework to explain the types of customer retention strategies. The framework, as illustrated in Figure 9, illustrated three levels of customer retention following a systematic process. Moreover, an increase in each level demands an increase in the customisation of the services to be delivered.

Level	Types of Bond(s)	Marketing Orientation	Degree of Service Customization	Primary Marketing Mix Element	Potential for Sustained Competitive Differentiation
1	Financial	Customer	Low	Price	Low
2	Financial and Social	Client	Medium	Personal Communications	Medium
3	Financial, Social and Structural	Client	Medium to High	Service Delivery	High

Figure 9: Three levels of customer retention strategies

(Source: Berry and Parasuraman, 1991; Zeithalm and Binter, 1996)

In Level 1, the only factor that creates a bond between customers and the organisation is financial gain. Customers generally expect to receive a lower price for the purchase they make in bulk or for maintaining a long-term relationship (Berry and Parasuraman, 1991). Therefore, firms offer loyalty discounts to customers to stimulate their intention to make repeat purchases and this is largely possible if they enter into a long-term relationship, for instance, the Clubcard loyalty program launched by the retail supermarket Tesco in the UK, that offers discounts to loyal customers and strengthens their retention process. However, Zeithalm and Binter (1996) argue that offering financial incentives to customers is generally a short-term objective, such as sales promotions to achieve quick sales by offering price cuts, discounts, and similar offers. Such marketing tactics are likely to fail in the long run as financial incentives or short-term discounts can be easily imitated by competitors who could provide offers and lure away customers. Therefore, a financial incentive is simply a customised element of the marketing mix, particularly ‘price’, rather than a strategy directed towards customer retention by building long-term customer relationships.

In Level 2, there are two kinds of incentives that help to create a bond between the customers and the firm, namely financial and social. The firm creates and designs customer-centric strategies to foster social bonding with customers by identifying their many needs and personally fulfilling those needs. Firms then offer customised services that are designed according to the explicit needs of the customers or customer groups, by closely interacting with

them, sharing views and exchanging ideas helps to engage them with the firm/brand. The use of appropriate technology is crucial in maintaining effective social bonds, because an appropriate communication channel/medium is necessary for engaging customers, for instance, using social media as a two-way interactive communication tool to connect with the customers, interact, share updates, exchange ideas, build relationships and develop social bonding.

Here, the communication platform is social media while the internet web 2.0 technology is used to connect with customers. Similarly, the use of mobile phone technology such as smartphone apps is also used to build a personalised customer information system, remain connected with customer around the clock and promote a stronger social bond. Unlike Level 1, competitors would find it difficult to imitate the social relationship as the quality of communication is usually distinctive. Nitzan and Libai (2011) consider social relationships to be more important and useful than financial incentives, particularly if the firm intends to maintain long-term customer relationships, and thereby retention.

In Level 3, the bond between customers and the firm is created with the help of financial incentives, social relationships and structural bonds. The firm creates this by delivering highly customised services and offer specific rights to the end-users in the system of service delivery. Khan (2012) argues that imitating the strategy in Level 3 is next to impossible for competitors to imitate, as the service delivery is highly structured and ingrained within the marketing framework of the firm. The firm is able to categorise its customers according to their varying needs and desires, implement sophisticated customer relationship tools/applications such as CRM, streamline the distribution channels, build networks, and strengthen its value chain (Rodriguez et al., 2015; Triznova et al., 2015; Santouridis and Veraki, 2017). This requires a structured process which is backed by social relationships with those customers who are not only engaged but are also offered financial incentives by way of loyalty discounts and bonuses (Triznova et al., 2015; Madhovi, P.G. and Dhliwayo, 2017). An example of Level 3 could be firms maintaining both physical and online retail shops backed with CRM support, multiple payment options, merchandise returns and strong communication systems that keep customers well informed and offer customised solution to customer problems.

2.21.1 CRM and customer retention

According to Famiyeh et al. (2015), business organisations maintaining effective CRM are in a better position to gain a competitive advantage and pursue customer retention. Carmen et al. (2016) consider retained customers as the most crucial asset for firms in any industry which is difficult for competitors to imitate. Therefore, there exists a strong integration between CRM and customer-specific marketing strategies (acquisition, add-ons, and retention) through CRM strategies. Meanwhile, Bahari and Elayidom (2015) insinuate that the main purpose of CRM is customer acquisition and customer retention. Jain and Patel (2016) find that CRM offers a wide range of strategies to manage customer relationships that link with the overall processes of sales, marketing and support functions within the organisation. CRM is also considered as a management approach that helps to identify, attract, develop and maintain successful client relationships over time so as to enhance the retention of loyal customers (Sun et al., 2014; Bramulya et al. 2016; Alshurideh, 2016). As a relationship marketing strategy, CRM makes it possible for a firm to identify, analyse, evaluate and deliver superior services to customers to strengthen the process of customer relationship and retention. CRM helps to add value to products and services offered to customers, thereby increasing their switchover cost and gaining their loyalty (Ryding et al., 2016). Loyal customers are more likely to offer their long-term custom to the organisation. Therefore, organisations often invest heavily in CRM strategies to develop, cultivate and nurture long-lasting relationship with customers. A Review of the literature indicates a positive relationship between CRM and customer retention; however, there is a lack of research into understanding whether a similar relationship exists in the luxury fashion industry.

2.22 Competitive strategy, retention and regain management

The marketing strategy which is based on the relationship constructs for a group of customers sells products and services. The issue of relationships not meeting required conditions and expectations leads to that marketing strategy shifting to a retention strategy (Bramulya et al., 2016; Kantén and Darma, 2017.). This is due to the simple fact that relationship marketing does not meet the standards of product or service deliverables which are designed to meet the customer expectation set. Customer retention can be defined in a different manner as the failure of loyalty patronage function in the marketing domain. The positive and negative retention

constructs are used interchangeably, as much of it depends on the indicators of the retention function (Bramulya et al., 2016; Wahyuningtyas et al., 2016; Kanten and Darma, 2017.)

Retention, however, is dependent on the customer's intention to engage with products or services making the construct purely an expression of behaviour (Thaichon and Quach, 2015). From realistic point of view, the marketing function depends on either loyalty when customer is positive about the product or service, or retention when disengagement leads to cognitive dissonance (Jenefa and Kaliyamoorthy, 2014; Degbey, 2015.). The loyalty factor clearly supports customer satisfaction in relation to the product or service quality, which leads to trust-building and commitment to repeat purchases. When none of these actions happen, this is an indication of the customer's disconfirmation paradigm and a failing relationship quality that necessitates the need for a retention strategy (Jenefa and Kaliyamoorthy, 2014). Any firm linking the retention factor to the corporate business marketing strategy is integrating the negative outcomes to be rectified in a structural operation process. This is an inward-looking strategy that focuses on the acquisition of customers who are leaving.

A retention strategy needs to understand and evaluate the customer's expectations and perceived gaps closely, as this perception of quality aids in either satisfaction or failure to maintain it leads to severing a cold relationship (Jenefa and Kaliyamoorthy, 2014; Bramulya et al., 2016; Javed and Cheema, 2017). The link of the competitive strategy in combining the marketing mix and meeting the expectation set shows the management side of minimising those risks that create dissatisfaction. Creating a strategy and sub-strategies in a competitive environment also requires the company to manage the complex links of satisfaction and dissatisfaction (Sun and Price, 2016; Kanten and Darma, 2017; Yang and Chao, 2017). The firm-level inability to resolve the gaps and meet expectations leads to diminished trust, which is mutual in nature. In the retention construct, the trust forms a major factor in reducing the customer's disorientation towards the product or service transactions. Trust is vital, as it is the only component between the customer and firm which is an expression of uncertainty or certainty (Gronroos, 1994). The second component that is important in the retention business relationship is commitment, as companies expect loyal customers to return, due to emotional bonding. Commitment also happens when there is a conviction in the customer's mind, whose benefits outnumber the negatives for which the customer defers the decision rather than terminates it. (Bramulya et al., 2016)

Retention strategy stretches the marketing function, as the concept of producing the same service and products through communication does not work. The customer is finished with the relationship with the company's products and services threshold expectation that forces termination of the emotional linkage and business contract (Jenefa and Kaliyamoorthy, 2014; Di Benedetto and Kim, 2016). The issue in terms of retention is a different target segment of customers which needs a differential treatment in order to regain the lost customers. Retention strategies are an extension of defensive relationship marketing, as the core action is the projection of buy-ins in order to revive the terminated relationship.

According to Mumuni and O'Reilly (2014), 'regain management' structurally focuses the marketing fundamentals on the pain points and the planning, realisation and greater control over incidents of threats and processes to be realigned in a manner to meet the business relationship which has ended. The authors, however, emphasized that prolonging the relationship that has been rekindled requires the following actions. The first is to identify the reasons for the customer exit decisions and the manner in which the customer became detached from the company. This needs to be a permanent system which needs embedding into the relationship marketing components and identifying those stages from where the customer perceived pain areas. This is a one-to-one basis approach in the end-to-end product and service delivery systems, which is bound to enrich the relationship development with the customer.

The second issue is to enforce retention through regain strategies of the lost ground of the customer's own decision to leave the relationship. Milan et al. (2015) adds that customers must be incentivised to re-join as an old customer which is a strategic angle to reviving the relationship. CRM needs to develop tools which capture indicators from the customers when he or she is about to terminate the buyer relationship. Adding value and aligning existing processes to customer lifetime values is important for the retention strategy design to pay off. It also relates to reducing customer exits from the brand and stop the switching behaviour (Kumar, 2015; Di Benedetto and Kim, 2016). The defensive marketing strategy in retention needs to address the roots of dissatisfaction that can be company-side ignorance, misunderstanding or disagreements, while few instances of customer-inflated expectations needs a better understanding. This is linked to the competitive strategy, as firms trying to differentiate their products and services need to align those components of customer feedback which make the realignment into homogenous industry. Competitiveness is about how fast the firm is able to incorporate those complaints through product or service alterations to convert

dissatisfied customers into satisfied ones and is the most potent competitive strategy (Fullerton, 2014; Sun et al., 2014; Di Benedetto and Kim, 2016; Stathopoulou and Balabanis, 2016).

2.23 Importance of customer satisfaction and retention in the fashion industry

In the fashion industry, the customer relationship begins with the initial sales; however, the challenge of keeping the customer continually interested in the **fashion brand** requires service and retail strategies (Islam et al., 2012). The aspect of how the luxury fashion label negotiates the space, branding and promotions defines the quality of the relationship in a multi-brand showroom or in a retail chain which affects the customer affinity towards the brand (Hendrayati and Gaffar, 2016). The B2B relationship between the manufacturer and seller seeking mutual benefits in terms of revenues and the qualitative aspect of the customer with the fashion label consists of many factors. The customer's loyalty is an attitudinal aspect which is expressed as a behaviour, while the word-of-mouth communication between the retailer and consumers have a positive impact on the buying relationship. The luxury fashion industry on the global stage is dependent on the production (supply side) and the consumer (demand side) in order to align their back-end production in batches for reducing costs. Lloyd and Luk (2010) state that over the years, mass production has ceased, and now more segmented fashion is the trend in the industry. Fashion garment manufacturers, therefore, are forced to communicate the latest trends as segmented fashion. They communicate their abilities of manufacturing in the luxury fashion industry through the introduction of new tastes to meet their expectations. As a result, the luxury fashion industry is maturing and moving up the value chain with fast fashion becoming a dominant factor for customer satisfaction (Nonaka et al., 2014).

This forms the manufacturers' response to the customer's needs and desires through the latest design, style, fabric and colour on the product side. The relationship becomes much deeper when the fashion retailer- either the company or third-party reseller of a multi-brand chain - is able to communicate those brand communication gaps at the service level (Rupik, 2015; Hendrayati and Gaffar, 2016). In this fashion management domain, the store-level service also indicates their capability to maintain the customer pulls to a specific fashion brand by replenishing the stocks on the store shelves. Organisational responsiveness and operations flexibility are one of the metrics which consumers' test, as it is directly linked to the product availability and their desire to purchase (Dabija et al., 2014). This organisational

responsiveness contributes to the customer engagement factor and the result is satisfaction which helps the customer to be retained. In the fashion industry, this is segmented, as retail stores contribute to the service component, while the apparel manufacturer deals with the product side.

Dabija et al. (2014) indicate that the issue of negative experiences in the consumer's buying stages at any point of time creates a disruption of the entire process. Companies focus on impeccable service to create a positive impression of the fashion-selling process. The in-store customer service quality should also complement customer expectations. This is a key factor, as the well-informed customer is able to connect to the personnel and visualise the item availability in order to make the final decision (Hendrayati and Gaffar, 2016; Stathopoulou and Balabanis, 2016). The issue of customer queries and their resolution goes a long way in mitigating the negativities of doubt, questions and criticisms. The internal marketing from the employee perspective is a potential counteractive force to satisfy the customer's intentions.

The other angle which is important to discuss is that the fashion industry is shifting from mass production to segmented production and the need at the backend operations is shorter lifecycles that depend much on the customer's mood and the seasonal flavour. Frequent changes in fashion tastes create more opportunities for the manufacturer to capture the customer and fashion community consensual future trends (Jenefa and Kaliyamoorthy, 2014). This is important from the marketing point of view, as saleability of the item in the next fashion season depends on the customer inputs. The relational quality of the customer in buying fashion items is important, as even though the fashion trend has become shorter, the seasonal opportunities in the whole year present a higher level of involvement from CRM perspective.

In order to contribute to the quality of the relationship dimension that customers hold on to a fashion label, in today's fashion marketplace fashion designers are emphasizing the retail outlet that contributes to customer satisfaction (Sun et al., 2014). In a market full of promotions for fashion brands that provoke impulse purchases, the consumer's buying decision has too many disruptions to continue the CRM element which subsequently continues to engage loyalty. CRM from the luxury brand is reflected in satisfaction, as for an apparel brand the next season's fashion may not stimulate the customer to buy the same fashion brand, while for the retailer it is about the 'availability' factor (Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Shukla et al., 2016). The brand recognition and the CRM at the store do influence the customer decision in choosing a fashion brand and also to stay loyal towards it. Non-availability is a major negative factor; even a

seasonal launch postponed from a fashion designer harms the customer expectation continuum in the fashion sector (Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Hennigs et al., 2015; Shukla et al., 2016). This can even lead to customers switching to another fashion brand, as the motivation and purpose for buying the item may be strong and imminent, but the external circumstances do not support those buying intentions (Mumuni and O'Reilly, 2014). The store and manufacturer fashion label relationship, the instances of positive experiences in the buying behaviour does affect the consumer brand affinity and loyalty towards the next purchase of the same fashion label, or from the same fashion designer.

All of these indicate that the self-concept of the consumer is satisfied only when the customer tries out the new fashion garment in the next season. The customer also equates the image of a changed perception of the body with the new fashion item in the next fashion season, which may or may not meet the expectancy set in consumer's mind (Dion and Borraz, 2015; Cheah et al., 2016). The brand-based emotive angle that is stimulated in the customer's mind, however, is subject to trials, as the consumer always wants to maximise their wants. From the fashion perspective, high street fashion or fast fashion has been disruptive, as it has created more market segments for the consumer (Chihab and Abderrezzak, 2016; Ajitha and Sivakumar, 2017; Salem and Chaichi, 2018). Luxury fashion or custom-made, limited edition fashion items designed to depict exclusivity and rarity is now reaching out to satisfy the upper-middle class. This strategy in the fashion industry has led to democratisation of luxury fashion labels where segmentation has led to the creation of sub-brands and yet the original luxury brand is kept intact (Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2016). This segmentation of consumers in fashion goods has led to differential pricing, with upper-, mid- and entry-level consumers aspiring to own an iconic fashion label.

The satisfaction of the purchase and demonstration of the brand in the social context is well known, and it shows that perception of consumers toward luxury products have changed over time. Satisfaction from wearing a fashion item which is rare costs more when it is worn for shorter period of time. It is a prized possession for some consumers, while for the fact of disappearance of the fashion season makes the item less valuable. Nonaka et al., (2014) adds that to link the customer satisfaction issue, the product becomes out of date, while consumer looks for satisfaction from newer fashion trends from the same fashion brand. This is a constant replenishment cycle that goes on forever, creating lasting value for the customer and the fashion brand. In this manner, the fashion brand is also able to meet the customer demand set over the disappearance of seasons by changing the style, colour, texture and design to meet the varied

consumption demands (Chihab and Abderrezzak, 2016; Ajitha and Sivakumar, 2017; Henninger et al., 2017). This indicates the strategy to retain the customer as the bond to the fashion label and the consumer's affinity to look for new novelty features in the next fashion season is evident. The longer lead times of heritage luxury fashion brands giving its way to the fast fashion brands, therefore, have created a wider scope of marketing function making the lifecycle of the fashion item shorter (Lervik Olsen et al., 2014). The firm-level capability to translate the imagery of the consumer to a product feature in a fashion label in the next fashion season is also a relationship-building strategy by the manufacturers (Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2016; Ajitha and Sivakumar, 2017; Brun, 2017). This helps to build the customer's orientation and perception of the towards the luxury fashion brands as the industry format is changing to accommodate wider range of consumers who can afford the luxury fashion ensemble.

2.24 Re-positioning fashion brand segments and its impact on CRM

The increase in advertising communication channels and easy availability of information to the customers is being challenged by word-of-mouth. This can be about any event, product release or product review by an individual in the social media platform that creates an impact on the customer's mind. Karaosman et al. (2016) point out that the perceptions about the luxury brands are therefore mostly affected by social media, as opinions in digital media follow a geometric progression dividing the responses into likes or dislikes. This is repositioning the fashion brand value as increasingly paid social media marketing strategies in e-WOM (electronic word of mouth) is helping to reposition the brands in the marketplace (Bezzaouia and Joanta, 2016; Eom and Seock, 2017). This is also applicable to luxury fashion brands, as consumers judge and expresses their opinions on the basis of how previous consumers have reacted on social media and online platforms, which affects the brands' reputation. The fashion firms 'shift of towards fashion as an experience is increasing the service dimension depth in appealing to the customer's perceptual set (Gautam and Sharma, 2017; Roy et al., 2018).

Firms are looking at repositioning strategy toward the online push as a new marketing resource to create a fresh perspective about the brand. Experience is one of the key strategies fashion brands are using to create a multi-perspective analysis of marketing, as it takes consumers to those levels of the sensory, emotional, relational and cognitive plane that leads to consumer's

pleasure to engagement (Lim et al., 2016; Wirtz et al., 2016). This significant shift of product to experience in the fashion industry context is also showing how happiness in consumers when they relate their experience through a digital or physical presence leads to an absorptive and joyful experience. It leads to memorable experiences at a cognitive state, leading to the growth of the fashion brand equity as the brand moves away from product-centric positioning to experience-centric fashion show launches (Lim et al., 2016; Wirtz et al., 2016; Roux et al., 2017).

2.25 Sensory marketing strategy

Sensory marketing is a significant alternative to the conventional mass marketing approach. While traditional marketing mainly focuses on customer acquisition, selling products and/or services, and a one-way communication process through exchange of words, sensory marketing extends the emphasis to multidimensional customer communication by way of digital technology, customer management and providing better customer experience (Krishna and Schwarz, 2014; Zong et al., 2016).

Sensory marketing is an array of controlled actions in order to generate explicit multi-sensorial environment encircling a product or service, either by making use of a product, or creating a positive interaction through a positive environment at the point of sale. Washington and Miller (2010) explain that sensory marketing helps to identify how a firm can enhance brand awareness using sense-based expressions and appropriate sensory strategies and finally setting up a brand image that relates to the customers' personality, lifestyle and identity. While researchers such as Sidali et al. (2013) consider the importance of sensorial marketing for stimulating customers to visit the stores and make a purchase, others such as Hinestroza and James (2014) link it with customer satisfaction. This is because customers in the fashion industry not only buy to satisfy a need, but also to seek pleasure, emotional attachment with a brand, relieve stress and spend leisure time associated with satisfaction.

Krishna (2012) conducted an in-depth investigation into the sensory marketing concept and stated its importance in applying to the understanding of customer perception and sensation in marketing – to cognition, learning, emotions, choices, preferences, and evaluation. The author also designed a conceptual framework of sensorial marketing strategy and demonstrated that the process involved various sensations of customers that may have affected consumer

behaviour in the physical store environment. Sensation occurs when an external stimulus invades upon the receptor cells of a particular sensory organ while perception indicates the understanding or awareness about the sensory information (Krishna, 2012). These are linked with grounded cognition and grounded emotion, which subsequently helps to define the attitude, memory and learning and the behaviour of customers.

Figure 10: Conceptual model of sensory marketing strategy

(Source: Krishna, 2012) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Referring to the above conceptual model, Krishna (2012) explains that consumers not only buy products or services, but also search for and buy emotional experiences in a store. Emotional cues present in a store are able to express the sensations that a consumer feels in the store environment and convert shopping into an emotional experience (Krishna and Schwarz, 2014). For example, the use of visual and auditory cues helps to activate sensations in the consumer's mind and then fortify attention followed by imagery processing. Visual cues such as colour and auditory cues such as music can create sensations and lead to positive store outcomes if the consumer perceives it to be emotionally appealing.

According to Wiedmann et al. (2013), the main objective of sensorial marketing is to foster positive signals in the store and eradicate negative ones. This would support the experiences of pleasure with a brand that customers anticipate while getting instantaneous sensorial satisfaction. Experience, in this context, refers to the extent of interactions that interfere during the service delivery process at different points of contact. Customers come across such experiences that occur in appealingly sensorial stores dominantly reflect the consumers'

attitude and lifestyle, and aiming to create fascination (for instance, the ‘WOW! factor’), and thereby memorisation (Wiedmann et al., 2013).

Hinestroza and James (2014) argue that firms sell memories in addition to products and/or services which affect consumers’ future purchase behaviour. A dull or an uninteresting experience with a store or a gloomy or an unattractive atmosphere is likely to create an unpleasant and negative experience which becomes encoded in the memory, thereby creating dissatisfaction with the store/brand. Despite the store having differentiated quality, competitive pricing or attractive promotions, negative customer experience may result in customer dissatisfaction and lower the chance of their coming back to the store. Creating experience requires maintaining appropriate decor (product display), manoeuvre (the product narrates its story) and action (creating an association between the product and the consumer/visitor) (Hinestroza and James, 2014). Brandt (2015) argues that modern consumers in the fashion industry are less fascinated by inert products, as they have a higher tendency to live an individual experience, i.e. exclusivity by the act of consumption. Therefore, Hilton (2015) suggests that the more the products in a fashion store mobilise the senses, the more the consumer would have a feeling of living the experience.

2.25.1 Emotional marketing as a part of sensory marketing

According to Consoli (2010), emotional marketing creates a strong appeal by arousing consumers’ deeper feelings. Customers come across affective experiences from an optimistic temperament to stronger feelings of sentiments such as enjoyment and pride. Rytel (2010) explains that emotional marketing works appropriately by gaining familiarity with stimuli and circumstances and the consumers’ willingness to be engaged with the process.

Lund (2015), however, argues that emotions are difficult to quantify in the actual buying and consumption situation. Nevertheless, if human emotions interfere with rational choices, they tend to articulate themselves in a pragmatic manner and reflect the need for hedonist benefits, as well as ludic, sensorial, and aesthetic. Menezes et al. (2016) assert that the outcome of emotional marketing is in the form of providing more pleasure and a satisfying experience for consumers. It also intends to personalise the consumers’ seduction in a rationale of subjective product differentiation. Emotional marketing is however supported by the use of human senses that create emotional cues to stimulate customers or those visiting a physical store. Hence, the

next section reviews the five senses used in marketing, namely sight, hearing, taste, touch and smell.

2.25.2 Use of senses in sensory marketing

The classification of the human senses into sight, hearing, taste, touch and smell generally considers an anatomic vision of discernment; for instance, the eyes, the hand, the nose, the mouth and the ears, but this categorisation has some restrictions (Malenkaya and Andreyeva, 2016; Taube and Warnaby, 2017). Firstly, the hand does not feel the complete sensation of touch, rather it is the skin, muscles, organs and articulations. Similarly, the mouth not only stimulates the sense of taste, but also touch, smell and sound. Therefore, a more extensive analysis of the physiology of senses provides a more complete approach to the study of senses (Kumar, 2014; Krishna et al., 2016). Human senses or the senses of a consumer can be categorised into several physiological systems and used to arouse their sensations through visual marketing, sound marketing, music, smell marketing, taste marketing and touch marketing.

Visual marketing

Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory indicates that seeking out aesthetics is an existential need and is articulated once the basic needs are satisfied. Consumers in the fashion industry are inclined to satisfy their 'search for beauty' and hence 'ugliness is difficult to sell'. Therefore, marketers use sight as the most important sense in fashion marketing, with a range of colours and shades to stimulate the viewers' mood through communication and positioning by designing attractive/appealing logos, packages and typographies (Ozuem and Tan, 2014). Shabgou and Daryani (2014) explain that the response time of any visual cue is short, primarily because it provides visual information and helps individuals to make quick judgements about products. Consumers as humans have a higher trust in their eyes than other sense organs and when faced with any doubt, vision is more crucial than the rest of the senses. Therefore, a fashion retailer is found to use more visual cues in the store, such as bright lighting, displays, TV screens and neon signs.

Sound marketing

Combined with vision, sound is one of the most important sensory marketing techniques. Sidali et al. (2013) clarify that hearing is passive while listening is active and pleasant sound creates an appeal that can stimulate purchase decisions in a positive manner. The sound of product or brand should target the consumers who are active listeners as well as those who are hearers, and explicit sounds are related to specific products and brands. For instance, the sound of opening or closing a door, curtain in a fitting room, steps on the floor, etc. can be memorised by consumers and can emotionally direct their behaviour. The effect of music is more influential than any other source of a sound and good music is used by brands to create a pleasant 'consumer mood', often creating an association between the customer's personality with the brand (Shabgou and Daryani, 2014)

Music in the form of a jingle or tune helps consumers to recall a brand (which is stored in consumers' long-term memory) by remembering its visual and emotional elements. Music also helps to strengthen the brand identity and influences the perception of time (Wiedmann et al., 2013). In a physical store, a fast music tempo with high volume tends to increase consumers' excitement state and stimulate them to act faster, while slow music has the opposite impact. A slow tempo, however, evokes emotional responses in a positive manner and creates a favourable environment that improves impulsive purchases. Meanwhile, Hussain (2014) argues that music matching consumers' taste can be used as an efficient tool to lower stress, control the irritation caused if the customer is kept waiting, and ignite positive consumer response towards purchase.

Touch marketing

Touch is largely undervalued in the area of marketing, although it offers several perspectives and covers an extensive range of sensations (Sidali et al., 2013). These sensations range from touch itself (touch of contact, of surface) to haptic sensations (bodily interactions). The sensation of touch occurs through the skin and this creates acquaintance with a particular

product by opening the consumer's access to intimacy, sense of proximity and choice (Hilton, 2015).

Touch is crucial in the fashion industry because it helps consumers to judge the quality of a fabric, the material, its softness and even compare between fashion brands (Petit et al., 2015). Even though fashion retailers are displaying demonstrative screens, considering the importance of touch, they are not eliminating the opportunities for consumers to touch and feel the products and assess the fabric quality. Haptic sensations are associated with the feeling that consumers have while touching a doorknob, or an escalator ramp, the shopping trolleys that they push and other different materials in the store (Petit et al., 2015). It is however important for the marketers to identify the objects that are likely to create a positive sensation or negative experiences when touched by a consumer. Accordingly, the objects along with the products, packaging materials, shelves and other items that customers come into direct contact with must be able to create a positive customer sensation when touched.

2.25.3 Sensory marketing practices by firms in the high street fashion industry

According to Barnes (2013), firms in the high street fashion industry have started to incorporate sensory marketing strategies in the store environment, and this is considered to be an emotion vector. Lund (2015) states that the introduction of music is widespread among retailers in clothing stores to attract customers and increase the time they spend in stores and this increases the likelihood of customers feeling the product fabric or quality, trying and actually making a purchase. Contrary to this, Hilton (2015) argues that fashion retailers give due importance to the lighting, flooring, ceilings and adornment while others implement a thematic approach to place special emphasis on their store environment. Meanwhile, McKelvey (2014) elucidates that sensory marketing in the fashion retail environment stimulates customers' emotional behaviour while controlling the rational approach to purchasing and hence around 80% customers tend to purchase garments unconsciously. Hendrayati and Gaffar (2016) focus on the importance of fashion impulse in the clothing sector and stress the fashion involvement behaviour of customers and how it influences the marketing atmosphere of retail stores. The behavioural variables applicable in the fashion store, for instance purchase behaviour, consumer characteristics and product involvement, have a dominant appeal in fashion involvement.

2.26 Visual commerce and CRM

According to Qian and Gao (2011), the CRM visual commerce is the next level where the process of users collecting photos, adding items to a wish list and sharing them across social circles and social networking sites creates visual marketing materials. In most cases, these have the consumer themselves adding value to the trials they performed in the fashion retail outlet. These authentic customer photos act as endorsement of the brand, which helps the firm to capture the social circle and much larger groups (Qian and Gao, 2011). There are advanced features used by online eCommerce fashion stores, where the virtual try-on feature is added for the fashion world. This is adding shop-ability layers, better customer engagement and the idea of the customer moving into the visual plane of experiential marketing. The challenge of the rich face-to-face interaction missing in a fashion retail outlet has been thus countered with the advanced level try-on features in the fashion websites (Kim et al., 2012). It allows consumers to try on the design, colour and style which affect the look and feel of the garment without having to buy it or visit a fashion retail outlet. Visual commerce is the next level of experiential marketing where the company is able to add layers of visual content in the fashion website. This definitely extends the customer stay factor, makes the engagement more meaningful and improves shop-ability (Hajli, 2012). These consumer activities also make use of technology with the online 'virtual try-on' method to click photos and share them.

Visual commerce uses these photos for visual marketing materials by spreading via social media. They also come to know about the clicks made, which angle the customer looks from during the 'virtual try-on' which all pertains to the fashion design, style and cut aspect which is important for the company (Faed et al., 2010). This also shows how the firms are exploring the e-commerce and eCRM concept in the crowded technology space to find something meaningful. This is an effective advanced methodology in e-commerce which is being increasingly deployed in online fashion e-commerce websites. Given that fashion e-commerce is a crowded place, visual commerce is assisting in the process of understanding how and why the customer deflects and does not make a purchase until the last moment and why the customer leaves the e-commerce shopping cart (Zhang and Zhang, 2013).

Though the negative experiences while shopping are hard to capture, in an online fashion e-commerce website, fashion companies are utilising advanced analytical tools to understand the website navigation, clicks and virtual 'try-on' data. This is collated to a level where they track the customer in social media, as their agreement to accept cookies passes the information to the fashion company. For the instance where a customer moves to a different fashion brand

website, a search showcases the visual banner advertisements of all the past fashion products visited by the customer (Heuer et al., 2015). This advertisement bombardment leads to constant excitement of the stimuli and evokes their preferences of that fashion item, style, colour, shape and incites the customer to buy against the competitor fashion brand.

The aspect of a customer staying longer with the fashion brand is dependent on the activities the customer performs. This is an emerging arena, as dissatisfied customers are likely to seek a third-party opinion about the look factor. For fashion marketing firms which are selling online, it has been a difficult proposition to retain a customer (Petkova, 2016). The longevity and staying power of the fashion item in the customer’s preferred list, wish list or shopping cart is a part of advanced CRM extended relationship management and social CRM. Firms are taking CRM to the next level where they create engagement factor for the consumer buying online. It is evident that user-generated content is shared more than that of the official company launched promotional products. Customers who feel a sense of belonging in the community that appreciates a brand in fashion is likely to share a photo or video to a person, group or multiple groups in social media accounts.

2.27 Thematic table of literature review

Literature review topics	Themes	Authors
Concept of brand, luxury fashion brand	Fashion luxury brands	Cavender and Kincade, 2014; Giovannini et al., 2015; Esmaeilpour, 2015; Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2016; Cheah et al., 2016; Ko et al. 2017;Cristini et al., 2017;Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2016;De Angelis et al., 2017; Tak et al. 2017Roy et al., 2018
Factors affecting luxury fashion brand	Luxury brands are inspirational products	Salehzadeh and Pool, 2017
	Exposure and association	Kim et al., 2012; Esmaeilpour, 2015;

		Eom and Seock, 2017; Salem and Chaichi, 2018
	Reference groups	Godey et al., 2016 Kembau, 2015; Wu et al., 2015; Han et al., 2017; Gautam and Sharma, 2017; Henninger et al., 2017
	Purchase environment	Ki and Kim, 2016; Eom and Seock, 2017; Roy et al., 2018; Alexander and Contreras, 2016; Henninger et al., 2017
	Purchasing motivation	Bezzaouia and Joanta, 2016; Godey et al., 2016; Roy et al., 2018
Marketing strategies	Push marketing strategies	Shaw, 2012; Pantano and Viassone, 2014; Quirke, 2017
	Pull marketing strategies	Shaw, 2012; Baker, 2014; Kotler et al., 2015; Smilansky, 2017;
	Push and Pull strategies in luxury fashion brands	Pantano and Viassone, 2014; Quirke, 2017; Smilansky, 2017; Atwal and Williams, 2017
	Market dominance strategy	Palmer et al., 2014; Parker and Wang, 2016; Yang and Chao, 2017; Blevins et al., 2017; Santouridis and Veraki, 2017
	Marketing mix strategy	O'Cas and Heirati, 2015; Wongleedee, 2015; Festa et al., 2016; Abril and Rodriguez-Cánovas, 2016
	Innovative marketing strategy	Nufer, 2013; Ramaseshan et al., 2013; Zeriti et al., 2014;
	Marketing strategies in case of luxury fashion	Okonkwo, 2016; Rios, 2016; Goworek et al., 2016; Amatulli et al., 2016; Goworek et al., 2016; Sanchez Torres et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2017
Relationship marketing	Relational perspective	Rizan et al., 2014; Skarmeas et al., 2016; Triznova et al., 2015; Gummerus et al., 2017

Customer relationship management (CRM) as a marketing strategy	Customer relationship management concept	Verhoef and Lemon, 2013; Demo, 2014; Hayley, 2016; Carmen and Marius, 2016; Zouaoui et al., 2016
	CRM as a strategy	Ahearne et al., 2012; Reimer and Becker, 2015; Carmen and Marius, 2016; Zouaoui et al., 2016
	CRM as a process	Saarijärvi et al., 2013; Bai and Qin, 2016; Thakur and Workman, 2016; Bhat and Darzi, 2016; Wang and Kim, 2017; Cambra-Fierro et al., 2017
	eCRM as a relationship management strategy	Choudhury and Harrigan, 2014; Yu et al., 2015; Papaioannou et al., 2014; Krämer et al., 2017; Cambra-Fierro et al., 2017; Hamid et al., 2019
	Social CRM	Lehmkuhland Jung, 2013; Choudhury and Harrigan, 2014; Elena, 2016; Wittwer et al., 2017
Customer satisfaction	Assimilation theory of consumer satisfaction	Terpstra and Verbeeten, 2014
	Contract theory of customer satisfaction	Isac and Rusu, 2014; Radojevic et al., 2015
	Assimilation-Contrast theory of customer satisfaction	Khan, 2015; Zboja et al., 2016
Models of customer satisfaction measurement	SERVQUAL MODEL	Parasuraman et al, 1985; Parasuraman et al, 1988; Ravichandran, 2010
	Retail Service Quality Scale Model	Dabholkar et al., 1996; Culiberg and Rojsek, 2010;
	Kano Model	Kano et al., 1984; Turisová, 2014; Lin et al., 2015; Rotar and Kozar, 2017

	American customer satisfaction index) Model	Deng et al. 2013; Lee et al., 2016
Impact of marketing strategies on customer satisfaction		Al-Hersh and Saaty, 2014; Bramulya et al., 2016; Edeling and Fischer, 2016; Rizan et al., 2014; Kumar, 2016; Aka et al., 2016; Sun and Price, 2016
Impact of CRM on customer satisfaction		Chuang and Lin, 2013; Rodriguez and Ajjan, 2014; Shaonand Rahman, 2015;
	CRM in luxury fashion brands	Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Reicher and Szeghegyi, 2015; Park and Kim, 2015; Kejmar and Stefansson, 2017; Abu Qdairi, 2018
Customer retention (Factors of customer retention)	Service Quality	Wilsonand et al., 2012; Wilson <i>et al.</i> 2012; Han and Hyun, 2015
	Customer Loyalty	Tripathi, 2014; Tamuliene and Gabryte, 2014; Kumar and Reinartz, 2016
	Trust	Martínez and Rodríguez del Bosque, 2013; Rasheed and Abadi, 2014
Impact of CRM on customer retention		Sun et al., 2014; Bahari and Elayidom, 2015; Bramulya et al. 2016; Alshurideh, 2016

2.28 Conceptual framework

2.29 Conclusion

This review of the literature has incorporated a comprehensive discussion of customer satisfaction theories and retention models and linked them to business strategies. While business strategy is a wider concept, the current review has emphasised the importance of relationship marketing followed by narrowing down the concept to customer relationship management (CRM), eCRM and social-CRM. Business strategies implemented in the area of relationship marketing and CRM have been specifically reviewed in the context of their importance for customer satisfaction and retention. The literature of customer satisfaction theories, stages of customer retention and factors that influence the retention process has also been reviewed in this chapter. The conceptual models supporting the process of customer satisfaction have helped in the analysis of the determinants of customer satisfaction, such as the SERVQUAL model, the Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS) and the Kano model.

Despite the extensive literature review carried out by studying the existing theories and literary work available in the academic domain, it was found that empirical testing of these models and tools in the fashion industry is inadequate. There is currently a lack of research in terms of identifying the business strategies with key emphasis on relationship marketing and the customer relationship management process, the service quality and product quality models that impact customer satisfaction in the fashion sector. Similarly, inadequate research is evident in the area of understanding the most effective business strategies that foster the process of customer retention in fashion. The different types of marketing strategies such as the marketing dominance strategy, the marketing mix strategy, innovative marketing, market development and expansion strategy have also been reviewed in the current literature; however, little is known about the impact of these marketing strategies in retaining customers in the fashion industry. In addition, the concept of sensorial marketing is also introduced in the literature with an emphasis on the use of emotional marketing and the use of the senses. The existing literature considers the use of sensory marketing to be extremely useful in the fashion industry to arouse the consumers' emotional response towards a purchase; however, little attention is paid to its impact on satisfaction and retention.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Designing an appropriate methodology to carry out a research study is a crucial factor, especially in social science research. Establishing an appropriate methodology involves evaluating a range of research methods, approaches and strategies that are considered relevant for the study and choosing the most suitable ones that will assist in the collection and analysis of data to resolve the identified problems (Holden and Lynch, 2004). Research methodology incorporates a holistic approach to carry out the entire process of a study, beginning with the choice of theoretical underpinnings and techniques of data collection and analysis, and extending to develop objective-based solutions to the identified problems (Rajasekar *et al.* 2006).

The current research aims to analyse the impact of business strategy (independent variable) on important constructs such as customer satisfaction, customer retention (dependent variables) and to provide recommendations to mitigate the negative impact on clients. In order to achieve this aim, it has been demarcated into a range of objectives and questions that underpin the research questions. The research methodology designed for the current study intends to collect data to meet the following objectives -

- To evaluate the underpinning business strategies, and customer retention and customer satisfaction models, thereby gaining knowledge by a thorough review of the existing literature
- To examine the importance of marketing strategies, especially CRM, that favour customer retention and satisfaction in Ozio
- To critically evaluate the marketing frameworks and business strategies that help to mitigate the negative impact on customers of Ozio
- To identify the positive and negative influences of marketing strategies on the business and customers perspectives of Ozio
- To recommend how the negative influences of these marketing strategies can be overcome and better customer retention strategies can be implemented in Ozio

3.2 Research philosophies

According to Morgan (2007), any research enquiry is based on certain philosophical suppositions in terms of what encompasses 'valid research' and which methodology is most appropriate for knowledge development in a given study. Therefore, in order to carry out and evaluate any research study, it is necessary to identify what the basic assumptions are.

Research philosophies intrinsically replicate the researcher's beliefs and values about the world, and the phenomena to be investigated (Peters, 2012). On the basis of such beliefs, a particular philosophical perspective or set of philosophical viewpoints are selected to carry out the research. In this context, the key philosophical assumptions that can be followed in social research relate to positivism, post-positivism, interpretivism, realism and pragmatism.

3.2.1 Positivism

Positivism assumes that observation and reasoning based on careful interpretation are the best ways to comprehend human behaviour and that the basis of true knowledge is the experience of senses that can be gained through experimentation (Uddin and Hamiduzzaman, 2009). The followers of positivism suppose that reality is given objectively and can be measured using instruments that are not dependent on the researcher (Saunders et al., 2009), thereby implying that knowledge is subject to quantification.

Positivist researchers implement scientific processes and systematise the process of knowledge generation using quantification to increase precision in the explanation of research variables and the relationship between them (Kuipers, 2013). The advocates of positivism consider human behaviour to be passive and controllable by the external environment. Positivism, when applied to a social research, helps to carry out the study in the same manner as followed in the natural sciences.

3.2.2 Interpretivism

Interpretivism opposes the philosophical assumptions of positivism and considers that true knowledge comprises of people's subjective views, experiences, and perceptions of the external world (Bridges, 2010). Interpretivism discards the assumption that true knowledge is always objective and independent of human reasoning; rather it believes that knowledge and

its meaning are acts of human interpretation and judgments (Saunders et al., 2015). The premise of interpretivism is that access to real knowledge is by means of social construction such as reasoning, consciousness, language and shared meanings. The purpose of research following the interpretivist philosophy is about understanding and interpreting social events, human experiences, social structures and the values that individuals attach to these phenomena (Rubadeau, 2015).

3.2.3 Realism

Realism integrates with it the assumptions of positivism and interpretivism (Morgan, 2007). To describe it more explicitly, realism embraces the existence of objects in the universe (as reality) to be independent of human mind, behaviour and beliefs. Nevertheless, it also admits that gaining an understanding of people and their behaviour necessitates acknowledgement of the subjectivity that is innate to individuals (Kuipers, 2013). Realism assumes that social processes and the forces that affect human behaviour and beliefs are beyond human control (Bridges, 2010), and these forces function at the macro-level. Peters (2012) contends that at the micro-level (that is, at the level of individual subjects or human beings), subjective perceptions and insights about reality are crucial in gaining an overall understanding of what is happening. Saunders et al., (2015) do not consider such subjective interpretation to be distinctive and individuals tend to share the same interpretations, mainly because the extrinsic forces influence everyone at the macro level.

3.2.3 Pragmatism

The philosophy of pragmatism is 'outcome-oriented' and researchers following this paradigm are keen to understand the meaning of things (Shields, 1998). It mainly focuses on the end result of research and therefore, places key importance on the research question. Pragmatism supposes that theories may be both generalisable and contextual, and hence can be analysed through 'transferability' from one situation to another (Shook and Margolis, 2007). The followers of this philosophy can maintain both objectivity in the data collection and subjectivity in their own reflections in the same research (Goldkuhl, 2012). Therefore, pragmatism is identified as more of an 'approach' to a social study, rather than a paradigm (Kuipers, 2013). This distinction is justified also because pragmatism helps to offer specific ideas and concepts to what includes valid knowledge, but which may not provide a completely surrounding worldview (Baker and Schaltegger, 2015).

3.3 Justification for following pragmatism

Pragmatism was considered appropriate for the current study in order to carry out mixed methods for data collection by integrating the quantitative and qualitative methods. Pragmatism, defined in simple terms, is a practical approach to solving research problems using a holistic approach and rejecting the differences between two contrasting worldviews (Scotland, 2012). Following the pragmatist viewpoint assisted the collection of quantitative data by surveying the customers of Ozio and scientifically analysing the data to arrive at measurable outcomes. On the other hand, qualitative data was collected by interviewing the senior managers and managers of the same company. Pragmatism helped to build upon the strengths of both positivism and interpretivism and merge these two different worldviews into a single study.

3.4 Research approach

The purpose of the research approach, either inductive or deductive, is to carry out a study to either test specific theories that already exist or fabricate new knowledge. The opposing approaches to social research follow either a general-to-specific process, i.e. deductive, or vice versa, i.e. inductive logic (Gregory and Muntermann, 2011).

3.4.1 Inductive approach

Studies following the inductive logic start with specific observations to arrive at the implicit generalisation of phenomena. In the case of the inductive process, a series of observations are carefully chosen to develop patterns and a tentative hypothesis that can be generalised to a wider population or members of a group faced with a similar situation (Goswami, 2010). College (2014) asserts that researchers following the inductive logic must act as an observer and document the observations in the context of the phenomena being studied, without any prejudice or bias. These observations help to build new theories, laws and beliefs that help to construct scientific knowledge and that are universally applicable (Bilicaand Flores, 2009).

3.4.2 Deductive approach

Studies following the deductive approach constitute the formation of assumptions on the basis of already-existing conceptual frameworks and theories and then design a specific research plan to test those assumptions (Singmann and Klauer, 2011). Hence, the research in social science deduces specific outcomes from the broader premises. Studies following the deductive logic usually require the formulation of a set of hypotheses based on gaps in existing knowledge, and these hypotheses need to be tested using statistical and scientific methods to arrive at objective-based outcomes (Hayes et al. 2010).

3.4.3 Abductive approach

According to Richardson and Kramer (2006), pragmatism relies on abductive reasoning; that is, moving back and forward between the two extremes – inductive and deductive approaches - to integrate theory with data. Abductive reasoning transforms observation into theoretical underpinnings, followed by evaluating the theories by way of action. Researchers employ this approach to integrate quantitative and qualitative data collection methods in a single study, using a sequential approach in which the inductive goals of a qualitative method are developed on the basis of deductive outcomes derived from the quantitative approach, and vice versa (Patokorpi and Ahvenainen, 2009).

3.5 Justification for following the abductive approach

Although the pragmatic worldview was followed in the current study, the approach followed in the current study was largely deductive. The use of both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods aimed at testing the existing theories studied in the literature review. The conceptual models relating to business strategies, relationship marketing, customer relationship management, customer satisfaction theories and service quality models (such as SERVQUAL, SERVPERF), retail service quality scale (RSQS), etc. were tested in terms of their applicability in contemporary business. Moreover, the effectiveness of these underpinning theories and conceptual models were tested in terms of customer retention, satisfaction and mitigating the negative impact that clients face.

Following the deductive approach, the current research started with a comprehensive study of the existing theories and identifying the knowledge gaps that existed in the current academic

domain. This was followed by formulating key research questions reflecting the knowledge gaps, empirical data collection, observation and finally, confirmation of the existing theories and knowledge. The use of the inductive approach was negligible, as the scope for theory-building and development of knowledge was limited. By going backwards and forwards between the open-ended, informal research contexts to a more formal closed-ended deductive setting, it attempts to conduct cross-verification of the findings through in-depth triangulation of the findings obtained from each method.

3.6 Research design

According to Waters (2007), research design usually incorporates two levels. The first level concerns the logic, structure or framework of the research. This relates to knowledge about the nature of the enquiry (such as exploratory, explanatory, or descriptive) which also helps to make decisions whether the investigation needs to be cross-sectional, longitudinal, case studies, experimental, or an appropriate combination these methods (Kothari, 2012).

3.6.1 Exploratory design

According to Jaeger and Halliday (1998), exploratory research is feasible when very little is known about the research problem and it is necessary to conduct a preliminary enquiry to gain clarity about it. Researchers following exploratory research usually maintain an interpretive mindset and the inductive approach so as to develop new theories or knowledge in areas where meagre research exists, and the need to conduct further enquiries is necessary (Davies, 2006). These studies often follow a qualitative approach to data collection and subjective analysis to develop new knowledge based on observation.

3.6.2 Explanatory

Also known as causal research, explanatory research provides deeper explanations of phenomena previously studied. It mainly aims to identify the main research variables that exist in the literature and to gain an understanding of the nature of the relationship that exists between those key variables (White and Roth, 2009). Explanatory studies mainly follow quantitative research and experimentation as a strategy to collect and analyse data. These studies generally a twofold objective, (i) to identify which variables are the cause and which are the effect, and

(ii) to understand the nature of the relationship that the casual variables share and the predicted effect of that relationship.

3.6.3 Descriptive design

Descriptive design relates to finding answers to the research questions from multiple dimensions, such as *Who? What? When? Where? How?* and *How many?* Adopting descriptive research helps to find a concrete answer to previously identified research problems and clearly defined questions (Sloman, 2010). The rationale for using the descriptive design is to better define an already identified problem, attitude, opinion or behaviour held by a sample (group of people) regarding a specific phenomenon (Elliott and Timulak, 2005). Descriptive studies usually have large sample size, from which data in high volumes are collected using quantitative data collection methods, such as survey, and the results are usually put to scientific test using statistical methods (Mansourian, 2008).

3.6.4 Justification for exploratory design

This research followed an exploratory design, as the research problems were largely unknown before initiating the investigation. It was necessary to explore the social phenomena and the underlying issues associated with them, in particular, the current status of CRM in Ozio and the relationship marketing problems that hinder customer satisfaction and retention. The inherent problems associated with the marketing of luxury products and problems in CRM were to be investigated and therefore background information was obtained by an initial review of the existing literature. Exploratory research helped to maintain flexibility and carry out an informal enquiry by reviewing the published literature from multiple sources to gain in-depth knowledge of the chosen topic (Sloman, 2010). Descriptive research was not considered suitable because it follows an inflexible, formal approach when the research problems are clearly apparent. Similarly, an explanatory design was not followed because the purpose of explanatory studies is to establish what relationship exists between the variables defined in the research.

3.7 Research methods

3.7.1 Primary versus secondary sources

Primary research involves collecting data from first-hand sources from a certain sample that has been chosen from a population of interest. It helps to collect data that is of current importance and requires the researcher to be a part of the data collection process (Thomas, 2010). The researcher needs to interact with the research subjects by taking the role of an interviewer or observer to record and document the perceptions or insights shared by the participants.

Secondary research involves data that draws upon existing primary sources of literature to interpret, analyse or discuss an idea or concept. Secondary studies involve knowledge that has already been collected, compiled, recorded and published by others (Thomas, 2010). It also involves case studies, periodicals and reports published by business organisations or government agencies. In the case of academic research, secondary sources involve underpinning journals, articles, books, case studies, reports, empirical research and previously written research papers extracted from academic databases.

3.8 Qualitative versus quantitative data

3.8.1 Quantitative research

Quantitative research involves data collection in a manner that information can be subject to quantification and put to statistical or scientific treatment to advocate or reject 'alternative knowledge claims' (Bryman, 2006). Similar to studies in the natural sciences, quantitative research in social and business research use pre-tested mathematical models as techniques for data analysis. Harwell (2011) considers three historical trends associated with quantitative research, namely research design, measurement and testing procedures, and statistical interpretations.

3.8.2 Qualitative research

According to Neuman (2003), qualitative research is a more holistic approach that encompasses discovery through elaborate human interaction and sharing of subjective information. Allwood

(2012) considers qualitative research to be an unfolding approach taking place in a natural setting that helps the researcher (as interviewer) to develop a level of comprehensive detail from high involvement in real-life experiences. Social phenomena are usually investigated in qualitative research from the viewpoints of human subjects or participants as actors in the social environment (Allwood, 2012). Unlike quantitative data, qualitative information is descriptive in nature and reflects deeper insights and perceptions of the human subjects involved with the phenomena.

3.9 Quantitative data collection strategies

3.9.1 Experiments

According to Creswell (2007), experimentation is a strictly quantitative data collection strategy that helps to test the relationship between key variables. It also helps to test the influence of one variable on another, wherein the variable being influenced is the dependent variable and the one doing the influencing is the independent variable (Allwood, 2012).

3.9.2 Survey

A survey is a strategy to collect information relating to variables in a study from a well-defined or specified number of subjects belonging to the target population. Surveys can be both qualitative and quantitative; however, in the latter case it involves a structured procedure using predefined instruments such as questionnaires (Krosnick, 1999). The research subjects or participants are usually asked closed-ended questions relating to their perceptions, attitude, motivation and behaviour, as well as their demographic characteristics (Harwell, 2011).

3.9.3 Justification for conducting a survey

Conducting a survey is not only cost-effective, but also a feasible strategy to collect data from a large sample size in a limited time period of time (Saunders et al., 2015). It does not require the direct involvement of the researcher as it can be conducted online without the need for physical distribution of questionnaire forms. Surveys involve questionnaires as the instrument of data collection by distributing them using online applications such as Google Forms. This eradicates the need to physically distribute the questionnaires to a large sample size. The

questionnaires were structured and contained mostly closed-ended questions that included variables and concepts discussed in the literature with options to be chosen by the participants.

3.10 Questionnaires design (for survey)

The questionnaires designed for the survey were structured, mostly closed-ended and focused on identifying customer perceptions relating to the marketing strategies of the company. The questionnaires included the variables and concepts discussed in the literature review and were tested through closed-ended questions. The use of the five-point Likert scale helped to measure the customer attitude on a range of parameter ranging from (i) strongly agree; (ii) agree; (iii) neither agree nor disagree; (iv) disagree; and (v) strongly disagree. The examples of questionnaires used in the customer survey are given below –

Does the CRM mechanism have the potential to build relationship with the customers based on trust and mutual understanding?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Nether agree nor disagree <input type="radio"/> Disagree <input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree
The CRM reps/customer care execs are knowledgeable and well trained to provide a satisfactory answer to your queries?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Nether agree nor disagree <input type="radio"/> Disagree <input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree
Are you allowed to touch, feel, and examine the product quality very carefully before buying?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Nether agree nor disagree <input type="radio"/> Disagree <input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree

3. 11 Qualitative data collection strategies

3.11.1 Case studies

According to Yin (2003), a case study is a qualitative research strategy where the researcher conducts in-depth exploration of a phenomena, event, program or activity. Yin (2003) considers the use of case studies to be a holistic approach for examining social phenomena, when the boundaries between such phenomena and their environment are not clear. It is an in-depth investigative method that helps to explore and study a phenomenon in its real-life situation (Noor, 2008).

3.11.2 Ethnography

Ethnographic studies mainly relate to the study of a group of people, such as communities sharing common a culture and lifestyle (Lillis, 2008). Often, the researcher is immersed within the cultural environment of the subjects being studied for prolonged periods, in order to understand their behaviour, attitude and perceptions towards socio-cultural phenomena. It may also involve studying an intact cultural group involving longitudinal research by way of observation and collection of primary data (Riemer, 2008).

3.11.3 Observation

Observation is a qualitative data collection method that involves investigating, listening and watching a phenomenon while it takes place. Bryman (2006) considers observation to be the best approach if the researcher intends to understand the behaviour of people rather than their perceptions and viewpoints. It is also appropriate when the research subjects are deeply involved in the phenomena and are not able to provide any information regarding the same (Neuman, 2014).

3.11.4 Action research

Action research involves a persistent, on-going process of investigation and hence the researcher usually develops long term relationship with the problem (Sale et al., 2002). Researchers following action research intend to set up a process of change and arrive at conclusive outcomes based on such process (Creswell, 2013).

3.11.5 Grounded theory

According to Marshall and Rossman (1995), grounded theory is a qualitative research method where the researcher attempts to obtain an abstract and general theory of an action, process or interaction that is grounded in the perceptions of the respondents in a study. Williams (2007) elucidates that grounded theory starts with empirical data that subsequently develops into theory. Grounded theory is of particular importance for studies in the field of sociology because such research examines the interactions and actions of people in their natural setting (Williams, 2007).

3.11.6 Content analysis

According to Lehmann (2010), content analysis incorporates a systematic and detailed examination of the contents of a specific body of materials to identify patterns or themes. As a qualitative research method, it helps to review different forms of human interpretations, including books, journals, newspapers and other forms of published materials so as to understand patterns or themes, as well as biases (Scotland, 2012).

3.12 Justification for conducting interviews in the current research

While qualitative data collection can take place using a range of strategies and methods such as case studies, observation, ethnography, action research and grounded theory (Sandelowski and Barroso, 2003), etc. the most preferred strategy for the current research was interview. The design of the interview questions was semi-structured and open-ended. This provided adequate opportunities to the participants to express their opinions, perceptions, and to share their experience. The interview questions emphasised the business and marketing strategies that the managers designed in order to retain their customers and to ensure high customer satisfaction, etc. Open-ended interview questions helped the researcher to probe deeply into the organisational values and the corporate aims and objectives that aligned with the business strategies and whether these inclined towards customer satisfaction and retention.

Interviews were carried out with five managers of the Ozio fashion store who had been engaged with the company for more than five years. Interviews were conducted via telephone, as face-to-face interviewing was not possible due to the managers' busy schedules.

Other methods such as a focus group could have been relevant. This would have required bringing together several participants at the same time in a specific venue and asking them to share their viewpoints with the researcher being the coordinator. However, it was not possible to arrange a venue or bring the managers together on a common platform in a specific timeframe. Observation was not considered appropriate because it requires examining the activities, body language, attitudes and behaviour of the subjects, which would probably not have helped in the clear understanding of the business and marketing strategies of the company. A case study was not appropriate because it requires a sufficient number of cases to be available in primary or secondary sources reflecting the phenomena to be studied, i.e. business strategies for customer satisfaction and retention that were not available.

3.12.1 Interview schedule

The interview schedule for the interview included semi-structured, open-ended questions that allowed the respondents to openly convey their opinions, viewpoints and perceptions. Open-ended questions also allowed the managers to share their experiences, emotions and critical insights into the problems being investigated through the interview. The interview questions focused on the marketing strategies designed and implemented by the marketing department to acquire customers, the nature of marketing mix and marketing communications (marcomm), etc. that supported the business strategies.

The interview also emphasised the company's approach towards relationship marketing and associated business strategies, such as customer relationship management (CRM), use of digital marketing and Social-CRM (CRM integrated with social media), that help to better interact with the customers, build relationships, enhance their level of satisfaction, promote loyalty to the brand and retain them. Similarly, several other variables and concepts studied in the literature review, specific to the fashion industry such as sensory marketing (with its components such as touch, sound, smell, sight etc), were also used to formulate the interview questions and to ask whether such marketing tactics were a part of their business strategies. Open-ended questions for the managerial interviews were designed in the following manner –

Q) What are the CRM strategies implemented by the company, as a part of the marketing strategy? Does it help to control/ remove negative customer impressions about the company? Please elaborate

Q) How is service quality related to marketing strategies and practices at Ozio? How does it relate to customer satisfaction and retention?

Q) As a fashion (luxury) does sensory marketing result in better customer satisfaction? Does the company follow it? Does it also help in customer retention? Please elaborate

3.13 Justification for use of mixed methods

‘Mixed methods ‘is a methodological term used when both quantitative and qualitative data are integrated in the same study to utilise the benefits of both methodologies. Harwell (2011) considers quantitative methods to be highly formalised and more unambiguously controlled as compared to qualitative methods, which has an assortment that is more precisely defined and comparatively close to social sciences. As opposed to quantitative methodology, qualitative methodology is one where the data collection procedure is not rigorously formal, the scope of the study is less likely to be defined (Neuman, 2014), and a more philosophical approach is adopted to data collection and analysis (Antwi and Hamza, 2015). Potential researchers need to familiarise themselves with the disparity between these two methods and determine whether a mixed approach should be undertaken to eliminate the weaknesses of each method when used on their own.

While most of the authors consider mixed methods to be a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches, Allwood (2012) argues that it incorporates a pragmatic worldview of mixing two different philosophies, research processes and a research design orientation that is comprehensive in nature. Therefore, mixed method research is a type of enquiry that integrates both quantitative and qualitative approaches, concepts and methods in a particular research or a sequence of related studies involving single or multiple phases within the philosophical paradigm of pragmatism, and conceptual lenses that guide the methodological plan for carrying out the study (Antwi and Hamza, 2015).

Blending both quantitative and qualitative approaches helps to produce a conclusive outcome that offers significant contributions of both. The advantages of implementing mixed methods for this research are as follows –

- An obvious weakness of the quantitative method is that it is weaker in terms of understanding the context or environment in which the subjects share their opinion and the complete voice of the participants is not heard (Kothari, 2012). Qualitative research, on the other hand, is deficient in the sense that the personal involvement and interpretations of the researcher may result in a bias in the findings. Mixing both methods helps to overcome these weaknesses and gain comprehensive evidence for finding answers to the research problems than each of the methods used on their own.
- Mixed methods help to follow a flexible approach to data collection rather than being tied up to a formal and structured approach as in quantitative research (Saunders et al., 2015). This allows the researcher to collect data from multiple sources to gain deeper understanding of the research problems (qualitative method) and find precise answers to the research problems using a structured and systematic approach (quantitative methods).
- Mixed methods help in better triangulation of the empirical data with the research problems and literature review. Usually, the numerical data collected through quantitative research can be backed up, cross-examined and validated with the rich, in-depth and elaborate information obtained through qualitative methods.

3.14 How each objective has been met [using mixed methods]

Both of the methods - quantitative and qualitative - were applied to conduct customer surveys and managerial interviews, respectively. Initially, a review of the extant underpinning literature was carried out by re-evaluating relevant journals, articles, books and published research papers to fulfil the **1stObjective** of the research, i.e. to understand the theoretical concepts of business strategies, especially marketing strategies, customer retention, customer satisfaction as they apply to luxury fashion brands.

Quantitative methodology was subsequently used to survey approximately 200 customers of the chosen luxury fashion brand, Ozio using primary research to obtain data to fulfil the **2ndObjective**. The customers' perceptions were identified with regards to the importance of marketing strategies that lead to satisfaction and encourage them to retain their custom with

the company. Using structured, closed-ended questionnaires, customers' perceptions were obtained regarding the effectiveness of Ozio's customer relationship strategy (CRM), availability of discounts and promotions, building relationships, after-sales services, marketing communications, service quality and strategies for customer retention.

The qualitative methodology was used by conducting interviews with three managers of the same company as primary research to obtain data/information to fulfil the **3rdObjective**, i.e. to evaluate in a critical manner whether such marketing frameworks (as examined in the **2ndObjective**) and business strategies help to mitigate the negative impact on customers. Interviews also included probing managers about the use of sensory marketing tactics, a key requirement in luxury fashion brands, and how they lead to customer satisfaction. Managerial interviews also involved seeking managers' views about what kind of marketing caused customers to develop negative perceptions about the brand/company.

The **4thObjective** was fulfilled by revisiting the data obtained from both customer survey and managerial interviews. The objective was intended to identify the positive and negative influences of the marketing strategies on the business and customers' perspectives. Rich, in-depth and descriptive information obtained by interviewing managers helped to understand the positive and negative influences of specific marketing approaches that led to customer dissatisfaction and switchover intention. On the other hand, findings from the customer survey emphasised those marketing activities that were not advocated by customers, caused customer dissatisfaction and resulted in their intention to switch over to a different brand.

Meanwhile, the **5thObjective**, relating to recommendations to be given to the marketing department of Ozio, was based on the gaps and shortcomings identified in their marketing activities causing customer dissatisfaction and difficulty in retaining them. The key recommendations were based on the findings (marketing gaps and shortcomings) that emerged automatically from the overall data analysis.

The following table shows how quantitative and qualitative method was used to fulfil each of the objectives -

Research method	Objectives met using quantitative/qualitative method
Qualitative (Review of existing literature)	To evaluate the underpinning business strategies, customer retention and customer satisfaction models, thereby gaining knowledge by a thorough review of the existing literature
Quantitative (Customer surveys)	To examine the importance of marketing strategies that favour customer retention and satisfaction
Qualitative (Managerial interviews)	To critically evaluate whether such marketing frameworks and business strategies help to mitigate the negative impact on customers
Quantitative (Customer surveys) + Qualitative (Managerial interviews)	To identify the positive and the negative influences of the marketing strategies on the business and customers' perspectives
Automatically emerged from the overall findings	To recommend how the negative influences of these marketing strategies can be overcome and better customer retention strategies be implemented

3.15 Sampling strategies

Probability sampling involves a scientific process of drawing samples from an already identified population according to already defined laws of chance, wherein each element has some explicitly pre-assigned possibility of being chosen (Newman and Benz, 1998). The various types of probability sampling include systematic sampling, cluster sampling, stratified sampling, area sampling and multi-stage sampling.

A total of **200 customers** of Ozio were chosen to take part in the survey. Sampling of the customers involved probability sampling, a simple random technique. Simple random sampling allows equal opportunity for each individual in the population to be selected without any bias (Newman and Benz, 1998). It facilitated the selection of a large sample size in a very limited time in an unbiased manner.

Non-probability sampling is a process where the desired number of sampling units are deliberately chosen or selected purposely on the basis of an object of enquiry, so that only the important elements reflecting the true characteristics of the population are chosen (Thomas, 2010). Sampling for **three marketing managers** to take part in the interview was undertaken using a non-probability convenience sampling process. This helped to sample those managers who were easily available and willing to take part in the interview.

Sampling process	Sample size	Data collection strategy
Probability -Simple random sampling	200 customers	Survey
Non-probability - Purposive sampling	3 managers	Interview

3.16 Analysis of research findings

Analysis of quantitative data encompasses transforming raw data obtained from surveys or experiments into meaningful and readable information by applying scientific formulae or statistical principles (McLellan et al., 2003). This may involve calculating the frequencies of the dependent and/or independent variables to arrive at measurable outcomes.

The findings obtained from the survey comprised the raw data that was coded into an MS Excel spreadsheet for filtering, purifying and making the data readable. Using simple in-built formulae, the cumulative data against each question was converted into a percentage, so that the data could be presented with the help of tables and graphs. This also helped to explain the results by referring to visual aids and discussing the findings in the context of the literature already reviewed in the second chapter.

Analysis of qualitative data encompasses reducing and making appropriate sense of the exhaustive information, subjective in nature, which is collected through deeper interrogation with the subjects or through observation. Filtering the exhaustive information also helps to segregate the similar, dissimilar and conflicting responses shared by the subjects. Noor (2008) argues that qualitative data analysis characteristically revolves around the interpretations and judgments made by the researcher analysing the data.

The researcher needs to remain unbiased and transparent while designing the themes that match the research questions and the collected data. The researcher is, however, required to formulate

certain themes that reflect the research problems and questions and discuss the findings against each of the themes. It is also crucial that the researcher makes interpretations and judgments in a structured manner, as qualitative data is not as reliable as quantitative data (Rajasekar et al., 2006). While analysing qualitative data, it is essential that the researcher cautiously considers the importance of ‘spoken words’ and the context in which information is collected. Importance should also be given to the sensibleness and consistency of opinions, frequency or the intensity of statements made by the participants and the emerging themes that arise (Ketchenet al., 2008).

Narrative data and expressive information obtained from the interviews was interpreted by carefully examining the transcripts for similar and conflicting sets of responses . The analysis was carried out according to specific themes that underpinned the research problems and the questions discussed in the first chapter. While discussing the findings, the theoretical studies conducted in the literature review were revisited for triangulation. The in-depth information collected from the interview helped to back-up and cross-examine the figurative information collected from the survey.

3.17 Ethical considerations

The research was conducted in compliance with the principles of the Data Protection Act, 1998. Hence, the names of the research participants have been kept anonymous, while any data/information shared by them was maintained confidentially. Data was stored and saved in a password-protected computer to avoid any unauthorised access.

None of the participants in the sample was forced or coerced to take part in the survey or the interviews. Their participation was on a completely voluntary basis. The participants were also informed about their rights to withdraw from the research at any point of time or to refuse to take part in the primary research even after being sampled.

3.18 Limitations and delimitations

Limitations in research denote the characteristics of the methodology or research design that influence or impact the interpretation of the findings of the study being undertaken (Rajasekar

et al., 2006). Identification of any research limitations is important in research because it helps to understand how the findings fit into the research context, analyses the validity of the undertaken work and assigns a level of credibility to the final outcomes (Sloman, 2010). The current study was conducted under certain limitations, particularly with regards to the primary data collection and analysis. The participants may have given biased responses while being interviewed and this could have affected the validity of the findings.

Delimitations, on the other hand, involve an act of fixing boundaries or limits that have been set for the study (Sloman, 2010); for instance, the theoretical underpinnings not considered for the study or the research methods that were not included, etc. The current research involved identifying the marketing strategies that are crucial for achieving customer satisfaction and customer retention while eradicating negative impacts on customers. Marketing strategies involve a range of theoretical models such as marketing planning, customer segmentation, targeting, positioning (STP), branding and brand management, communication mix, etc., which were not included in the literature review. The marketing theories and models associated with relationship marketing, CRM, marketing mix, integration of service quality in the marketing strategies, product repositioning, sensory-based marketing and customer satisfaction theories with its key constructs were all included for review and discussion. As regards methodology, selective choice of data collection methods, namely survey and interview for quantitative and qualitative approaches were considered suitable.

3.19 Conclusion

This chapter has outlined the most suitable and appropriate research methods that formed the methodology and design for this study. The choices were made from a range of research elements that could have been suitable for undertaking the research, data collection and finding the answers to the research problems. The methodological framework designed for the current study was however appropriate in terms of implementation, feasibility of use, cost-effectiveness and the collection of rigorous data that could be carefully interpreted to resolve the research problems.

Chapter 4

Findings and Data Analysis

4.1 Introduction

The current chapter is the data analysis and findings section and presents the results obtained from the survey and the interviews. Initially, the results collected by surveying 200 customers of Ozio are diagrammatically represented using tables and graphs to illustrate the findings and form the basis for the subsequent discussions. In the second part of the chapter, the rich, in-depth and subjective information collected from the interviews is presented and discussed in triangulation with the theoretical studies carried out in the literature review in chapter 2. Part A presents and analyses the data obtained from the customer surveys, while Part B analyses the in-depth, descriptive and elaborate responses obtained from the managerial interviews.

4.2 Part A – Quantitative data analysis

Q1) Please indicate your gender?

Gender	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Male	61%	122
Female	39%	78
Transsexual	-	0
Total	100%	200

Table 1: Gender

Chart 1: Gender

The majority of Ozio customers taking part in the survey were male (61%), while the remaining 39% were female. The data indicates that the company has a reasonable mix of customers, as regards to the gender distribution of people who visit their stores.

Q2)Please indicate the age group you belong to?

Age group	Frequency(percentage)	Frequency (n)
Below 20	11%	23
20-25	24%	49
26-35	37%	73
36-45	15%	29
46-55	13%	26
Above 55	-	0
Total	100%	200

Table 2: Age Group

Chart 2: Age Group

Most of the participants in the survey belong to the 26-35 age group, followed by 24% between 20 and 25 years of age. 15 % of customers were aged between 36 and 45, while no one was above 55 years of age. Overall, the data indicates that most of the customers are young or middle-aged while elderly consumers are very few.

Q3) Please indicate your marital status?

Marital status	Frequency(percentage)	Frequency (n)
Married	54%	108
Single	21%	43
Living with partner	12%	24
Divorced	4%	8
Others	9%	17
Total	100%	200

Table 3: Marital status

Chart 3: Marital status

The majority of customers taking part in the survey were married (54%), while 21% were single. 12% were living with partner, 4% divorced and 9% declared some other marital status. Overall, the data indicates that most customers were married and accounted for twice the number of single participants.

Q4) Please indicate your occupation?

Occupation	Frequency(percentage)	Frequency (n)
Employed	46%	92
Self-employed	24%	48
Student	6%	12
Housewife	8%	16
Sports personnel	-	0
Not working	5%	9
Others	12%	23

Total	100%	200
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Table 4: Occupation

Chart 4: Occupation

46% Ozio of customers participating in the survey were employed, while 24% were self-employed. Apart from these two groups, there were also customers such as housewives, students, those not working and those belonging to some other occupational status.

Q5) For how long have you been purchasing from Ozio/ or been a customer of this company?

Tenure with the company	Frequency(percentage)	Frequency (n)
Less than 1 year	5%	11
Around 1-3 years	15%	31

Around 3-5years	44%	88
Around 5-7 years	27%	53
Around 7-10 years	9%	17
More than 10 years	-	0
Total	100%	200

Table 5: Number of years with Ozio as a customer

Chart 5: Number of years with Ozio as a customer

The findings indicate that 44% of customers had been purchasing from the company for 3-5 years, while 27% had been making purchases for between 5 and 7 years. 15% had been making purchase for around 1-3 years, while only 9% for around 7 to 10 years.

Q6) The Company (Ozio) has a dedicated CRM system backed with customer services team to help the customers?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	23%	46
Agree	36%	72
Nether neither agree nor disagree	13%	26
Disagree	18%	37
Strongly disagree	10%	19
Total	100%	200

Table 6: Whether the Company (Ozio) has a dedicated CRM system

Chart 6: Whether the Company (Ozio) has a dedicated CRM system

The above question was asked to identify whether the company has a dedicated CRM system, backed by a customer services team, to help customers. A positive response was obtained from 59% of customers (23% SA + 26% A) who gave an affirmative response, while 28% (18% D + 10% SD) shared a negative response.

The findings indicate that Ozio maintains a CRM system and hence its business strategy is inclined towards ‘relationship marketing’. CRM is an essential component of relationship marketing which is strategic in nature. Supporting this view, CRM is a strategic approach to relationship marketing, a philosophy, technology, or a tool that is relevant to the contemporary business world. Maintaining a dedicated customer services team is essential to operate the CRM functions because it is considered to be a process that integrates technology with the human factor to interact and build relationship with the customers. This helps to deliver superior value to the customers, enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty (Wahlberg et al., 2009).

Q7) The Company (Ozio) makes use of its CRM capabilities to acquire customers like you?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	46%	93
Agree	29%	58
Nether neither agree nor disagree	8%	17
Disagree	6%	11
Strongly disagree	11%	21
Total	100%	200

Table 7: The Company (Ozio) makes use of its CRM capabilities to acquire customers

The Company (Ozio) makes use of its CRM capabilities to acquire customers

Chart 7: The Company (Ozio) makes use of its CRM capabilities to acquire customers

The majority of customers in the survey - 75% (46% SA + 29% A) - shared an affirmative response that the use of CRM was made by the company for customer acquisition. Comparatively, a much lower 17% (6% D + 11% SD) shared a negative response, while 8% preferred to remain neutral.

CRM is relationship marketing tool used in the art of acquiring customers, managing data and building long term customer relationships. The idea of CRM as a mechanism to acquire customers has been supported by Ahearne et al. (2012) and Saarijärvi et al.(2013), who focus on CRM as a platform to capture customer data, understand customer requirements and develop marketing capabilities to enable better sales and service delivery. Therefore, the data shared by customers while enquiring about any product or service is captured by CRM and such useful data is made use of to acquire additional such customers.

Q8) The Company (Ozio) makes use of CRM to inform you about the fresh arrivals in the store in a timely manner?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	14%	28
Agree	32%	65
Nether neither agree nor disagree	13%	27
Disagree	22%	43
Strongly disagree	19%	37
Total	100%	200

Table 8: Using CRM to inform about the fresh arrivals

Chart 8: Using CRM to inform about the fresh arrivals

A mixed response was obtained when asked whether the CRM personnel of Ozio informed customers about the fresh arrivals in the store. 46% (14% SA +32% SA) shared a positive response, while the responses of 41% (22% D + 19% SD) did not corroborate with them.

As a strategic relationship marketing approach, one of the key functions of CRM is to keep customers informed about the product and service offerings, foster more interactions, add more value to services offered to the customers, and facilitate increased business transactions (Reimer and Brecker, 2015). CRM is also considered to be an informative database, a contact centre and a helpdesk used for providing updates to the customers and keeping them informed.

Q9) The marketers/CRM execs make frequent calls asking you make a purchase based on promotional offers and discounts?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	38%	77
Agree	32%	64
Nether neither agree nor disagree	8%	16
Disagree	14%	28
Strongly disagree	8%	15
Total	100%	200

Table 9: The CRM execs make frequent calls asking to make purchases

Chart 9: The CRM execs make frequent calls asking to make purchases

The majority (70%) of customers taking part in the survey (38% SA +32%A) shared a positive response that the marketers/CRM executives make frequent calls asking them to make a purchase based on promotional offers and discounts. In comparison, a negligible 22% (14% D + 8% SD) responded negatively to the question.

As discussed in the literature review, CRM is used by the company to build customer relationships and to nurture such relationships to strengthen customer retention. However, these findings indicate that Ozio makes use of its CRM capabilities to make frequent calls to the customers in terms of a sales-centric attitude. This behaviour of the marketers represents the transactional marketing perspective of CRM, wherein the company utilises customer data to make frequent calls to make them aware of promotional discounts and offers and convince them to make purchases. CRM, therefore, is utilised not only to acquire customers, build relationship, resolve customer queries and complaints, but also to promote sales. However, the extent to which frequent marketing calls shape customers’ positive or negative attitudes towards the company is identified in the next question.

Q10) If you strongly agree/agree to the above question, do you consider the frequent marketing calls to be intervening, disturbing and resulting in dissatisfaction?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	31%	62
Agree	25%	51
Nether neither agree nor disagree	16%	33
Disagree	18%	35
Strongly disagree	10%	19
Total	100%	200

Table 10: Whether frequent marketing calls are intervening, disturbing and causing dissatisfaction

Chart 10: Whether frequent marketing calls are intervening, disturbing and causing dissatisfaction

A large percentage (56%) of customers taking part in the survey affirmed that the frequent marketing calls made by the CRM representatives of the company was intervening, disturbing and results in dissatisfaction. Meanwhile, a much smaller 28% (18% D + 10% SD) did not confirm to the question, and a good 16% neither agreed nor disagreed to the idea.

The review of the underpinning literature indicates that CRM is identified as a marketing strategy, a technology and a process for building customer relationships to deliver superior and increased customer satisfaction (Wahlberg et al.,2009). Other researchers such as Ahearne et al. (2012) also perceive CRM as a strategic marketing tool that helps to acquire customers, manage relationships and retain customers to increase profitability and long-term value.

While the rationale behind implementing CRM is to acquire, build and nurture customer relationships, etc., often marketers consider it to be an informative database, a contact-centre, helpdesk or a means to offer promotions. Likewise, this is the case with the marketers of Ozio, who seems to consider CRM as a tool to achieve higher sales by informing customers about available promotions. Adopting a sales-centric strategy with the use of CRM, rather than from a relational perspective, is considered to be one of the main flaws of a CRM strategy. In the case of Ozio, the use of CRM for making frequent calls to customers to foster sales is considered by customers as intervening, disturbing and results in customer dissatisfaction.

Q11) The CRM representatives undertake initiatives such as ‘customer satisfaction surveys’ to identify the level of customer satisfaction?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	14%	27
Agree	23%	46
Nether neither agree nor disagree	28%	56
Disagree	25%	49
Strongly disagree	10%	21
Total	100%	200

Table 11: Whether CRM representatives undertake initiatives such as ‘customer satisfaction surveys’

Chart 11: Whether CRM representatives undertake initiatives such as ‘customer satisfaction surveys’

As regards to whether the CRM representatives regularly interact with the customers to identify their level of satisfaction, 37% (14% SA + 23% A) shared an affirmative response, while a close 35% (25% D + 10% SD) said the opposite. It was however notable that 28% of customers preferred to remain neutral.

As discussed in the literature review, CRM is considered a central element to managing relationships with customers while making use of tactics to deal with their issues and problems by maintaining an interactive platform (Reimer and Becker, 2015). Meanwhile, Awasthi and Sangle (2012) focus on electronic CRM as a means of dealing with customers' issues by allowing them to express their concerns, thoughts and complaints. The importance of conducting activities such as customer satisfaction surveys through CRM is emphasised by authors such as Rahimi and Koza (2017), who consider it necessary for companies to encourage customers to take part in such surveys.

The authors deem it necessary for CRM representatives to manage customer information, log their complaints, carry out repeat follow ups and conduct customer satisfaction surveys to engage customers and locate the 'pain areas' that hinder customer satisfaction. This in turn helps staff to undertake marketing activities that assist in increasing the level of customer satisfaction and ultimately improve retention capabilities.

Q12) The CRM mechanism has the potential to build relationship with the customers based on trust and mutual understanding?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	15%	31
Agree	13%	27
Nether neither agree nor disagree	24%	48
Disagree	33%	65
Strongly disagree	15%	29
Total	100%	200

Table 12: CRM mechanism has the potential to build relationships with customers

Chart 12: CRM mechanism has the potential to build relationships with customers

48% of respondents (33%D + 15%SD) shared a negative response as regards to whether the CRM system of Ozio has the potential to build relationships with customers based on trust and

mutual understanding. In comparison, a smaller percentage, 28% (15% SA+ 13% A) shared and affirmative response to the question.

The review of the literature indicates that the sole purpose of CRM implementation in an organisation is to build and strengthen customer relationships. CRM is an integration of technology, people, and process to acquire customers, and build and nurture relationships. Ahearne et al. (2012) supports this view and considers CRM as an advanced level of the strategic relationship marketing approach to manage customer relationships and retention in order to generate long term profitability.

In addition, the CRM continuum designed by Wahlberg et al. (2009) considers CRM as a holistic approach of managing customer relationships to create increased shareholder value. The relationship dimension of CRM extends to eCRM and researchers such as Faaseet al. (2011) consider it as a strategic tool to develop customer relationships and extend personalisation.

Q13) Overall the CRM system is tailored according to the specific needs of customer groups?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	10%	21
Agree	16%	32
Nether neither agree nor disagree	23%	45
Disagree	36%	72
Strongly disagree	15%	30
Total	100%	200

Table 13: CRM system is tailored according to the specific needs of customer groups

Chart 13: CRM system is tailored according to the specific needs of customer groups

The majority of the customers in the survey, 51% (36% D + 15% SD), denied that the CRM system of the company is tailored to the specific needs of customer groups, while a meagre 26% (10%SA + 16% A) shared a positive perception. In this regard, 23% preferred to remain neutral.

Apart from being a platform for interaction and relationship building, CRM also helps to understand the varying needs of customers and tailor products and services accordingly to meet their specific needs. This helps to enhance service quality levels by bringing improvements to the customer services (Harrigan et al., 2011). As a holistic framework, CRM provides increased opportunities to relationship marketers to use customers' data to customise marketing strategies by understanding their needs and co-create value (Verhoef et al., 2010). In addition, Longet al. (2013) also emphasise the necessity of using customer data from the CRM tool to customise product and service offerings according to consumer groups. However, findings from the survey indicate that the CRM strategies are barely customised according to specific customer needs, indicating that a uniform CRM strategy is meant for all customers.

Q14) The CRM system of Ozio is well designed in terms of providing efficient after sales services to the customers?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	8%	17
Agree	11%	23
Nether neither agree nor disagree	21%	41
Disagree	38%	73
Strongly disagree	22%	43
Total	100%	200

Table 14: CRM is well designed to provide efficient after sales services to the customers

Chart 14: CRM is well designed to provide efficient after sales services to the customers

The majority of customers in the survey, 60% (38% D + 22%SD), denied that Ozio’s CRM strategies are well designed to provide efficient after sales services to customers. In

comparison, a meagre 19% (8% SA + 11% A) had experienced such efficient services from the CRM system implemented by the company.

The review of the literature indicates that ‘after-sales service’ is the most crucial activity in the CRM process maintained by organisations. After-sales services, as described by Milovic (2012), relates to merchandise return, replacement, seeking customer feedback about the purchase made, experiences, complaints handling and intention to place subsequent orders, which can be dealt with through CRM. Emphasising the importance of after-sales services in CRM, Yu et al. (2015) consider it to be a crucial factor to gain customer trust in the company, engage customers and improve retention capabilities. However, in case of Ozio, the findings indicate that the level of after-sales services provided through CRM is subject to be questioned, as a majority of customers do not consider it to be efficient.

Q15) Complaints logged through the CRM/complaints management system of the company addressed in a timely manner?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	33%	67
Agree	29%	58
Nether neither agree nor disagree	9%	19
Disagree	15%	29
Strongly disagree	14%	27
Total	100%	200

Table 15: Whether complaints are addressed in a timely manner

Chart 15: Whether complaints are addressed in a timely manner

In response to whether the complaints logged through the CRM/complaints management system of the company addressed in a timely manner, a significantly higher percentage 62% (33%SA + 29%A) shared an affirmative answer.

As discussed in the literature review, CRM is considered to be a multi-channel communication platform where customers can log their complaints. CRM systems that are designed using internet capabilities or through the company websites with easy navigation can log the complaints, obtain access to resolutions in real time, provided a robust eCRM is maintained by the company. The process approach considers CRM to be a customer-centric tool and a comprehensive business process that helps to provide flawless customer services to the service users in real time and also minimise the number of customer complaints.

Referring to the SERVQUAL model designed by Parasuraman et al. (1988), ‘responsiveness’ is a crucial element in the service delivery process. This element is also relevant in the area of CRM as customers expect the service provider to respond to their queries in a prompt manner. In case of Ozio, the CRM personnel are able to respond to customer complaints in a timely manner, indicating that the CRM mechanism is responsive.

Q16) The CRM reps/customer care execs are knowledgeable and well trained to provide satisfactory answer to your queries?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	26%	53
Agree	32%	65
Nether neither agree nor disagree	14%	27
Disagree	16%	32
Strongly disagree	12%	23
Total	100%	200

Table 16: CRM reps/customer care execs are knowledgeable and well trained

Chart 16: CRM reps/customer care execs are knowledgeable and well trained

The majority of survey participants, 58% (26% SA + 32% A), shared a positive response that the CRM reps/customer care executives are knowledgeable and well-trained and are able to

provide satisfactory answers to customer queries. In contrast, 28% (16% D + 12% SD) denied this and shared a negative perception.

The capability of the service provider (or customer service personnel representing the CRM) must ensure that customers feel assured with the services. Hence, they need to be well-trained and knowledgeable enough to provide appropriate answers to customer queries so that the latter feel assured about the services. Well-trained CRM staff also ensure that the level of services provided to customers is dependable and reliable and meets their expectations.

Q17) The company follows multichannel approach (using telephone calls/mobile apps/ online chat/emails/ postal letters) etc to foster easy communication with the customers?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	13%	27
Agree	34%	68
Nether neither agree nor disagree	12%	25
Disagree	29%	57
Strongly disagree	12%	23
Total	100%	200

Table 17: Ozio follows a multichannel communication approach to foster easy communication with customers

Ozio follows multichannel communication approach to foster easy communication with the customers

Chart 17: Ozio follows a multichannel communication approach to foster easy communication with customers

As regards to whether the company follows a multichannel approach to foster easy communication with customers, 47% (13% SA + 34% A) shared an affirmative response, while a close 41% (29% D + 12% SD) shared a negative response.

A multi-channel approach to CRM ensures that the company uses different communication modes and channels to connect and interact with the customers and makes it easier for them to reach the marketers. The process perspective of CRM considers the inclusion of several communication channels to provide customers with different forms of services to strengthen customer loyalty (Kocoglu and Kirmaci, 2012). As an approach towards multi-channel communication, companies often maintain an electronic-based customer relationship management (eCRM) approach, thereby allowing customers to express their perceptions and thoughts, and make the marketers aware of any issues to be resolved in real time (Milovic, 2012).

Q18) The company extensively uses digital communication channels such as social media to interact with the customers on 24x7 basis?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	31%	63
Agree	38%	76
Nether neither agree nor disagree	10%	19
Disagree	13%	26
Strongly disagree	8%	16
Total	100%	200

Table 18: Ozio extensively uses digital communication channels such as social media to interact with customers on a 24x7 basis

Chart 18: Ozio extensively uses digital communication channels such as social media to interact with customers on a 24x7 basis

The above question was asked in order to understand whether the company makes use of digital communication channels, especially social media, to connect and interact with customers on a round-the-clock basis. The majority of participants - 69% (31% SA + 38% SA) -shared a positive viewpoint, confirming that social media was used by the company, while 21% (13% D + 8% SD) did not share an affirmative response.

The literature indicates that contemporary business organisations are currently making extensive use of social media to connect and interact with their target audiences (Sigala, 2011) and to share information about products and brands. Social media communication is used as a business strategy to foster round-the-clock (24/7) interaction with customers to address their queries, issues, problems and experiences, based on which a deeper understanding of those customers can be gained. Social media channels such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and others are used extensively by companies as a marketing communication strategy, as they have wide acceptance among consumers. The survey findings reveal that Ozio makes extensive use of social media as a digital communication strategy to interact with customers on a round-the clock-basis.

Q19) The CRM system is integrated with social media (social CRM) to ensure customers have access to customer care execs on a 24x7 basis?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	9%	19
Agree	13%	27
Nether neither agree nor disagree	25%	49
Disagree	34%	67
Strongly disagree	19%	38
Total	100%	200

Table 19: Whether the CRM system is integrated with social media (social CRM)

Chart 19: Whether the CRM system is integrated with social media (social CRM)

As an extension of the previous question, the current question intended to find out whether the company had integrated its CRM system with social media (Social CRM) to better engage with customers and allow them access to CRM personnel on a 24/7 basis. The majority of customers, 53% (34% D + 19% SD), shared a negative response, while only 22% (9% SA + 13%A) shared an affirmative response.

While Ozio makes extensive use of social media to interact with its customers, it has failed to integrate its CRM capabilities with those interactive channels. Academic studies examined in the literature review indicate that Social CRM is more of a business strategy rather than a database that helps to manage customer information or deliver customer services. The importance of integrating CRM with social media is emphasised by Zouaoui et al. (2016), who consider it to be a business strategy supported by the use of technology and information systems. Social CRM as a business strategy also helps to engage customers in a collaborative environment while offering reciprocally beneficial value to both customers and marketers.

The main benefit of Social CRM is considered to be customer engagement, which provides customers with a collaborative environment to raise their issues, discuss the same with CRM representatives and obtain faster solutions to their problems in real time. Moreover, as a business strategy, Social CRM can engage customers through online social forums, contests,

discussion boards, etc., thereby enhancing the likelihood of retaining customers (Lehmkuhland Jung, 2013).

As regards Ozio, the company is missing the opportunity to engage its customers, build rapport, track their activities and behaviour, and allow them to express their views, issues and problems in a collaborative manner. The company does make use of social media but the absence of CRM in the social media environment hinders the process of customer engagement and brand loyalty.

Q20) The customer service offered through CRM or otherwise has been reliable so far for you?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	19%	38
Agree	25%	50
Nether neither agree nor disagree	16%	33
Disagree	21%	41
Strongly disagree	19%	38
Total	100%	200

Table 20: Reliability of CRM as it relates to customer services

Chart 20: Reliability of CRM as it relates to customer services

A mixed response was obtained when asked whether the customer services offered by the company was reliable, as 44% (19% SA + 25% A) shared a positive response and a close 40% (21% D + 19% SD) shared a negative perception.

Reliability is one of the core dimensions of service quality, as represented by the SERVQUAL model, and refers to the ability of the service provider to offer dependable services that are consistent, accurate and designed in accordance with customer expectations (Parasuraman et al., 1988). To provide reliable services, it is necessary for Ozio to deliver the right service from the very first time a customer encounters their services and expects the same level of services on an ongoing basis.

The importance of ‘reliability’ is also emphasised by Dabholkar et al. (1996), who explain the necessity of maintaining a competent and well-trained employee base to deliver the right services and fulfil the promise made for superior service quality. In the case of Ozio, customer services are reliable, as confirmed by most of the participants. However, the scope for providing more reliable services still exists, as many customers are not on the same platform.

Q21) Overall, do you perceive that the CRM system of Ozio is mainly aimed at pushing sales rather than helping customers and keeping them satisfied?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	38%	76
Agree	10%	19
Nether neither agree nor disagree	11%	23
Disagree	29%	58
Strongly disagree	12%	24
Total	100%	200

Table 21: Whether CRM system of Ozio is mainly aimed at pushing sales

Chart 21: Whether CRM system of Ozio is mainly aimed at pushing sales

47% (38% SA + 10% A) of participants shared an affirmative response that the CRM system maintained by Ozio is mainly aimed at pushing sales rather than ensuring that the customers were satisfied. Comparatively, a close 41% (29% D + 12%SD) did not support this idea.

As discussed in the literature, CRM is implemented by an organisation to cultivate and nurture relationships with customers (Shaonand Rahman, 2015) and strengthen the ability of the company to retain the most loyal ones. Rahimi and Kozak (2017) stresses the importance of CRM to manage long-term customer relationships built upon the principles of ‘relationship marketing’, rather than utilising CRM as a tool for transactional marketing purposes.

As a holistic platform, CRM helps firms to shift their marketing orientation from a one-off transactional perspective to a relational approach, implying that it is not meant for pushing sales but rather for developing customer relationships through inclusion and engagement. However, in case of Ozio, many customers have experienced sales calls being made to them by the CRM personnel. This indicates that CRM is often used by Ozio to drive sales which exhibits a transactional marketing orientation and is likely to cause customer dissatisfaction.

Q22) The company has been able to resolve your issues and complaints so far to the best of your satisfaction?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	13%	26
Agree	15%	31
Nether neither agree nor disagree	17%	35
Disagree	42%	83
Strongly disagree	13%	25
Total	100%	200

Table 22: Resolving complaints and issues to the customer’s satisfaction

Resolving complaints and issues to the best of customer satisfaction

Chart 22: Resolving complaints and issues to the customer's satisfaction

As regards to whether the company has been able to resolve the customer issues and complaints to their satisfaction, the majority (55%) shared a negative response (42% D + 13% SD). Comparatively, a smaller 28% (13% SA + 15% A) shared a positive response.

The above question was asked to understand the overall customer perception relating to the customer services offered by Ozio as a part of their marketing strategy. The marketing framework for delivering customer services at Ozio is CRM that works as an analytical model to capture useful data from the customers to customise the marketing strategies for specific groups. This may be one of the reasons why CRM at Ozio is less inclined towards providing customer services leaving the majority of customers dissatisfied.

Q23) Are you allowed to touch, feel, and examine the product quality very carefully before buying?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	55%	111
Agree	25%	49
Nether neither agree nor disagree	7%	14
Disagree	9%	18
Strongly disagree	4%	8
Total	100%	200

Table 23: Whether Ozio allows customers to touch, feel and examine the product quality

Chart 23: Whether Ozio allows customers to touch, feel and examine the product quality

A significantly higher percentage of the customers in the survey (80% - 55% SA + 25%A) confirmed that they were allowed to touch, feel, and examine the product quality very carefully

before buying. Only a small percentage, 13% (9% D + 4% SD), denied and shared a negative response.

As studied in the literature review, the ability to touch and feel the product is an element of sensory marketing practices which are predominately used in the fashion industry. It creates an emotional appeal by arousing the inner feelings of the customer (Consoli, 2010). As a part of the sensory marketing practice, emotional marketing is supported by the use of human senses such as sense of vision, touch, smell, sound and feel, and is used to stimulate customers visiting the store. The diverse range of luxury fashion products offered by Ozio requires them to be examined by customers using their senses of touch and feel, and this is possible at the physical store.

Touch helps consumers to examine the material and fabric quality and compare between different varieties and brands before making a purchase (Petit et al., 2015). Touch facilitates bodily interactions and helps customers to become acquainted with the desired product by facilitating a sense of proximity, intimacy and choice (Hilton, 2015). The sense of touching and feeling products are emotional cues that are a source of pleasure, thereby enriching the customer's shopping experience., As Krishna (2012) points out, consumers not only visit a store to purchase products but also to buy emotional experiences and therefore, the importance of such sensory marketing techniques cannot be undermined.

Q24) The internal store ambience (such as lighting, product display, sound such as music, smell etc) are emotionally appealing to make you feel satisfied as a customer?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	38%	77
Agree	24%	49
Nether neither agree nor disagree	3%	6
Disagree	26%	51
Strongly disagree	9%	17
Total	100%	200

Table 24: Whether internal store ambience is appealing

Chart 24: Whether internal store ambience is appealing

As regards to whether the internal ambience of the Ozio stores were emotionally appealing and helped to satisfy the customers, the majority - 62% (38% SA + 24% A) - shared a positive response, while 35% (26% D + 9% SD) did not believe it was so.

As an extension of the previous question, the current question emphasised internal store ambience, which is a crucial part of sensory marketing techniques. Internal ambience is directed towards the sense of vision, as visual marketing and the use of attractive colours, shades, pictures, displays, lighting, etc. is extremely important to provide a sense of satisfaction to the visitors. As reviewed in the literature, consumers of the fashion industry intend to satisfy their 'search for beauty' and therefore, it is difficult to sell ugliness. The positive internal ambience at Ozio provides 'visual information' to the visiting customers and positions its brand in their minds to stimulate their mood. Such visual cues are important because internal store ambience is generally the first thing that customers notice (Shabgou and Daryani, 2014). These authors also indicate that customers trust their eyes more than the other sensory organs and predominately trust their sense of vision when faced with any doubts in the purchase environment.

As an important constituent of internal ambience, sound supplements vision in the emotional appeal and is considered to be an important sensory marketing technique. In this context, Sidali et al. (2013) considers hearing to be passive and listening as active, as pleasant sound creates a positive appeal during the consumer's decision-making process. In the realm of sound, music aids the internal store ambience, as good music creates a pleasant consumer mood and customers can relate their own personality with the brand (Shabgou and Daryani, 2014).

Internal store ambience supported by a fast music tempo at high volume can increase the excitement state of the consumer, making the shopping experience more satisfying and motivate them to act faster. Good store ambience also lower customers' level of stress, controls instincts of anger and encourages positive consumer behaviour. While the existing literature does not place much emphasis on the effect of store ambience and sensory marketing on consumer satisfaction, the findings from the survey clearly indicate a direct relationship between these constructs.

Q25) The products (product quality, range, availability) offered by the company so far has been up to your expectations?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	43%	87
Agree	26%	52
Nether neither agree nor disagree	6%	11
Disagree	17%	34
Strongly disagree	8%	16
Total	100%	200

Table 25: Whether the products have met customer expectations

Chart 25: Whether the products have met customer expectations

An affirmative response was given by the majority of participants - 69% (43% SA + 26% A) - in that the products (product quality, range and availability) offered by the company so far have been up to their expectations. On the other hand, 23% (17% D + 8% SD) denied that the products have been able to meet their expectations.

According to the Assimilation-Contrast theory of customer satisfaction, if the performance of the products or services availed by a customer falls within the range of acceptance, then the customer will ignore any discrepancy, even if the product/service fails to meet expectations. The customer will experience activation of assimilation and deem the performance to be acceptable. The outcome of such experience is 'customer satisfaction', as the customer will be likely to exhibit satisfaction that is the outcome of acceptance. From this perspective, satisfaction is the function of the extent of discrepancy between the expected performance of the product/service and the its perceived performance (Von Martens and Hilbert, 2011). The findings obtained from the survey indicate that the products availed by the customers from Ozio has met their expectations and hence, the likelihood of customer satisfaction is higher.

Q26) The services (CRM, complaints handling, after-sales services, merchandise return, etc.) provided by the company so far has been up to your expectations?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	9%	19
Agree	17%	33
Nether neither agree nor disagree	9%	18
Disagree	39%	78
Strongly disagree	26%	52
Total	100%	200

Table 26: Whether services have met customer expectations

Chart 26: Whether services have met customer expectations

As an extension of the previous question, the current question focused on the ‘service-scape’ of the company, particularly services associated with CRM such as complaints handling, after-

sales services, return of merchandise, etc. A significantly greater percentage of customers - 65% (39% D + 26% SD) - shared an optimistic response, while 26% (17% A + 9% SA) did not agree with the proposition.

While the majority of the customers in the previous question affirmed that the products offered by the company met their expectations, the majority gave a negative response when asked about the service area. This implies that there are persistent gaps in the ‘services’ that fail to meet customer expectations and therefore may result in customer dissatisfaction.

Q27) Is it essential that the company should always keep you satisfied to retain your custom for long term?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	63%	126
Agree	24%	48
Nether neither agree nor disagree	7%	14
Disagree	4%	9
Strongly disagree	2%	3
Total	100%	200

Table 27: Keeping customers satisfied to retain their custom for the long term

Chart 27: Keeping customers satisfied to retain their custom for the long term

87% (63% SA + 24% A) gave an affirmative response that the company should always keep its customers satisfied in order to retain their custom for the long term, while a very small percentage of respondents said the opposite. The overall responses indicate there exists a direct relationship between customer satisfaction and customer retention, as satisfied customers are more likely to stay with the company for longer as compared to dissatisfied ones.

Q28) How satisfied are you with the experience you have had so far with the quality of services offered by Ozio?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Very satisfied	11%	23
Somewhat satisfied	37%	74
Can't say	7%	14
Dissatisfied	32%	63
Very dissatisfied	13%	26

Total	100%	200
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Table 28: Customer satisfaction with the quality of services

Chart 28: Customer satisfaction with the quality of services

With regards to the level of satisfaction, the majority of customers (37%) were somewhat satisfied and only 11% were very satisfied. 32% indicated that were dissatisfied, while 13% were very dissatisfied.

Improvement in the quality of services, such as customer services, after-sales service, etc. can be brought about by integrating models such as SERVQUAL, the Retail Service Quality Model, and similar models of customer satisfaction to ensure that services are effective and efficient. However, in case of Ozio, the various services availed by the customers in the marketing domain is not satisfying for every customer.

Q29) As a customer are you satisfied enough to recommend others to choose this company/brand?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Strongly Agree	14%	29
Agree	19%	38
Nether neither agree nor disagree	23%	46
Disagree	28%	55
Strongly disagree	16%	32
Total	100%	200

Table 29: Recommending the Ozio brand to others

Chart 29: Recommending the Ozio brand to others

The response was inconsistent among the participants in the survey, as 33% (14% SA + 19% A) confirmed that they were satisfied enough to recommend the Ozio brand to others, while 44% (28% D + 16% SD) did not agree to the question.

Customers' willingness to recommend the brand to others usually indicates that they are satisfied and happy to recommend it to others such as family, friends, acquaintances or peers. The fact that the majority do not show any eagerness to recommend Ozio as a brand to others indicates a lack of satisfaction and a lower possibility of remaining as a loyal customer in the long term.

30) How likely are you to remain loyal to the company for the rest of your life?

Options	Frequency (%)	Frequency (n)
Very likely	15%	31
Somewhat likely	34%	68
Can't say	12%	25
Unlikely	25%	49
Very unlikely	14%	27
Total	100%	200

Table 30: Likelihood of remaining loyal to the company

Chart 30: Likelihood of remaining loyal to the company

The above question was asked to identify whether customers would remain loyal to the company forever, thereby ensuring that Ozio is able to retain its customers. In response, 34% indicated that they were somewhat likely to remain loyal to the company and only 15% were very likely. The overall findings indicate that Ozio may find it difficult to retain its customers, as most of the participants do not show confidence in remaining with the company as a loyal customer for long.

Chi-Square tables:

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Gender			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
male	122	100.0	22.0
Female	78	100.0	-22.0
Total	200		

Age			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Age between 18-20	23	40.0	-17.0
Age between 20-25	49	40.0	9.0
Age between 26-35	73	40.0	33.0
Age between 36-45	29	40.0	-11.0
Age between 46-55	26	40.0	-14.0
Total	200		

Status			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Married	108	40.0	68.0
Single	43	40.0	3.0
Divorced	8	40.0	-32.0
Living with parents	24	40.0	-16.0
others	17	40.0	-23.0
Total	200		

Occupation			
	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
employed	92	33.3	58.7
Self-employed	48	33.3	14.7
Student	12	33.3	-21.3
house-wife	16	33.3	-17.3
unemployed	9	33.3	-24.3
others	23	33.3	-10.3
Total	200		

Test Statistics

	Gender	Age	Status	Occupation
Chi-Square	9.680 ^a	44.400 ^b	161.050 ^b	153.340 ^c
df	1	4	4	5
Asymp. Sig.	.002	.000	.000	.000

- . Chi-square=X²
- . df: Degrees of freedom= number of categories – 1
- . Asym significance= P value
- 1. Gender variable: X²(1) = 9.6, p<=.005
- 2. Age variable: X²(3) =44.4 (3), p<001
- 3. Status variable: X²(3) =161.05 (3), p<.001
- 4. Occupation variable: X²(3) =153.34 (3), p<001

1.Spearman's Status/ Occupation:

(Graph1)

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Status	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%
Occupation	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Status	.306	200	.000	.729	200	.000
Occupation	.282	200	.000	.753	200	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Nonparametric Correlations

Correlations

		Status	Occupation
Spearman's rho	Status	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	200
Occupation	Occupation	Correlation Coefficient	.874**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Analysis:

There was a significant positive correlation between Ozio's clients based on status and occupation.

As we can see in the (graph 1) once the client's occupation is changing to a higher level the status is changing to more settled situation.

N=Number of clients.

N (200) = .87, $p < .001$.

The correlation coefficient result (.87) is telling us that there is a very positive relationship between the occupation and status. The reason is, when the person is promoted in his/her business life, his/her personal life will be settled and knowing exactly where he/she wants to be in his/her personal life.

2.Spearman's Age/Status.

(graph2)

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Age	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%
Status	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Age	.201	200	.000	.908	200	.000
Status	.309	200	.000	.726	200	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Nonparametric Correlations

Correlations

		Age	Status
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	200
Status	Status	Correlation Coefficient	.785**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Analysis:

There was a significant positive correlation between Ozio's clients based on age and status. As we can see in the (graph 2) once the clients age is increasing and their status is almost confirmed, the value of purchasing is also increasing. We can see that there is a Monotonically increasing relationship.

N=Number of clients.

N (200) = .78, $p < .001$.

The correlation coefficient result (.78) is telling us that there is a very positive relationship between the age and status. The reason is, the person will be settled by time, which is the age, knowing his/her status. The person will organize his/her entire life based on their status.

3.Spearman's Age/ Occupation:

(Graph 3)

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Age	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%
Occupation	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Age	.201	200	.000	.908	200	.000
Occupation	.282	200	.000	.753	200	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Nonparametric Correlations

Correlations

			Age	Occupation
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.797**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	200	200
	Occupation	Correlation Coefficient	.797**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	200	200

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Analysis:

There was a significant positive correlation between Ozio's clients based on age and occupation.

As we can see in the (graph 3) once the clients age is increasing and their occupations is confirmed, the value of purchasing is also increasing. We can see that there is a Monotonically increasing relationship.

N=Number of clients.

$N(200) = .79, p < .001.$

The correlation coefficient result (.79) is telling us that there is a very positive relationship between the age and the occupation.

The reason is the person will be more confident of choosing from luxury brands based on his/her income. Usually having higher income is coming through experience, the individual gain experience through time, so by getting older.

4.2 Part B – Qualitative data analysis

This part of the chapter analyses the findings obtained from interviews with the managers of Ozio. The use of open-ended questions allowed the researcher to probe the participants and gain in-depth clarification regarding any doubts associated with the research questions. Open-ended questions also made it possible for the marketing managers to express their feelings, ideas and experiences, thereby provide a deeper insight into the problems being investigated. The following is the demographic profile of the marketing managers (Ozio) chosen for the interview.

4.2.1 Demographic profile of the managers taking part in interviews

Managers (M) [Marketing department]	Age	Gender	Marital status	Total Experience
M1	48	Male	Married	7 years
M2	44	Female	Married	5 years
M3	36	Male	Single	5 years

Q1) What are the CRM strategies implemented by the company as part of the marketing strategy? Does it help to control/ remove negative customer impressions about the company? Please elaborate.

M1 emphasised the nature of luxury business and commented,

“Luxury retailing in the current era demands for hands-on sales approach in terms of personalised communications, high-service interactions, and custom fittings.”

M1 explained that this required setting up a holistic CRM platform through which regular interactions between customers and marketing personnel could be made possible along with understanding the varied needs of the customers. The CRM framework maintained at the physical retail luxury store is based on the Analytical CRM approach which helps to capture customer data from different touchpoints, i.e. from each of the tools through which the customer interacts (such as telephone, website, emails) with the company. M1 further

explained that it helps to take appropriate marketing decisions based on the customer data by analysing the customer behaviour in terms of purchase frequency, type of luxury items purchased, payment history, use of bank cards, and other similar activities.

In response to the second part of the question, the manager explained that an analytical CRM approach as part of Ozio's relationship marketing strategy largely helps to create better understanding between the clients and marketers. as it facilitates rapport-building and creates personalisation. Rather than a formal relationship, a human-centric approach to client interaction makes it possible to eradicate the gaps between customers and marketers, avoid misunderstandings and offer concrete solution to customer problems. In this way, CRM helps to remove any instances of negative customer behaviour.

M2 stressed that the CRM framework of Ozio was more of a process and less of a technology or a tool to interact with clients. The viewpoints of M2 coincided with that of M1, as the former clarified that Ozio's CRM was an analytical process that worked very systematically. M2 remarked,

“Everything in marketing is based on analytics; we need to rely on numbers, data, and sales to run business.”

The manager emphasised the importance of using the CRM mechanism to drive sales-based customer relationships, such as repeat customer purchases, in order to sustain in the competitive business environment. The manager narrated some of the main benefits of the analytical CRM maintained by the company, expressing his views as,

“CRM at Ozio helps to cross-sell or up-sell products as a priority function, including optimisation of sales coverage, financial forecasting, contact optimisation, and growth in customer satisfaction scores.”

Therefore, CRM at Ozio is meant to carry out a range of activities and functions with the main intention to foster sales and increase customer satisfaction. In response to the second part of the question, the manager discarded the possibility of the occurrence of any negative feelings in the customers' minds, although stressed the effectiveness of Ozio's CRM that helped to shape positive customer perceptions about the luxury brand – Ozio. The manager disclosed that its CRM system facilitates customer engagement which helps to eliminate any negative influence that surrounds customers and assures them about the presence of a dedicated CRM team to take care of them.

M3 clarified that Ozio is a customer-centric company and the marketing strategies are largely based on the 'relationship marketing model'. **M2 commented,**

“Our marketing strategies are built around the relational aspects of marketing and less inclined towards the transactional perspective.”

The manager further explained that Ozio maintains a robust CRM framework based on optimal co-ordination between information technologies, social assets (employees) which are aligned with the business processes. The views of this manager also corroborated with that of M1 as regards to considering CRM as an important touchpoint between the company and its customers, which helps to gain a 360-degree view of the end users of the products and services. As a strategic marketing process, CRM is meant to gain access to comprehensive customer data from the different customer touchpoints and accordingly, design the marketing mix strategies that could meet the requirements of individual customer segments and groups. While responding to the second part of the question, M3 emphasised the dissemination of negative reviews about the Ozio luxury brand on social media posted by many consumers that creates a negative impression about the brand. Ozio's presence in social media helps its CRM personnel to connect with audiences and thereby monitor those negative reviews and map the situation.

Q2) Does CRM as a business strategy in Ozio help in customer satisfaction? Please elaborate.

M1 remarked,

“Yes, definitely, by all means. CRM is the only platform that allows closer interaction with the customers, personalise the conversation, build rapport, and encourage emotional based relationship.”

The manager elaborated that any customer enquiries are resolved by the CRM representatives of the company, who are the first point of contact for the customers. The use of a CRM tool at Ozio helps to maintain a systematic process of responding to the customers in a prompt manner without any delay. The manager emphasised the effectiveness of CRM to resolve customers' complaints which are often too complex to be resolved by a salesperson at the Ozio store. M1 revealed that CRM leads to better customer experience, as well-trained, friendly CRM

personnel who interact with the customers and show them that they are being cared for. CRM helps to personalise the relationship and pay attention to minute details of the customers, such as the kind of craftsmanship, size and fittings or fabric that customers look for. CRM leads to better customer experience and builds superior relationships, which is an essential ingredient of customer satisfaction in luxury fashion.

The manager **M2** added,

“Our CRM offers a systematic process of complaints log where customers can escalate their complaints to the customer care personnel, and then to the senior levels, if it is not resolved.”

Customers can log on to the complaints management system (CMS) on the website and post their complaints straightaway to the customer relationship officer if he/she was not satisfied with the resolution provided by the customer care personnel. M2 explained that the complaints of almost every customer are resolved to the customer’s full satisfaction and those involved with resolving customer complaints aim to achieve ‘customer delight’. Each time a complaint is closed from the customer’s end, a customer satisfaction survey is conducted through the CRM tool and the customer satisfaction scores (CSat scores) are usually high. The manager commented, “We never had detractors so far”.

M3 pointed out that customer complaints are very frequent in the hospitality sector and remarked,

“Ah! A very satisfied guest today can start yelling tomorrow for a minor service gap and things may go out of control if the issue is not handled tactfully.”

Well-trained CRM personnel take the escalations, log the complaint and initiate a complaint management process. From a different angle, CRM also helps to gain access to useful customer data from the different touchpoints, based on which the customer groups are segmented according to their demographic or behavioural profile and marketing strategies tailored to serve the respective groups. Customers receiving customised services according to their expectations are more likely to be satisfied. Ozio’s CRM assures customers that their voice is being listened to and operates on the principle of ‘We Are Listening’ to show concern about customers’ views and grievances which is a satisfying experience for them. The manager disclosed that customers of luxury products and services are not price sensitive, but they are sensitive about what they wear and desire clothing that adds magnificence to their personality. Therefore, they

seek to discuss their expectations, desires and unique requirements with a dedicated, specialised team of professionals, and this role is played by Ozio's CRM team. This is a satisfying experience for customers, made possible by Ozio's trained CRM team.

Q3) What kind of marketing mix strategy is adopted by the company to foster customer satisfaction?

M1 considered 'product' and 'price' and the association between the two as the main ingredient in the 4Ps of marketing, and mainly emphasised the importance of pricing for the luxury range offered by Ozio. The manager commented,

"I have experienced customers consciously or sub-consciously develop a psychological luxury stature of the price range maintained by Ozio, as a luxury brand ...hence we strive to charge the right price from the customers ...offering lower price than their expectations and the customers' eagerness to pay is likely to harm the brand value...and the other way round may not give enough justification to customers to make a purchase."

Elaborating on the views, M1 further clarified that lower price or competitive pricing for luxury items was not the key to customer satisfaction, but rather setting the 'right' price for the right product was more important to keep customers satisfied. Next, M1 focused on product attributes indicating that there are key attributes of luxury –

"... quality, scarcity, heritage, non-utility/superfluous, and integrity ... at Ozio we make sure the product range irrespective of its price met their attributes to ensure that the customers derive value for money and subsequently satisfied with every purchase they made."

M2 pointed out specific mixes in the marketing of luxury brands such as Ozio, for instance **persona, placement, performance, and paucity**, apart from the usual marketing mix elements available in the academic literature. As regards to 'persona', the manager commented,

"... persona of Ozio is the result of its unique projection, and consistency across the different customer-touch points and marketing communication through the ads."

As regards to placement, M2 related it to store location, presentation of the salesmen/customer service personnel, and the in-store ambience and experience of the customer that heightened their brand experience as well. Elaborating the views on **performance** as a mix, M2 explained it to be the delivery of a distinctive experience of Ozio as a luxury brand,

“Our performance is at two levels, at the product level and at an experiential level.....in the former case (product level), we ensure that the product range is capable of satisfying the functional characteristics as well as the delivering on its physical attributes.....design excellence, precision, craftsmanship, unique design, excellent quality, best fabric, and innovation were the core of product performance.”

M2 explained that at the **experiential level**, it is necessary that the emotional value of Ozio as a brand is much ahead of what the product represents. As regards to **paucity**, M2 pointed out that over-revelation and mass distribution of the luxury range usually dissolves the luxury character of a reputed brand and hence they have to maintain the customers’ perception that it is scarce.

“We have some limited-edition products which are customised through the innovative capabilities, priced at very premium rates, largely personalised for niche customers seeking elegance and make available during special occasions only.”

With reference to pricing, the viewpoints of M2 coincided with M2, wherein the latter believed in fixing the ‘right’ price for the ‘right’ product range, rather than maintaining a very competitive price or a premium price for the luxury range.

M3 remarked,

“Customer services are at the heart of our marketing mix and I personally believe efficient services are the most important ingredient of customer satisfaction.”

The manager explained that the marketing mix comprise of a set of elements and that Ozio still mainly concentrates on the extended mix, yet not leaving aside product and place to which much importance is given. It is important to maintain product differentiation while distribution should be limited, as limited-edition premium items are meant for people with a sophisticated taste in luxury fashion. M3 stressed the elements of ‘process’ and ‘people’ in the marketing mix, the importance of maintaining a well-trained workforce to run the process of daily

business operations and customer services. The main focus is to maintain exceptional quality of services at all levels and processes which was possible only if well-trained staff were there. M3 added,

“We ensure that customer services were prompt and responsive on which the customers can rely upon.... the customer services staff are well trained on soft skills, customer service skills, and knowledgeable about handling different types of customers.”

The manager elaborated that customers of luxury fashion brand like Ozio look for extraordinary quality, fabric and unmatched design that they may not have come across before. In addition, customers expect flawless services and marketing personnel who can live up to their expectations, and hence a customised marketing mix that satisfies the aforementioned customer expectations are important.

Q4) Does CRM as a business strategy help to retain customers? Please elaborate.

M1 commented,

“The best way is to keep the customers happy and this is possible by offering them the best quality services and CRM makes this possible.”

The manager further explained,

“The comprehensive information gained from CRM helped to pay close attention to customers’ problems and any signs of an impending customer departure, and knowledge about this is gained by identifying variables such as the purchase frequency, service calls, type of complaints made, etc.”

CRM helps staff to see such signals of customers intending to switch over to a different service provider and then take immediate action to convince customers to stay before they leave. The manager also commented that,

“We follow a practice of running the sales report for the last six months and such data is obtained from CRM...any customer, or customer groups who had not made any purchase for a long period are most likely to leave the organisation and hence the marketing personnel follow up with them.”

The views of M2 corroborated with that of M1, who emphasised the importance of implementing target marketing with the help of a CRM tool. M2 remarked,

“CRM at Ozio provides us with key insights into the purchase history of customers and accordingly we target our offers and make them most relevant and appealing to the customers.... this increases customer satisfaction and make it easier to retain the satisfied customers.”

M2 added that there were several other ways in which CRM can be helpful in retaining customers. The manager disclosed that the most profitable customers (making higher purchases from the company) were incentivised to enhance retention. CRM at Ozio is as good as a customer database which helps to track those customers who yield the most revenue by making frequent purchases or purchasing in bulk. Using this information helps the company to design lucrative perks or incentives to the most profitable and loyal customers and then retain them. The manager pointed out that this helps to budget both time and resources and also to retain customers that are the biggest potential for return.

The views of M3 were more or less similar to those of M1 and M2, however the manager emphasised viewing CRM as a personalised platform to engage customers and therefore increase the chances of retention. M3 stated,

“CRM is instrumental in creating personalised offers for the customers, engage them, and boost customer retention.”

Unlike the views of M2, M3 did not believe in incentivising only the most profitable customers and emphasised engaging every customer using the CRM process. M3 added,

“...make personalised offers for almost every loyal customer on the basis of CRM intelligence.!”

Elaborating on this, the manager considered it necessary to offer personalised offers, listen to customers, create engagement and thereby increase the chances of retention.

**Q5) How is service quality related to marketing strategies and practices at Ozio?
How does it relate to customer satisfaction and retention?**

M1 replied,

“Ah! Yes, service quality has to be embedded in the marketing principles and policies of an organisation to sustain the competitive pressures.”

The manager explained that buyers of luxury products are very particular and conscious about the quality of the services combined with every purchase they make. Most of Ozio’s customers are the rich and affluent, usually time-bound and do not mind paying more for prompt delivery of their orders. Hence, the manager stressed on the ‘responsiveness’ element, indicating that the customers hate being kept waiting, even if it was for mere 5-10 minutes. For both online and offline purchases, customers expect prompt delivery of the merchandise, prompt billing, and they also have similar expectations for merchandise return or after-sales services. Therefore, the marketing strategies, especially from the ‘services marketing’ perspective, are supposed to be prompt without causing any delay. Prompt services, on-time delivery and assurance that the same level of service would be provided every time the customer visits the store are all essential to maintaining utmost customer satisfaction. M1 remarked,

“Better services quality ensures high customer satisfaction, which no doubt creates high switch over cost for the customers to change their preference for brands, and consequently helped to retain customers.”

M2 asked the question,

“...marketing strategies... now look, marketing is a broad concept, are you talking about the service dominant logic of marketing?” Of course, service quality is an essential part of the services marketing at Ozio and dominantly includes it in the service delivery to ensure better customer experience, co-creation of value, and thereby maintain an unmatched value proposition.”

Elaborating on this view, the manager disclosed that,

“Ozio’s marketing services is built on the basis of customer centricity and this necessitates that the staff is equipped with the right skills, right knowledge, right behaviour and temperament to serve the clients to their best satisfaction.”

The viewpoints of M2 coincided with that of M1 in terms of being responsive to the customers’ needs. However, the manager emphasised more the efforts undertaken by the service provider (sales personnel, customer services, CRM representatives) who were trained effectively in terms of being knowledgeable, courteous and tactful in delivering services and keeping customers satisfied. M2 further added that,

“Each and every customer are important irrespective of what they purchase, how they purchase, and the quantity they purchase and it was our primary duty to see everyone received the same level of services – i.e. differentiated to create customer delight’, and these customers would always return to the store as a satisfied customer.”

M2 summed up the conversation and remarked that it was easy to retain satisfied customers, particularly those who were satisfied with the level of services being offered.

M3 linked service quality with the extended marketing mix of physical evidence, process and people and remarked,

“Who would like to visit a messy store? Who would like to purchase if the buying process or making payments is unsystematic? And who would like to talk to rude salesperson? (laughs) that’s why service quality forms an intrinsic part of the service mix.”

The manager directed his attention towards the tangible view of Ozio stores and mentioned the excellent decoration, cleanliness, ambience and the way customer-facing staff maintain a tidy dress code and pleasant appearance. M3 also focused on the way Ozio’s employees interact and deal with the customers at the different customer touchpoints, starting from the initial contact until the final transaction is complete, and thereafter each time the customer visits the store.

Q6) Are satisfied customers more likely to remain loyal to the company? What marketing efforts are directed towards customer retention? Please elaborate.

M1 affirmed,

“Definitely, Yes! No doubt, one of the major implications of customer satisfaction is customer loyalty ... and the signs of loyal customers are repeat purchase, low intention to switch over to competitor brands, and suggesting others to choose the brand to which they are loyal.”

The manager elaborated that these were the key factors that make their marketing efforts successful. Loyal customers are less price sensitive and do not mind paying extra if the prices for the products or service are increased to some extent. M1 further explained,

“It’s the age of relationship marketing and CRM tools are the most dominant tools for customer retention...,the use of which helps to understand customers, identify their changing needs and behaviour, track their purchasing patterns and accordingly design the marketing activities that is customised for specific target segments.”

Elaborating on this, the manager explained that the CRM representatives of Ozio were well-trained to deliver excellent customer services while maintaining trust-based, long-term relationships with customers so that they do not go elsewhere.

M2 remarked,

“Higher the customer satisfaction, higher is the chance that they would make another purchase from the same store in future ... and satisfied customers become advocates to the brand recommending the company to family and friends and others... obviously we can’t expect loyalty from dissatisfied customers!”

The manager further stated that,

“...the key to customer loyalty was relationship marketing and the tool was customer relationship management.”

The views of M2 corroborated with M1; however, the former added a few more dimensions to the current marketing efforts that assist customer retention. In this respect M2 remarked,

“Marketing should involve ethics right from the marketing planning stage, to the development of products, packaging, and customer segmentation, brand positioning and creation of the marketing mix elements ...the product quality, price, and distribution, process of product and service delivery should all incorporate a fair and transparent play.”

The manager believed that Ozio’s customers were the affluent, rich and well-educated masses who know” what *includes a foul play*”, implying that customers would cease buying from the company if they discovered any unethical practices in marketing. Therefore, M2 laid emphasis on **ethical marketing** to retain its customers in addition to the usual CRM approach.

M3 commented,

“The tendency of satisfied customers to remain loyal to the organisation is always higher than the dis-satisfied ones ...and that’s since ages in the marketing world.”

The manager pointed out that customer satisfaction was the key to customer loyalty and retention.

As regards to the marketing strategies that help to retain customers, the perspectives of M3 differed from that of M1 and M2, as he concentrated on marketing innovation. The manager asserted that the usual marketing activities- sales promos, the communication mixes and the marketing mix - were quite common for all business organisations trying to keep their customers satisfied. However, going beyond customer satisfaction is the need to achieve customer delight, which is possible through service innovation, which goes further than service quality. M3 remarked,

“The concept of customer satisfactions seems to fade away in the current economy and given way to customer delight ... and the level of satisfaction I (Ozio) am giving can be matched easily by the nearest competitor.”

The manager elaborated that modern customers, in their quest for innovative products and services, could switch suppliers at any time. M3 also explained that,

“Meeting customer expectations was not enough in the current marketing age, but it was essential to exceed their expectations to achieve their long-term custom, loyalty and retention”

With regards to the use of CRM for customer retention, M3 was of the same viewpoint as M1 and M3, but gave importance to innovative capabilities of CRM, such as integrating the tool with social media or smartphones to better understand customer needs, provide customised solution in real time and create personalised relationships and thereby a higher retention rate.

Q7) As a fashion (luxury), does sensory marketing result in better customer satisfaction? Does the company follow it? Does it also help in customer retention? Please elaborate.

M1 commented,

“Hmmm, that’s interesting...sensorial marketing is definitely a part of our (Ozio) marketing strategy, however, we yet to leverage the full benefits of such innovative marketing practices...and create a positive appeal.”

The manager explained that customers visiting the Ozio store did not only expect superior products or services but also wanted enjoyment and happiness and stated,

“Buyers of luxury are the ones seeking much pleasure and emotional satisfaction out of their shopping experiences.”

The manager elaborated that the sensory experience at the store helps customers to relax, de-stress and calm down, and influences their decision-making in a positive manner. Luxury brands have customers that are usually rich, affluent and time-bound and therefore a serene atmosphere with good music, aroma, nice interior and similar factors have a positive influence on their waiting time. In addition, the sense of touch strengthens brand identity, the sense of sound attaches meaning to a luxury brand, while taste incorporates a range of experiences that a customer has with the brand, such as how it looks, sounds, smells and feels; all these factors are inherently satisfying.

M2 pointed out that sensory marketing is the one of the main sources of competitive advantage that a fashion retailer having a physical retail presence can build upon. M2 remarked,

“We use the different neurotic stimulations of vision, touch, sound and smell to provide customers a unique experience that they do not get during the online purchase...”

(pause)... it helps to incite powerful and provocative emotions that is persuasive and convincing and satisfying at the same time.”

The manager elaborated that Ozio’s sensory marketing comprises of ambient elements that have a positive influence on customers ‘senses and make their cognitive, behavioural and emotional responses favour brand awareness and the creation of positive brand image in their minds. M2 also stressed the importance of touch not only for the merchandise that the customers purchase, but also the shelves, packaging and the handshake that was meant to give customers a pleasing experience so that they feel comfortable. M2 stated,

“For every luxury item that we sell at Ozio, the customers prefer to touch the product, have a close look at the item, go for a trial, and so on therefore, it is necessary to create a vibrant environment which has positively appeal to their senses...otherwise even the best of our products may look dull.”

In regard to the second part of the question, M2 stated that the sense of touch and physical examination of the merchandise this way ensures that they are satisfied with the purchase they made, i.e. it delivers value for money. However, how far sensory marketing helps to retain customers was an area that the marketing department had not concentrated much upon.

M3 stated that the Ozio store stands out from its surrounding environment and grabs customers’ attention, due to the visual stimulation, emotional appeal and the personal touch that is extended. The views of M3 were similar to M2 as regards to the importance of touching and feeling the items to remain satisfied with their purchase. However, M3 remarked,

“My personal opinion and experience are that customers of luxury products are strongly attached to MUSIC’.....and playing the right music according to the type of customers that matches their age, lifestyle, and taste is more effective, although it’s very challenging...without any doubt.”

The type of music, the tempo and the genre combined with a beautiful aroma largely determines the length of time a customer would willingly spend and the speed at which a customer navigates around the products. M3 elaborated,

“At the Ozio store, we prefer sober yet peppy music, dim lighting and comfortable seating arrangements if the customer wants to rest.”

On being probed about the second part of the question, M3 affirmed that specific aspects of sensory marketing that appealed to the customers leads to an increase in their satisfaction, as their experience with the brand is good. For instance, an elderly customer being offered a comfortable chair to sit, or a younger one who found his favourite numbers (music) played at the store, etc. are more likely to feel more satisfied and eager to revisit the store. This is how sensory marketing helps to satisfy and retain customers.

Q8) What kind of marketing tactics actually result in negative customer impression and dissatisfaction? How do you overcome them? Please elaborate.

M1 commented,

“Oh, that’s so straightforward (laughs) while marketing efforts are directed towards positive customer experience and satisfaction, often customers develop negative impression about our brand and products.”

M1 stressed that marketing communications including online advertisements such as sudden pop ups, display ads, and sometimes banner ads are considered by customers to be intrusive and they resist them. However, the intention of such communicative ads is to make customers aware of the fresh offerings or arrivals at the store rather than to intrude into their privacy. The manager disclosed that there have been a large number of customer complaints in the past regarding unwanted advertising content, literature or promotional messages posted to customers via the communication platforms that the customers used, such as social media. However, such online ads are very common on the website but do not work well for Ozio in terms of gaining customer advocacy or satisfaction.

The perceptions of M2 were quite similar to that of M1; however, M2 emphasised the sales promotions that were often ‘*too pushy*’ and meant to convince customers to make a purchase. However, these were part of the marketing strategies wherein the salesmen were assigned with soft targets to acquire new customers and sell or cross-sell different products to existing customers. The manager said,

“Often the marketing personnel try to persuade customers to make a purchase of a newly launched item that needs to be sold through aggressive sales promotion;

however, we ensure that our marketing campaigns are manned by ethics and strict protocols.”

The manager pointed out that there is a very thin line of demarcation between sales and managing customer relationships and disclosed that customer relationships were maintained to ensure that the customers did not switch to competitors and to encourage them to make purchases from the Ozio brand. Nevertheless, the manager admitted that sometimes sales promotions are considered too pushy by customers, even the most loyal ones, and this creates a negative impression of the brand.

M3 said,

“Tailoring or customising the marketing strategies according to the explicit needs of customers or customer groups was very challenging ... (deep breath) ...especially when customer demands, orientation, and attitudes are continuously changing.”

From a different perspective, the manager also emphasised the misuse of social media by customers. The manager shared his experience that some customers have a tendency to share any negative experiences with the company on social media, often exaggerated, and circulate it extensively, despite a satisfactory resolution given to the customer. M3, while sharing his experiences, lamented,

“Social media marketing is to remain connected with the customers, ‘listen to them’ and allow them to be loud, but they are louder than what is expected (laughs)...often with the liberty to write anything and circulate it among masses with just a few mouse clicks.”

The manager pointed out that even the most loyal customers spread unfavourable word-of-mouth reviews on social channels regarding any negative issues they had with the company while the good experiences are subdued. Hence, the spread of negative word-of-mouth content, often exaggerated, sometimes fake and threatening is posted by customers anonymously and the spread of such content is not traceable as the manager remarked, *“Social media communication is not traceable. neither easy to monitor”*. Therefore, M3 explained that the spread of negative word-of-mouth content, posts and reviews create a negative impact on other customers who view them, and it is next to impossible to control such occurrences.

4.4 Summary

The customers of Ozio who participated in the survey comprised both male and female gender, were aged mainly between 20 and 35 years, were employed (occupation), and the majority have been purchasing from Ozio for around 3 to 7 years. The main intention of the survey was to investigate the customers' perceptions about the relationship marketing approach of Ozio and how effectively the CRM system supports the current marketing framework of the company. It was found that Ozio has a dedicated CRM system which is used to acquire customers, inform customers about fresh arrivals/offerings from the company and is also used as a marketing tool to achieve sales. It was found that the CRM personnel often make unsolicited calls to customers to inform them about new product launches and to convince them to make purchases. Therefore, the transactional perspective of the CRM tool is evident. The managerial interviews also disclosed that the CRM personnel are often directed to call customers to sell them newly introduced products as a part of the marketing strategy.

At the same time, customers also revealed that CRM representatives undertake initiatives such as 'customer satisfaction surveys' (C-sat survey) to identify the level of customer satisfaction. However, very few affirmed that the CRM system is well-tailored to meet the specific needs of customer groups, nor that the marketers show a keen interest in building relationships with customers based on trust and mutual understanding. On the positive side, customers in the survey affirmed that complaints logged through the CRM/complaints management system are addressed in a timely manner, i.e. maintaining responsiveness. At the same time, the customer-facing CRM representatives are knowledgeable, well trained and provide reliable services when needed.

The marketing mix approach of Ozio was criticised by the customers, particularly with regards to the promotional mix. Digital ads such as sudden pop-ups, banner ads, unclose-able browsers, etc. that are meant to spread awareness are actually considered as intrusive, disturbing and ultimately cause customer dissatisfaction. However, the use of a multichannel communication approach maintained by Ozio allows easy communication with customers, which is satisfying. Sensory marketing strategies followed by Ozio are also appreciated by the customers, as they get opportunities to touch, feel and try the products before the actual purchase. The in-store decoration, aroma, interior design, music and ambience are appealing in a way that creates increased customer satisfaction. The product quality, range and availability meet customer expectations and provide a satisfactory experience. The customers also affirmed it is necessary

for a company such as Ozio to keep customers satisfied in order to retain their custom in the long-term.

Chapter 5

Discussions

5.1 Findings from quantitative research

As regards to demographic profile of the customers taking part in the survey, the majority (61%) was males and most participants were aged between 26-35 (37%) and 20-25 (24%). The Majority (54%) of the participants were married, while most (46%) were 'employed,' as regards occupational status. The findings indicate that Ozio's customers base is comprised of young customers, as well as those in their mid-30's, and has been purchasing from the brand for more than 5 years.

The findings indicate that Ozio maintains a dedicated customer relationship management (CRM) system as part of its marketing strategy to strengthen its relationship with customers. Used as a dedicated tool for relationship marketing, Ozio also uses its CRM mechanism to acquire potential customers, capture data, and use that data to design and/or customise its marketing strategies according to customer requirements.

In addition to the core use of its CRM, Ozio uses it for a range of activities, i.e., interacting with customers and updating them about the fresh product arrivals of the Ozio brand and associated promotions and discounts. CRM is used as a helpdesk and point of contact where customers can connect with Ozio's marketers, post their queries or doubts and seek clarification and ask for their complaints to be logged and resolved. The findings coincide with the theoretical debate conducted by Reimer and Brecker (2015), who consider CRM as a strategic marketing tool to foster customer interaction, facilitate increased business transactions and add value to the services provided to customers.

While CRM is used for beneficial purposes such as keeping customers informed about fresh arrivals, clarifying doubts and resolving complaints and building long-term relationships, the downside of Ozio's CRM was also evident from the customer surveys. CRM is often used as a sales-centric marketing tool the use of which is used by Ozio's marketing personnel to make frequent and unsolicited calls to customers to push them to make purchases. Such use of CRM is from a transactional perspective rather than relational perspective, and hence the use of customer information is used by marketers to increase sales. The use of CRM as a transactional

marketing tool is considered intervening by the customers, as 'sales calls' are deemed to be pushy and disturbing. This finding corroborates with the arguments made by Frow and Payne (2009), who criticise the use of CRM as an information database meant for sales promotions, as opposed to one for nurturing customer relationships.

The marketing team at Ozio uses its CRM functions to conduct customer satisfaction surveys and to understand the level of customer satisfaction. This helps Ozio to understand the issues faced by customers, identify areas of dissatisfaction and pinpoint areas that require improvement. Academic researchers such as Rahimi and Koza (2017) consider the use of CRM crucial for identifying the level of customer satisfaction, which is undertaken by CRM representatives at Ozio.

As regards to the **CRM capabilities of Ozio**, findings from the survey indicate that the customer relationship management personnel are knowledgeable and well-trained to deal with customer issues in a reliable manner. Well-trained CRM representatives are likely to be in a better position to understand customer problems and provide a correct resolution in the very first interaction. A multichannel communication approach to CRM ensures that the company uses different communication channels such as emails, mobiles and the website to make it easier for customers to connect with the CRM representatives. In addition, social media is also used as a communication channel; however, the use of Social CRM (Lehmkuhland Jung, 2013) is at a preliminary level.

The **weakness of Ozio's CRM** was identified from the findings obtained from customer survey in the form of a 'one size fits all' approach to customer relationship management, rather than a customised approach. This implies that CRM is not customised according to the profile, needs and desires of various customer groups, and therefore it may not cater to the needs of all customers. Ozio's CRM approach in this sense does not align with the ideas of Harrigan et al. (2011) and Long et al. (2013), who consider it necessary to customise CRM in accordance to the needs of different customer groups or segments in a holistic manner. Another weakness of Ozio's CRM approach is its lack of capability to support superior after-sales services, which are considered vital by researchers such as Yu et al. (2015) in the relationship marketing approach. Overall, the findings from customer survey indicate that Ozio's CRM has not been able to meet customer expectations, even though majority are satisfied with the level of service quality maintained at the store.

Being a luxury fashion brand, Ozio has capitalised on sensory marketing techniques and allows its customers to touch, feel and examine the product quality before making a purchase, thereby arousing their inherent feelings and creating an emotional appeal (Consoli, 2010). The internal store ambience is backed with good lighting, decoration, music, aroma and visual information and this helps to position the brand effectively in the customer's mind (Shabgou and Daryani, 2014). Good store ambience also lowers customers' level of stress, controls instincts of anger and encourages positive consumer behaviour. While the existing literature does not focus much on the effect of store ambience and sensory marketing in terms of consumer satisfaction, the findings from the survey clearly indicate a direct relationship between sensory marketing and customer satisfaction.

. Based on the chi-square test:

We sampled 200 clients and evaluated whether the number of clients who are male ($f=1$) was equal to the number of female ($f=2$). The data was analysed using chi-square test. The null hypothesis was rejected " $X^2(1) = 9.6, p < .005$ ". The P value is less than .005

In the 4 variables Age/Gender/status and occupation the P value is less .05.

. The Spearman's correlation:

We do have 3 results. All of them are positive relationship between each other. These results explain to us that Ozio is on the right path, the good vision made by the owner and every senior manager, we don't have to forget the retail team who is on the shop floor facing the clients and delivering the best customer service level.

Based on the results as we can see in (graph 1), we can say that the relationship between the status of the client and his/her occupation give us the idea that our clients are the wealthy people in each society we have an Ozio store. That's mean we are targeting the same kind of people not only in different cities but in different countries which make Ozio a global luxury brand.

Based on the results as we can see in (graph 2), we can say that the relation between the age and the status is a positive relationship, that's help Ozio to know which kind of individuals to target and which age. This result will help Ozio to target the clients who are in their 40's for both gender and who are married. That what Ozio will be targeting in future, with trying to create a new line for other ages and status like the urbans.

Based on the results as we can see in (graph 3), we can say the relation between the age and the occupation is a positive relationship, that result will give Ozio a mission which is targeting the people who works in the public sector like Actors, Businessmen, Politicians who need to be always in a perfect image.

5.2 Findings from qualitative research

As regards to the **nature and type of CRM**, the findings indicate that Ozio maintains a **holistic** approach to CRM and considers that luxury retailing requires personalised communication and high-service interactions. Ozio's approach to CRM is also **analytical** and considers the importance of capturing useful customer information across various **touch points**. CRM supports a relationship marketing strategy that is meant to personalise customer relationships and create better understanding. Ozio's CRM is also **process oriented** and its CRM capabilities are directed towards building strong customer relationships in addition to customer interactions. The use of CRM is also undertaken to drive sales, as well as cross-sell products based on customer relationships, and to conduct surveys to obtain customer satisfaction scores. CRM at Ozio helps its marketing personnel to address customers' issues and complaints and provide resolution in real time. Based on data obtained from different customer touchpoints, marketing strategies are designed in a customised manner to align with customer requirements. CRM is backed by multiple communication channels to foster customer interactions, including social media; however, the integration of both of these (Social CRM) is in a preliminary stage.

According to researchers such as Wittwer et al., 2017; Wang and Kim, 2017; Girchenko et al., (2017), Social-CRM provides considerable benefits to luxury fashion retailers by allowing to connect and interact with customers who seek differentiated service and personalised attention. The integration of socially accepted collaborative technology in Social-CRM helps to deliver superior value to customers by understanding luxury customers who are time-constrained. Social media marketers acting as CRM personnel on Social-CRM can monitor customers' activities on social media understand their behaviour, areas of satisfaction or dissatisfaction, and any signals that reveal their switchover intention. Based on such data, Social-CRM professionals can customise the marketing making it more customer-centric and strengthen their CRM capability.

Meanwhile, the approach to CRM followed by Ozio aligns with the theoretical claims made by Saarijärvi et al. (2013), who consider its importance in terms of capturing data from different touchpoints to understand customer requirements, and accordingly design marketing capabilities, marketing operations and sales. The holistic approach to CRM corroborates with the arguments made by Reimer and Becker (2015), who consider CRM as an effective tool to acquire useful information from customers and tailor marketing strategies accordingly to create superior value. However, this requires a cross-functional integration of people, process,

business operations and marketing capabilities, backed by the coordination of technology and information. The process-driven strategy of CRM is supported by researchers such as Kocoglu and Kirmaci (2012), who suggest the use of several communication channels to ease customer interactions, and to achieve customer loyalty and retention.

In luxury fashion brand, apart from CRM, the marketing mix elements, namely, product and price and the association between these mixes was considered significant in terms of strengthening customer satisfaction and minimising their switch-over intention. Findings from the managerial interviews indicate that luxury consumers consciously or sub-consciously form a psychosomatic luxury stature of price that is differentiated and therefore it becomes imperative to charge the right price for the luxury range. Luxury customers do not mind paying a higher price for premium products and therefore maintaining the right price for the right product is inevitable. Alternatively, charging lower price that does not align with the customers' expectations tends to destroy the brand value. Therefore, luxury products need to be differentiated, classy, rare and maintain a premium price appeals to the customers. For that reason, in case of luxury fashion, charging lower price does not appeal to customer, neither helps to satisfy or retain them; rather, quoting the right price for the right product contributes to customer satisfaction.

As regards to product attributes, it is necessary to maintain scarcity, heritage and integrity for which premium price needs is charged to ensure customers get value for money. Findings also indicate that specific mixes, going ahead of the usual marketing mix dimensions, are P-persona, P-performance, P-placement, and P-paucity. This was a new piece of finding obtained from the empirical investigation, wherein 'persona' is the outcome of a luxury product's distinct projection, and reliability across various customer touchpoints and marketing communication through the luxury advertisements. The element 'placement' is similar to place or distribution in the usual marketing-mix, and refers to store location, including presentation of the store personnel, in-store ambience and thereby customer experience that intensify their brand experience. Performance in case of luxury marketing mix is the delivery of a unique experience that customers should be provided with.

The dimension performance in case of Ozio is delivered at two levels, at the experiential level (i.e. product level) keeping in mind that the product satisfies the functional attributes – craftsmanship, fabric quality, precision, design excellence, and innovativeness. At the experiential level, Ozio ensures that the emotional value of Ozio is much ahead is much ahead

of what the product replicates. Meanwhile, the element 'paucity' in case of luxury fashion ensures that mass distribution and over-revelation of the products is restricted, or else over-revelation dilutes the luxury character and disposition of reputed luxury fashion brands. In particular, for Ozio, the marketing managers maintain limited-edition range, which is innovative, customised, and classy and creates a unique value proposition. The sale of such products is not endorsed through sales promotions, but the elegance, uniqueness, and limited-edition features made available during special occasions pulls customers to the luxury store.

Findings also reveal that luxury fashion brand such as Ozio adequately focus on the extended marketing mix, especially people and process. Differentiation is maintained not only through products but also the process of service delivery and customer services. The 'people' element is to maintain well trained, knowledgeable, and dedicated customer service or CRM personnel enthusiastic enough to provide superior service delivery through a sophisticated process and ensure high customer satisfaction. This required that the staff members were trained on soft-skills, customer service skills, operational skills for CRM and the ability to deal with and satisfy the varying needs of different types of customers.

Triangulating the above findings with the theoretical debates undertaken in the literature review, it is revealed that marketing-mix is used as a framework by companies/brands to take marketing decisions, configure each marketing mix element to meet the divergent needs of customers (O'Cas and Heirati, 2015). As identified in the findings, it is imperative for marketers to maintain the right price for the right set of products and make it available at the right place and time as validated by researchers such as Wongleedee, 2015; Festa et al., 2016. This is imperative for luxury fashion brand marketers to maintain exceptional value proposition for luxury customers wherein 'right' is the customers' response to products and services that are appealing (Schultz and Dev, 2012).

While findings obtained from the interview indicated that P-persona, P-performance, P-placement, and P-paucity are imperative for luxury fashion brands, review of extant literature emphasise on the importance of extended marketing mix, i.e., process, people and physical evidence. The 'people' factor emphasises not only on knowledgeable, well-trained employees but also customers (Festa et al., 2016); process entails strengthening the operational systems to ensure on-time availability of products, including the entire value chain process, operations process and smooth transactions. Meanwhile, physical evidence in case of luxury fashion brands entails the tangible features, store design, store facilities, layout and ambience, ease of

movement, tidiness that create a favourable appeal for luxury customers. For luxury brands with online presence, as studied in extant literature, it is essential to maintain an attractive website with superior design, easy navigability, user-friendly, and informative website with secure payment gateway. The importance of physical evidence in case of online business is emphasised upon by researchers such as Azeem and Sharma, 2015; Abril and Rodriguez-Cánovas, 2016. However, managerial responses obtained from the interview do not focus on maintaining superior physical evidence for the online luxury brands.

The link between **CRM and customer satisfaction**, according to the findings, indicate a direct, positive relationship. CRM leads to a better customer experience allowing a prompt response to customers' queries or concerns and giving them personalised attention. It uses a customer complaint management system to provide customised solutions to customer problems, takes escalations for complex problems and resolves their issues to their satisfaction. Using the CRM tool, customer satisfaction (CSat) surveys are conducted by the marketing team to measure the extent of customer satisfaction and to strive for higher CSat scores. The 'We Are Listening' philosophy of Ozio's CRM provides a satisfying experience to the customer, as their voice is listened to informally and in a friendly way, building an emotional-based affiliation which is inherently satisfying.

Relating the findings with the theoretical debates carried out in the literature review, especially with regards to the impact of CRM on customer satisfaction, academic researchers such as Long et al. (2013) assert that CRM applications contribute to customer satisfaction in three different ways. Firstly, by providing rich customer information obtained from various customer touchpoints, CRM helps luxury brands to customise their products and services according to distinct customer needs. This information also helps luxury marketers to understand the latent customer needs. Customised product and service offerings and innovative practices that meet distinct customer needs, including latent needs, add to the perceived quality of goods and services. What Ozio's marketers did not focus much upon is the concept of 'perceived quality' that is considered a crucial determinant of customer satisfaction (Shaon and Rahman, 2015) in academic literature. This also implies that CRM indirectly affects perceived quality leading to customer satisfaction in case of luxury fashion.

Apart from enhancing the perceived quality of the luxury brand, CRM helps to increase the reliability of customers' consumption experiences by ensuring precise and timely indulgence of orders placed by customers (Shaon and Rahman, 2015). CRM makes possible for companies

to maintain and nurture customer relationships effectively across different stages of relationship initiation with customers, communication, continuation of the relationship and termination. This helps to manage long term customer relationships, customer satisfaction and gaining customer loyalty which is essential for customer retention.

The findings also corroborate with the theoretical debates in the literature; for instance, Rahimi and Kozak (2017) point out that CRM directly contributes to customer satisfaction within the realm of relationship marketing. CRM helps to avert the age-old, one-off transactional approach to marketing and build long-term customer relationships which are more satisfying. By capturing useful data, it helps to understand customers' likes and dislikes, purchase history, purchase frequency and their behaviour, based on which customer-centric marketing strategies can be designed to provide superior value, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction. However, Shaon and Rahman (2015) indicate indirect relationship between CRM and customer satisfaction by considering perceived quality as the most crucial determinant of satisfaction. CRM increases perceived quality of the luxury brand offerings, enhances customer dependability and the overall consumption experience.

As regards to the importance of **CRM for customer retention**, the findings indicate that comprehensive information obtained from several customer touch-points help to recognise signals of customers who are intending to switch to a different luxury fashion brand, and therefore enables staff to take immediate steps to stop the switch-over. As a customer database, CRM helps in the study of customer behaviour, identification of the most loyal ones and the implementation loyalty programs to foster retention. Ozio's CRM helps to create personalised offers, build rapport, engage customers and thereby boost retention. The literature does not focus much on the impact of CRM on customer retention, even though some researchers insinuate that customer satisfaction leads to customer retention.

CRM helps luxury brands to deliver customised services and enhance the level of service delivery to affluent customers of luxury brands. Sophisticated CRM tools that are difficult for competitors to imitate help luxury fashion brands to streamline their distribution channels and strengthen the value chain, backed up by better social relationships and engagement that enhances retention (Khan, 2012). Carmen et al. (2016) indicate strong relationship between customer-specific marketing strategies such as customer acquisition, add-ons such as service delivery, and retention and CRM. At the same time, Jain and Patel (2016) emphasise on the key strategies to manage customer relationship as endorsed by CRM systems linked with the

process of marketing and sales, and support functions. Other researchers such as Sun et al., 2014; Bramulya et al. 2016; Alshurideh (2016) consider CRM to be a management approach that helps to identify customer needs and develop successful relationships to ease customer relationships.

Empirical investigation also emphasised on whether customer satisfaction led to customer retention, i.e. whether it was easier to retain satisfied customers in luxury fashion. The investigation also tried to understand the importance of customer satisfaction and retention for luxury fashion marketers. Findings indicate that one of the major implications of customer satisfaction is customer loyalty exhibited by customers through repeat purchase, low switch-over intention, and recommending the brand to others. Therefore, in the luxury fashion brands industry customer satisfaction contributes to customer loyalty and loyal customers are easy to retain. Luxury customers are generally educated, rich, affluent and choosy about what they purchase and therefore they are particular about the company policies, values and ethics. For that reason, apart from maintaining sound customer relationships through CRM it was necessary that fashion brand was ethical in terms of other marketing practices such as product development, packaging, distribution, price, and quality. Findings also indicate that customer satisfaction is the key to customer retention in the luxury sector and to achieve this innovative marketing practices including innovative CRM is imperative. Going ahead of the usual customer satisfaction trends it is necessary to achieve customer delight and this possible by maintaining innovative CRM capabilities.

In contrast to the above findings, theoretical debates carried out in the literature review indicate that, apart from CRM capabilities, it is brand recognition that impacts customer decisions to choose a luxury fashion brand for repeat purchase and remain loyal to it. Apart from this, postponing a seasonal launch implies unavailability of the expected fashion range at the right time which hampers customer expectations and therefore hinders customer satisfaction (Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Hennigs et al., 2015; Shukla et al., 2016). Consequently, customers may switch over to competitor luxury brands having product availability according to seasonal trends. Therefore, CRM has little role to play to retain customers as the importance of product availability prevails over CRM capabilities.

5.3 Comparing and contrasting qualitative and quantitative findings

Triangulating the overall findings obtained from the customer survey and managerial interviews - especially with regards to CRM, customer satisfaction and retention - indicates agreements, differences as well as discrepancies between the quantitative and qualitative responses.

Agreements are found with regards to the use of CRM to drive sales, often intruding into customers' privacy by making sales calls, or spreading awareness about promotional discounts and fresh product arrivals, all of which can lead to customer dissatisfaction. However, CRM is also used to address customer queries, complaints and escalations and to resolve customer issues in real time. The quantitative and qualitative findings corroborate the fact that Ozio uses a multi-channel approach to communication, including social media. However, the integration of CRM with social media is still at the preliminary stage for the Ozio luxury fashion brand. Agreements also exist with regards to the use of CRM for undertaking customer satisfaction surveys, measuring the level of customer satisfaction and strengthening customer relationships.

However, discrepancies are evident with regards to the design customisation of CRM according to the specific needs of different customer groups, as customers majorly disagree. While managerial interviews indicate that CRM is used to engage customers, provide efficient after sale services and resolve customer issues to their utmost satisfaction, these factors are largely denied by customers in the survey.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusions

This final chapter of the project concludes the entire thesis by revisiting the research aims and objectives formulated in the first chapter. While concluding the thesis, the findings obtained from primary research, i.e. the customer surveys and the interviews, are also revisited to evaluate how far the findings help to meet the original aims and objectives. In addition, the conclusions also integrate the theoretical models, conceptual frameworks and the assumptions

discussed in the literature review with the findings obtained from empirical research, where relevant.

The aim of the research was to investigate and analyse the impact of business strategies, particularly marketing strategies on customer satisfaction, and retention. The research was with respect to the fashion industry, specifically Ozio, a luxury fashion and accessories brand. The preliminary objective of the research was to explore the underpinning business and marketing strategies, customer retention and customer satisfaction models, and thereby gain conceptual knowledge by review of the existing literature. This was followed by the objective that intended to examine the importance of marketing strategies that favour customer retention and satisfaction in the fashion luxury sector. The subsequent objectives were to critically evaluate whether such marketing frameworks and business strategies helped to mitigate the negative impact on customers, and to identify the positive and the negative influences of the marketing strategies in the business and customers perspectives. Finally, the last objective was to recommend how the negative influences of these marketing strategies can be overcome and better customer retention strategies be implemented.

In order to satisfy the research aim and each of the objectives, corresponding research questions were simultaneously framed and against each question there were a number of questionnaires formulated. These questionnaires were meant for the customers taking part in a closed-ended survey while a separate set of open-ended questionnaires meant for the managerial interviews. The overall findings obtained from the customer surveys and managerial interviews will be cumulatively discussed, cross-examined and verified against each other. In the subsequent sections, each of the research objectives and questions are triangulated with the findings and the literature review, where relevant, to ensure that the objectives have been satisfied, and the research questions resolved.

Findings reveal that Ozio has established its own CRM system as part of its marketing agenda, especially relationship marketing approach. Extensive use of CRM is made to acquire customers, interact with customers, capture data and utilise the useful information to redesign or enhance their marketing capabilities. CRM also helps to carry out other activities such as making customers aware of the fresh arrivals at the store, new launch, promos and discounts. CRM also functions as an initial point of contact and as a helpdesk where customers can connect with the customer service representatives, raise their concerns, clarify doubts and

escalate any issues or complaints. This adds value to the Ozio's relationship marketing approach and service delivery.

Apart from functioning as a platform for customer interactions, it also helps to engage customers and establish long-term relationships. However, Ozio generally uses its CRM as a sales-centric tool to convince customers to make purchases by inciting their purchase decisions through ads and promos. Regular communication with the customers is usually in the form of un-solicited and frequent calls to stimulate their purchase decision. CRM practices are from a transactional perspective rather than relational perspective, and therefore the use of customer information is used by marketers to increase sales. Even though the CRM personnel are educated, knowledgeable and disciplined they are not trained on superior customer-centric skills and therefore their orientation is mainly towards communicating with the customers to achieve sales.

The CRM soft is analytical and therefore focuses mainly on capturing extensive customer data throughout the different customer touch points. It also functions as a process centric CRM to develop strong customer relationships, however, with the main intention to drive sales, cross-sell products, inform about new launch, and undertaken customer satisfaction surveys. The rich information is also used to customise its CRM system based on the profile and different requirements of the different customer segments. CRM is also used as a mechanism to satisfy customers by providing superior customer experience and offering them personalised attention. The use of CRM to retain customers is by capturing customer data to identify the different signals that customers give thereby indicating that they may switch over to different other brands. Based on the crucial information, Ozio's marketers take immediate steps to further probe the customers and redesign their CRM capabilities or marketing strategies to retain the customers.

6.2 Linking research objectives/questions with the findings

6.2.1 Objective 1

To evaluate the underpinning business strategies, customer retention and customer satisfaction models, thereby gaining knowledge by thorough review of the existing literature –

This objective was directed towards conducting an extensive review of the underpinning literature associated with business strategy and narrowed down to marketing strategies and frameworks that are relevant for customer satisfaction and retention. The conceptual explanation of business strategy according to Porter (1996), is business progression with the help of aggressive and defensive actions to accomplish a reasonable position in any industry. Business strategies also help a company to effectively handle competitive pressures, external in nature, that impact business operations and help to secure a sustainable return on investment. Business strategies also encompass conducting situational analysis. In addition to the external market analysis, this involves identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the firm along with the opportunities and threats, based on which a strategic fit need to be created. Strengthening the organisational capabilities, competencies and resources helps to achieve competitive advantage and long-term superior performance. Business strategies also help firms to respond to the ever-changing business environment. However, the choice of appropriate strategy, intensity, timing and process is crucial for implementation success.

Business strategy, from the customer's perspective involves creating 'customer value' and hence, an in-depth understanding of customers' needs, demands and expectations is necessary along with the identification of the characteristics of products and services that are desired. Therefore, the diversified customer needs and expectations needs to be researched and the information used to design the business strategy. Accessing such information about customers that is of current importance is necessary to define and redefine the business strategies. Therefore, listening to customers is equally as important as conducting marketing research, which includes considering the customer's predispositions, moods, behaviour and factors that shape such behaviour, cultural orientation and expectations. Gaining access to such useful information requires establishing a long-term relationship with the customers within the scope of 'relational marketing', i.e. the transactional marketing approach. This is how business strategy gives way to marketing strategies wherein 'relationship marketing' is the stepping-stone towards customer acquisition, relationship building, nurturing and strengthening relationships that cumulatively lead to customer retention.

The fundamental approach towards relationship marketing incorporates the design and implementation of customer relationship management (CRM) which is regarded as an ideology, a tool, a process, a strategy and technology. However, within the scope of marketing, CRM is largely characterised as a process that is strategized to achieve the marketing goals and objectives. CRM is referred to as the integration of people, business processes and technology

(Wilson et al., 2002) and a business tool (Verhoef et al., 2010) that help to engage customers. With advancement in internet technology, the implementation of eCRM (electronic CRM) and integration with social media (Social CRM) have been instrumental in automating the process of CRM, creating better interactivity between the marketers and the customers, and between customers, and providing solutions to customer problems in real time. Therefore, the overall process of CRM has undertaken a strategic approach to help customers, provide customer support and unmatched service delivery, with the overall marketing aim of customer satisfaction, and retention.

Underpinning the literature associated with customer satisfaction are the models to measure the level of customer satisfaction, including the SERVQUAL Model, the Retail Service Quality Scale (RSQS), assessing the Product Quality Dimensions, ACSI (American customer satisfaction index) Model. The key dimensions of the SERVQUAL model, namely tangibility, responsiveness, assurance, reliability and empathy. These dimensions need to be incorporated in the marketing strategies such as CRM in order to minimise customer complaints and deliver superior services that align with their needs and expectations and keep them satisfied. The dimensions of the RSQS model such as physical aspects, personal interactions, reliability, organisational policy and problem-solving are especially designed for the in-store retail environment.

Within the scope of business strategies, the market dominance approach helps marketers to place the company's products or services ahead other brands. This helps firms to maintain their dominance in the market by offering differentiated products or by being a cost leader to offer very low price, or unmatched services that exceed customer expectations. To achieve market dominance, marketers either try to become market leaders, followers, challengers, or target a niche segment (Melnik et al., 2008). The market leaders hold a significant market share and strive to protect their existing market position. The market follower, on the other hand, tries to imitate the products and services that the market leader maintains and offers competitive pricing to lure the customers of the market leader. The challenger designs its marketing strategies aggressively to disrupt both the marketer leader and the follower. The market challenger also tries to target them on the basis of any vulnerability of the market leaders and followers, such as attracting their unsatisfied customers through aggressive promotions, implement superior technology, etc. Market challengers use offensive marketing strategies while the leaders implement a defensive marketing approach.

These different marketing approaches followed by companies incorporate different marketing mix designs that can appeal to potential customers, or existing customers, and keep them satisfied. The marketing mix incorporates the 4P's, namely product, price, promotion, and place (distribution), and the extended 3Ps comprises process, physical evidence and people, and these are all integrated to meet the needs and expectations of target customers and ensure their full satisfaction. Supporting the marketing mix is often the 4C's of marketing, starting with customers, communication, cost and convenience.

6.2.2 Objective 2

To examine the importance of marketing strategies, especially CRM that favour customer retention and satisfaction

A range of marketing strategies have been implemented by Ozio in order to keep its customers satisfied and retain them as loyal customers. The company follows a relationship marketing strategy as a relational marketing approach and the findings obtained from the customer survey indicate that the company maintains a dedicated customer relationship management (CRM) system operated by a team of customer service professionals. The company follows a strategic approach to CRM by integrating people, technology and process to deliver superior value to the customers. The CRM is used not only to acquire customers but also a build trust-based relationship on the basis of mutual understanding and co-operation. It uses its CRM capabilities to make customers aware of the fresh arrivals.

Findings from the customer survey reveal that the CRM representatives maintain close and regular interaction with the customers to ensure their issues, problems and complaints are acknowledged in a timely manner. To ensure that the CRM helps to achieve higher customer satisfaction, the key dimensions of the SERVQUAL model, especially responsiveness, assurance and reliability, are incorporated in its CRM system and capabilities. Used as a relationship marketing strategy, CRM functions like a complaint management system and allows customers to log their complaints for immediate attention by the company. Ozio makes sure that the complaints are attended without delay and resolution is given within the promised time. Timely response to customer problems and complaints indicates that the CRM is 'responsive' to keep customers satisfied, with resolution given in real time. Along with responsiveness, Ozio ensures that the CRM also provides 'assurance' to the customers that

their queries, problems and doubts will be clarified in an appropriate manner and to the best of their satisfaction. Therefore, the CRM representatives and the customer service personnel are well-trained, knowledgeable and tactful enough to resolve customers' queries and problems and to provide assured services. The CRM approach of Ozio is also reliable, as the findings from the survey indicate, and this implies that the customers can depend upon its customer services. Therefore, the marketing strategies of the company with respect to 'relationship marketing' are supported by a dedicated CRM which incorporates the service quality dimensions of responsiveness, assurance and reliability to maintain superior service delivery and achieve customer satisfaction.

In addition to CRM, other marketing strategies include maintaining a multi-channel approach to communication to enable interaction with customers and to eliminate any communication gap. The marketing communications (marcomm) is multi-channel, implying that a range of channels and platforms to communicate, such as telephone, mobile apps, website chat, emails, postal letters, and social media. Out of these communication channels, social media is used extensively as a digital communication channel to maintain round-the-clock, two-way interaction with the customers and 'listen' to their voice.

Ozio makes use of sensory marketing strategies that allow customers visiting the store to touch, feel and examine the fabric quality and other characteristic attributes of the merchandise before making the actual purchase. The use of sensory marketing helps to create an emotional appeal and ensure that the customers are satisfied with the purchase they make. The internal ambience of Ozio stores is also designed using sensory marketing tactics to have proper lighting and visuals, refreshing smell and good music that all create a positive appeal and create customer satisfaction. With regards to the marketing mix strategy, the findings from the customer survey reveal that in terms of quality, range, availability, etc), the products have met customer expectations and have been satisfactory.

In order to cross examine and verify the customer responses obtained from the survey, the managers of Ozio were interviewed and probed with similar questions. Response obtained from the managerial interview (Q1) indicated that the relationship marketing strategies of company are backed by 'Analytical CRM' which are meant to capture useful data from customers from different touchpoints. The data is used by the marketers to customise the marketing mix strategies according to the specific customer groups to ensure that the differing customer needs and expectations are satisfied. The managerial responses also indicated that the CRM works as

a systematic process; however, it uses robust analytical software to capture data and also identify which products to up-sell or cross-sell to which customers. Conflicting responses were received during the interview, as one of the managers disregarded the use of CRM for up-selling or cross-selling products; rather, it was implemented to maintain a customer-centric behaviour. The responses indicate that the marketing strategies of Ozio have been built around the relational aspects of marketing and are less inclined towards the transactional perspective. CRM functions as an important touchpoint between the company and its customers and facilitate the marketers to gain a 360-degree view of the customers, thereby allowing them to design marketing strategies to achieve higher customer satisfaction.

Managerial responses obtained from (Q2) clearly indicate that the CRM platform helps the company to interact with customers, personalise the conversation, build rapport and encourage an emotionally based relationship. The findings also indicated that the customer complaints are resolved to the full satisfaction of the customers with the help of CRM and the CRM representatives well trained enough to provide customer delight. CRM is also used as a mechanism to undertake customer satisfaction surveys and identify the level of customer satisfaction. Conclusively, the findings infer that CRM helps Ozio to build better customer relationships, keep the customers satisfied and this subsequently helps in customer retention. The findings indicated that satisfied customers are more likely to stay with the company for the long term, and this promotes customer retention.

With regards to the marketing mix strategy, the findings from the managerial interview indicate that the product mix at Ozio, being a luxury brand, was sophisticated, rare, and of superior quality and priced in a manner that provide customers with value for money and satisfaction with every purchase they make. The distribution of Ozio's luxury collection is not widespread and restricted to maintain its 'rarity' and luxury image. The limited-edition products of Ozio are customised using innovative capabilities and priced at very premium rates, basically personalised for niche customers who looked for elegance and seek such products during special occasions only. The managerial findings indicated that the extended marketing mix is given special emphasis by ensuring the in-store staffs are well-trained, polite and knowledgeable enough to serve visitors. The process of customer services, billing, after-sales services, return of merchandise, etc. is maintained at a superior level to achieve higher customer satisfaction.

6.2.3 Objective 3

To critically evaluate whether the marketing frameworks and business strategies help to mitigate the negative impact on customers

In response to the managerial interview (Q5), it was found that Ozio incorporates the dimensions of 'service quality' into its marketing frameworks and strategies to strengthen its relationship marketing approach. The marketing strategies are customer-centric and the core dimensions of service quality such as 'responsiveness' and 'assurance' are given due importance. Responsiveness ensures that the customers visiting the store, enquiring about the products or making payments do not have to wait for a long time and are attended to in a prompt manner. Customers are also assured of getting the same (superior) level of services each time they interact with Ozio, whether through online or offline channels. The findings from the managerial interview also revealed that marketing at Ozio is designed on the basis of the 'service dominant' logic of marketing, focusing on the services mix of people, process and physical evidence. Ozio's marketing services are built on the basis of customer centricity and the employees are equipped with the right skills, right knowledge, right behaviour and temperament to serve the clients to their utmost satisfaction.

The findings also indicated that the internal ambience, cleanliness, store atmosphere and other tangible elements included in the services mix are managed carefully to ensure they have a positive impact on visiting customers. The operational process as a part of the marketing strategy related to purchase, payments, customer services and return of merchandise have been designed in a systematic manner that have a favourable influence on customers. In addition, the marketing staff are also well-trained and competent enough to serve customers and interact with them throughout the different touchpoints. Therefore, the incorporation of the service quality elements into the marketing strategies and emphasising on the services mix of physical evidence, people and process help to create a favourable environment.

Included in the marketing framework (Q4) is a well-designed CRM tool that helps the marketers to gain access to useful customer information that is captured during each transaction. Wide-ranging information gained from CRM helps to pay close attention to customers' problems and any signs of an impending customer departure and knowledge about this is gained by identifying variables such as the purchase frequency, service calls or type of complaints made. The data captured in this manner also helps the marketers to understand the consumer attitude and behaviour, signs of dissatisfaction, or any intention to switch over to

other providers if there are no purchase made for a prolonged period of time. The useful information gained from CRM is a part of the marketing strategy and help to predict the intention of the customers, whether it is negative or not and could result in customer dissatisfaction.

Based on the customer information and data, the marketing mix strategies have been designed to fulfil customer needs and expectations and eliminate any negative perceptions. CRM helps to track the negative signals of customers intending to switch over to a different competitor and then take instantaneous action to persuade customers to stay with the company. CRM is also a strong customer-database at Ozio which helps to track those customers who yield the most revenue by making frequent purchases, or purchase in bulk. The use of such information helps Ozio to design incentive plans for the most profitable customers and strengthen customer retention. CRM also helps to personalise the interactions that take place between customers and the company, engage them, listen, and create a platform of trust.

6.2.4 Objective 4

To identify the positive and the negative influences of the marketing strategies in the business and customers perspectives

The findings obtained from the customer surveys indicate the marketers of Ozio make frequent calls asking customers to make purchases based on promotional offers and discount which is perceived to be intervening and disturbing. In support of these findings, customers in the survey also revealed that the CRM system at Ozio is meant to achieve sales by convincing customers to make more frequent purchases rather than building long-term relationships, resolving issues or making attempts to keep customers satisfied. Findings from the survey also revealed that the CRM often fails to provide resolution to customer issues and complaints to their best satisfaction. These are a few areas in the marketing approach of Ozio that influence customer perceptions in a negative manner.

Findings obtained from the managerial interviews indicate that the marketing efforts of Ozio are usually directed towards achieving positive customer experience; however, customers often

develop negative impressions of the company. The marketing communications often create a negative influence on customers, especially online advertisements such as display ads, banner ads, sudden pop-ups, and similar forms of intrusive communication which are considered disturbing and result in customer complaints. These types of advertising campaigns, promotional messages and marketing literature that are posted on digital platforms and are meant to educate customers about the offerings lead to a negative impact on the clients.

The findings from the managerial interviews also indicated that the marketing promotions, such as sales promotions are perceived by customers to be pushy, wherein the sales personnel attempt to convince customers to buy a newly launched product. Therefore, the marketing strategies that are sales-centric lead to negative customer impressions of Ozio and adversely affect customer relationships.

The marketers find it difficult to tailor the marketing mix and the marketing communication strategies to the ever-evolving customer demands and expectations. Individual customers, groups or segments who encounter any marketing mix elements or communication that do not cater to their needs, usually develop negative perceptions about the company.

Managerial responses also revealed that social media communication is one of the core reasons for negative customer perceptions of the Ozio brand, for which the company is not solely responsible. In most cases the customers post their own content on social media that is fake or includes exaggerated stories and poor product reviews, which creates a negative impact on other customers. The customers have a tendency to frequently share any unfavourable experiences on social media and distribute to mass consumers rather than any favourable experiences. Even the most loyal customers spread negative word-of-mouth content about the Ozio brand and tracking the quality and circulation of such content is not easy. Therefore, social media communication that is not under full control of the marketers, often have a negative influence on customers.

While online advertising such as pop-up ads and banner ads, etc. are considered intrusive by the customers, sales promotions and sales centric calls are resisted and misuse of social media communication is carried out by spreading negative content and unfavourable word-of-mouth recommendations, resulting in negative customer perceptions about the brand, there are some marketing strategies adopted by the company that ensure customers have a positive perception about the brand. The most significant marketing strategies in this context is CRM operated by well-trained customer services personnel who are always eager to resolve customer queries,

issues, problems and complaints, thereby ensuring that it has a positive influence on the consumers.

Ozio also implements ‘sensory marketing strategies’ to ensure that customers have a positive impact about the company and the brand. Sensory marketing strategies are implemented based on the principle that customers of luxury products do not visit the store to purchase superior quality merchandise but also enjoyment, pleasure and happiness, and thereby emotional satisfaction. The sensory marketing strategies comprised of elements that had a positive influence on the customers’ senses and made their cognitive, behavioural, and emotional responses favour brand awareness and the creation of positive brand image in their minds. The opportunity to touch, feel and examine the products before buying, enjoy the music and an exciting shopping environment, and even a warm handshake was meant to create a positive influence about the company on the customers’ mind.

6.2.5 Objective 5

To recommend how the negative influences of these marketing strategies can be overcome and better customer retention strategies be implemented

Negative influences, as identified from the overall primary research were in several areas of marketing. While the managerial interviews revealed that the managers boast of a solid ‘relationship marketing’ approach implemented by the company, the approach is often transactional in nature. Findings from the customer survey clearly indicate that the CRM personnel often make repeated calls to customers endorsing some kind of promotions to push customers to make a purchase. These unsolicited calls are often disturbing and create a negative impact. The managerial interviews disclosed that such sales-centric calls are usually carried out after a major product launch where the marketers/ CRM/ sales personnel are instructed to sell the products on the basis of aggressive sales promotions with the main objective to achieve quick sales in a specified period of time.

The findings also revealed that the online digital communication, especially the advertisements such as pop-ups, banner ads, un-closable browsers, etc. are considered to be intrusive and disturbing. It undertakes the usual activities of the customers on the internet and often leads to a large number of customer complaints.

Next, social media marketing, particularly communication on social media fostered by the marketers, is often subject to manipulation by the customers while even the loyal ones spread negative word-of-mouth content. In addition, fake content, exaggerated stores, poor product reviews generated and posted by the customers and their massive circulation without any control, result in unfavourable perceptions for the viewers.

The recommendations are therefore based on the aforementioned shortcomings that would help to mitigate the negative impact that the marketing strategies have on Ozio's customers and help the company to achieve higher customer satisfaction and retention.

6.3 Recommendations

6.3.1 Recommendation 1

Avoid unsolicited marketing calls/ intrusive advertisements

It is strongly recommended to the marketers of Ozio to prevent unsolicited marketing calls and minimise the frequency of online advertisements such as banner ads, sudden pop-ups, un-closable browsers that all result in negative customer perceptions about the marketing efforts of the company and its brand. Telephone calls can be substituted by digital marketing capabilities such as mobile messaging, smartphone apps, or posts on social media. Rather than making sales calls to the customers as a part of the sales promotion strategy to persuade them to make purchases or repurchases, notifications via smartphone apps could be sent. Similarly, intrusive ads that are repetitive, showcase the same message again and again and that are monotonous need to be replaced with innovative advertisements that contain up-to-date information, attract customers' attention and are more interesting and engaging.

Unsolicited marketing calls and interruptive ads that are likely to cause customer dissatisfaction need to be controlled using ethical marketing and innovative advertising capabilities,

respectively. If making calls is of utmost importance, the marketing department of Ozio should call within specific timelines or a calling window, rather than attempting to call at any time.

6.3.2 Recommendation 2

Adopt Social CRM as a holistic approach to customer relationship management

While Ozio maintains a dedicated CRM system to strengthen its relationship marketing capabilities, the 'engagement' factor is not given due importance. Integrating social media with the CRM system will help to strengthen the customer relationship management and the relationship marketing frameworks. Creating dedicated fan pages for loyal customers on popular social media platforms such as Facebook and linking them with CRM capabilities would help to serve each customer individually, build rapport, personalise the interactions, develop close relationships based on trust and improve customer retention.

Social CRM will help the marketing department to shift from a product-focused strategy to a customer-centric framework. In particular, Ozio's CRM, which works as an analytical tool to collect extensive customer data from several customer touchpoints, can be strengthened with the help of Social CRM to create better value for the customers, better understand their needs and provide value-added services. The analytical CRM system of Ozio can be strengthened with the help of Social CRM by gaining access to Big Data from comprehensive customer information collected from mass media. Social CRM will help marketers to track every form of communication that the customers post on social media- formal or informal, authentic or fake, exaggerated brand stories or real-life experiences, negative reviews or favourable ratings or positive /negative word-of-mouth suggestions. Gaining a holistic view of such customer information will help to monitor the quality of information, the rate and speed at which information is disseminated and its influence on others and customer reactions associated with it. Access to such 360-degree information will help staff to take more effective marketing decisions, facilitate better distribution of information among the customers designed by the marketers/brand managers in real time and maintain competitive intelligence.

6.3.3 Recommendation 3

Engage loyal customers to act as ‘brand advocates’ and spread positive eWOM that helps to retain customers

The marketers at Ozio should engage their loyal customers on Social CRM or by using other platforms and motivate them to act as brand advocates. Customers can also be engaged on social platforms by encouraging them to take part in online social events and contests. The marketers can organise discussion boards, social forums, workshops, etc. where customers can share their knowledge and experiences, clarify doubts and feel involved with the company. These customers can be motivated to become opinion leaders who advocate the Ozio brand to other consumers seeking luxury items and willing to join the social group.

Acting as brand advocates, the opinion leaders are likely to spread positive word-of-mouth recommendations for Ozio’s products and shape the intentions of others in a positive manner to go ahead and purchase. Therefore, engaging the customers on Social CRM will help the company to increase the number of loyal customers, as well as motivate them to be opinion leaders and act as brand advocates to retain other customers also. This will also be a cost-effective form of publicity for the Ozio brand that would help to eliminate the detrimental effects of negative word-of-mouth content.

6.4 Contribution to theory

Existing underpinning theories in the academic literature increasingly emphasise on the theories of relationship marketing, customer relationship management, service quality and theories of customer satisfaction. However, the relationship between these theoretical underpinnings is not established in the existing literature; for instance, the impact of service quality, CRM and marketing communications on customer satisfaction and retention. The contribution to theory, as an outcome of this research conceptually explains the importance of maintaining service quality in the CRM design. CRM should be backed by superior service quality, specifically with the integration of SERVQUAL dimensions such as reliability, assurance, responsiveness, empathy and tangibility to ensure utmost customer satisfaction. This is highly applicable to consumers in the luxury fashion industry who generally seek premium quality, differentiated service and unmatched experience with the brand they choose.

The importance of service quality dimension – ‘tangibility’ lies in maintaining an attractive, easily navigable, well-designed website if CRM services are provided online. ‘Reliability’ would ensure that the CRM personnel are capable of providing accurate and dependable services so that customers trust the fashion brand and a stronger bond can be built between the customers and the brand. The incorporation of the dimension ‘responsiveness’ in the CRM is crucial to ensure that the CRM representatives provide prompt services to customers and ensuring minimum customer wait-time. The inclusion of the element ‘assurance’ in the CRM ensures the service provider has the necessary knowledge and confidence to serve the customers and install trust in them. Finally, ‘empathy’ is to ensure that the CRM personnel provide individualised attention and utmost care to the customers. Therefore, the integration of the SERVQUAL model with the CRM system, whether online or offline, ensures that the service provisions are robust, dependable and trustworthy that increases customer switchover cost. This will subsequently increase the level of customer satisfaction and retention capabilities of the brand.

Theoretically, this research also emphasises that there exists a direct relationship between customer satisfaction and retention, even though constructs such as brand advocacy, loyalty and repeat purchases reflect low switching intention of customers. Customers who are satisfied with the services, especially CRM in the luxury fashion industry, are more likely to show their commitment towards the brand, thereby making ‘customer retention’ easier for the company.

6.5 Contribution to management practice

The management of fashion brands such as Ozio must ensure that the use of CRM is made for the right purpose, i.e. building and nurturing customer relationships to gain their long-term commitment. Therefore, the use of CRM as a sales-centric tool to make unsolicited calls to customers should be avoided. The use of CRM from the relationship marketing perspective must be used to connect, interact and engage customers in a manner that gains their trust and advocacy for the brand. CRM strategies should be inclined towards relational marketing perspective rather than following a sales-centric approach to push sales.

Ozio’s management should build upon the capabilities of Social-CRM, i.e. integration of 24/7 and marketing communication (social media) with CRM to offer round-the-clock support services. Social-CRM will help to monitor customers’ activities on social media, provide better

response to their queries and customise solutions to their day-to-day problems to ensure higher customer satisfaction. The dissemination of negative content, fake reviews, exaggerated experience stories and negative word-of-mouth recommendations can be controlled, and thereby the extent of customer dissatisfaction by engaging these customers.

The managers of luxury fashion brand such as Ozio could integrate the core dimensions of SERVQUAL with the Social-CRM model to ensure that an exceptional service scape is maintained. The time-bound, premium niche segment of customers of luxury fashion brand avail exceptional customer services and prefer remaining loyal to the brand. Customer information obtained from different touchpoints should be used to design the CRM system in accordance to the profile, needs and expectations of different customer groups. A customised CRM solution is likely to offer superior after-sales services, complaints handling and engagement that aligns with their requirements.

Another piece of contribution is the inclusion of specific marketing mix for luxury fashion brands, i.e. 4Ps [P-persona, P-performance, P-placement, and P-paucity] going beyond the usual product, price, place and promotion elements. Persona refers to the final outcome of the luxury brand's unique projection, dependability and value proposition across different customer touchpoints. Placement is the instore ambience, decoration, presentation (in case of online luxury it is the website design, beautification, navigability) and comfort that the luxury customers experience. Performance refers to the functional characteristics or attributes such as precision, excellence, craftsmanship and innovativeness of the luxury brand/product while paucity refers to the rarity of the brand. Paucity is of utmost importance because extensive distribution and over-revelation of luxury may dilute the luxury characteristics and therefore luxury brands often produce limited edition. The adoption of 4Ps [P-persona, P-performance, P-placement, and P-paucity] is to support the CRM capabilities of luxury fashion brands such as Ozio.

6.6 Limitations of the study

One of the major limitations of this research was that a cross sectional study was undertaken while collecting primary data from the customers and the managers in the survey and interview respectively. Therefore, data was collected only in a single phase of time from a specific sample size. However, human perceptions are likely to change over a period of time and it is useful to capture the changes in their attitude and perceptions. This is possible by undertaking a longitudinal research in which data collection is carried out in multiple phases of time to

capture and measure the changes in human perceptions and attitude. Longitudinal research was not possible to undertake in this study due to budgetary constraints and therefore the changes in the customer perceptions about Ozio's CRM approach could not be tracked. Other limitations of the research were also present such as the possibility of biased response in the primary data collected from the survey and interviews. This could have affected the quality and validity of the findings.

6.7 Scope for future research

The current research mainly focused on relationship marketing strategies and the associated CRM approach of the company to deliver superior customer services, build and nurture customer relationships, keep customers satisfied and achieve their long-term retention. The focus of the research was also on marketing mix strategy, communication mix and sensory marketing due to the nature of the business Ozio is involved in. Many areas still remain unexplored and un-researched, especially with regards to digital marketing capabilities of fashion and luxury brands such as Ozio and how it helps to achieve higher customer satisfaction. The scope for future research lies in investigating the effectiveness of implementing omni-channel marketing strategies which integrate the usefulness of both 'online' and 'offline' marketing capabilities.

This provides a holistic marketing platform for shopping, wherein customers can connect, interact, shop, transact, lodge complaints, etc. through physical brick and mortar stores, high street outlets or company websites, online shopping portals, emails, social media, or mobile apps. It also provides a seamless shopping experience to the customers by allowing them to purchase at anytime, anywhere, by any means without being restricted to the use of a few defined channels. In addition, emerging concepts such as 'webrooming' or 'showrooming' could be extensively researched, with regards to customer satisfaction and retention in the luxury fashion industry. These concepts are used interchangeably and reflect a phenomenon wherein customers see, examine and try the product in a physical retail store before buying it from online channels. Future researchers can conduct research regarding how companies such as Ozio invest in innovative marketing strategies such as Omni channel marketing, webrooming, etc. and achieve higher customer satisfaction and subsequently, increase their customer retention rates.

6.8 Reflective statement

The reflective statement is based on the conceptual model designed by Gibbs and comprises five sequential stages -

Description – The situation I faced was challenging, as I was supposed to initiate and complete a thesis following a systematic plan. I initiated the task by reviewing the existing literature obtained from secondary sources, in particular journal articles, books and previously published research papers. Collecting relevant material was very hectic, although this was the preliminary stage of my journey towards the thesis.

Feelings – It was a mixed feeling that started with anxiety, sometimes very interesting, and at times feeling totally lost to new concepts and theories that I came across in the literature. Similar was my experience while reviewing the research methodology that included philosophical standpoints, research approach, and data collection methods. At times I felt very confident while doing the write-up, even if it was a rough draft in the beginning.

Evaluation – It was a positive feeling looking at the quantity of my write-up, and I felt optimistic. However, negative emotions cropped up as soon as I started to read the content as I felt there was scope for improvement. Feedback from my supervisor, including moral support and encouragement, was instrumental in terms of upgrading my work. The contribution from my supervisor in the form of feedback and suggestions worked well for me and I got a clear direction of what to do, and how to do it. It was time to prepare the survey questionnaires and interview questions for primary data collection, followed by collecting the actual data, which I did. The participants who were sampled for data collection were cooperative and what I had presumed to be the toughest phase, worked out really well.

Conclusion–At the stage where I was about to complete the thesis, I was faced with a dilemma and planned to change the thesis title. Yet again, I was fortunate enough to get valuable guidance from my supervisors who advised me about the implications. I realised it was feasible to modify the title in a way that aligns well with the overall write-up, findings and conclusions. However, I believe that the thesis could have been much better, more analytical, if I had had better analytical skills which I need to develop.

Action plan– For similar tasks in the future, I need to maintain a more analytical approach to writing and create a better flow and layout that is more interesting. In future, I would rather follow a more pro-active approach, a systematic plan and continuously assess my work in terms of logic, analytical flow and clarity.

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Appendix A-Survey questionnaires for customers

Q1) Please indicate your gender?

Male
Female
Transsexual

Q2)Please indicate the age group you belong to?

Below 20
20-25
26-35
36-45
46-55
Above 55

Q3) Please indicate your marital status?

Married
Single
Living with partner
Divorced
Others

Q4)Please indicate your occupation?

Employed
Self-employed
Student

Housewife
Sports personnel
Not working
Others

Q5) For how long have you been purchasing from Ozio/ or been a customer of this company?

Less than 1 year
Around 1-3 years
Around 3-5 years
Around 5-7 years
Around 7-10 years
More than 10 years

Q6) The Company (Ozio) has a dedicated CRM system backed with customer services team to help the customers?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q7) The Company (Ozio) makes use of its CRM capabilities to acquire customers like you?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q8) The Company (Ozio) makes use of CRM to inform you about the fresh arrivals in the store in a timely manner?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q9) The marketers/CRM execs make frequent calls asking you make a purchase based on promotional offers and discounts?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q10) If you strongly agree/agree to the above question, do you consider the frequent marketing calls to be intervening, disturbing and resulting in dissatisfaction?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q11)The CRM representatives undertake initiatives such as ‘customer satisfaction surveys’ to identify the level of customer satisfaction?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q12)The CRM mechanism has the potential to build relationship with the customers based on trust and mutual understanding?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q13)Overall the CRM system is tailored according to the specific needs of customer groups?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q14)The CRM system of Ozio is well designed in terms of providing efficient after sales services to the customers?

Strongly Agree

Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q15) Complaints logged through the CRM/complaints management system of the company addressed in a timely manner?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q16) The CRM reps/customer care execs are knowledgeable and well trained to provide satisfactory answer to your queries?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q17)The company follows multichannel approach (using telephone calls/mobile apps/ online chat/emails/ postal letters) etc to foster easy communication with the customers

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q18)The company extensively uses digital communication channels such as social media to interact with the customers on 24x7 basis?

Strongly Agree

Agree

Nether neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q19)The CRM system is integrated with social media (social CRM) to ensure customers have access to the customer care execs on a 24x7 basis?

Strongly Agree

Agree

Nether neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q20)The customer service offered through CRM or otherwise has been reliable so far for you?

Strongly Agree

Agree

Nether neither agree nor disagree

Disagree

Strongly disagree

Q21) Overall, do you perceive that the CRM system of Ozio is mainly aimed at pushing sales rather than helping customers and keeping them satisfied?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q22) The company has been able to resolve your issues and complaints so far to the best of your satisfaction?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q23) Are you allowed to touch, feel, and examine the product quality very carefully before buying?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q24)The internal store ambience (such as lighting, product display, sound such as music, smell etc) are emotionally appealing to make you feel satisfied as a customer?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree

Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q25)The products (product quality, range, availability) offered by the company so far has been up to your expectations?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q26) The services (CRM, complaints handling, after sale services, return merchandise etc) provided by the company so far has been up to your expectations?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q27)Is it essential that the company should always keep you satisfied to retain your custom for long term?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Nether neither agree nor disagree
Disagree
Strongly disagree

Q28) How satisfied are you with the experience you had so far with the quality of services offered by Ozio?

Very satisfied
Somewhat satisfied
Can't say
Dissatisfied
Very dissatisfied

30) How likely are you to remain loyal to the company for the rest of your life?

Very likely
Somewhat likely
Can't say
Unlikely
Very unlikely

Appendix B-Interview questionnaires for managers

Q1) What are the CRM strategies implemented by the company, as a part of the marketing strategy? Does it help to control/ remove negative customer impressions about the company? Please elaborate

Q2) Does CRM as a business strategy in Ozio help in customer satisfaction? Please elaborate

Q3) What kind of marketing mix strategy is adopted by the company to foster customer satisfaction?

Q4) Does CRM as a business strategy help to retain customers? Please elaborate

Q5) How is service quality related to marketing strategies and practices at Ozio? How does it relate to customer satisfaction and retention?

Q6) Are satisfied customers more likely to remain loyal to the company? What marketing efforts are directed towards customer retention? Please elaborate

Q7) As a fashion (luxury) does sensory marketing result in better customer satisfaction? Does the company follow it? Does it also help in customer retention? Please elaborate

Q8) What kind of marketing tactics actually result in negative customer impression and dissatisfaction? How do you overcome them? Please elaborate

Appendix C-Transcripts of interviews (managers)

Q1) What are the CRM strategies implemented by the company, as a part of the marketing strategy? Does it help to control/ remove negative customer impressions about the company? Please elaborate

M1 – *“luxury retailing in the current era demands for hands-on sales approach in terms of personalised communications, high-service interactions, and custom fittings”(pause).... Look! towards this end, we have set up a holistic CRM framework which facilitates regular client interactions and help our marketers to identify the varied needs of customers.....””at Ozio’s brick and mortar stores the marketing strategies are supported by the ‘analytical approach’ to CRM which helps in data capturing, I mean acquiring useful data from customers from the various touch points where they share their basic information... such as smartphones, company website, emails, and verbal communication with the staff at the store. “this is useful data” (smiles)it could be their names and contact details, type of goods purchased, quality and quantity of items purchased, frequency of purchase, bank details..... and so on....the data is comprehensive, often haphazard and it’s a strenuous job to filter such data and make it useful” so what we do is use the data not only for customer profiling, but to categorically design our marketing tactics according to customer requirement as far as possible*

Analytical approach to CRM as a part of our relationship marketing approach is instrumental in terms of creating better understanding between the marketers and the customers, build rapport and personalize the relationship.....what I mean is to treat them as human beings and not just ones with whom only a formal exchange based relationship is maintained.....(long pause) CRM eliminates communication gaps between us and the customers, avoid misunderstandings, and provide concrete solution to their problems....this subsequently eliminates the possibility of any bitterness between the company and the customers and thereby wipe up any negativity”

M2- *“Our CRM framework is more process oriented rather than a mere technological tool...it follows systematic process..... The CRM capabilities are directed towards building customer relationships rather than just a tool or a medium for exchange of words.....” “ the approach is analyticalnow see everything in marketing is based on analytics and analytical thinking and therefore we have to rely on numbers, data and sales to run the business analytically..... “Everything in marketing is based on analytics; we need to rely on numbers, data, and sales to run a business”.....(takes a deep breath)CRM mechanism to drive sales is based on customer relationships, such as repeat customer purchase, in order to sustain in the competitive business environment...” ... “I’d clearly tell you that the benefits of CRM are immense and you know ..CRM at Ozio helps to cross-sell or up-sell products as a priority function, including optimisation of sales coverage, financial forecasting, contact optimisation,*

and growth in customer satisfaction scores''. "not only CRM helps to foster sales but also to enhance the level of customer satisfaction" ...

For the second part of the question, M2 remarked *"Oh! there is nothing as negative in our customers' mind about Ozio as far as I know (laughs)..... but then if you are asking then let me tell you that CRM helps to shape positive customer perceptions about our brand as a provider of premium luxury backed with customer centric behaviour" "See, the key to remove any negative influence of our marketing strategies is to keep customers engaged using the CRM process...if you understand what I mean to sayCRM assures customers' that yes! There's someone, a dedicated team in the company who cares about them".*

M3 indicated *"Ours is a customer centric company and therefore we have designed our marketing strategies based on relationship marketing model"our marketing strategies are built around the relational aspects of marketing and less inclined towards the transactional perspective'. we have a robust CRM framework based on optimal co-ordination between information technologies, social assets...err...I mean employees are aligned with the business processestry and understand....CRM is an important touch point between the company and the customers which helps to gain a 360-degree view of the end users of the products and servicesPractically as a strategic marketing process CRM is meant to gain access to comprehensive customer data from the different customer touch points and accordingly design the marketing mix strategies that could meet the requirements of individual customer segments and that of customer groups.. it helps to log customer complaints and resolve their issues and grievances to the best of their satisfaction, and that too in real time (smiles).*

M3 asked to repeat the second part of the question ... (after prolonged silence)...disclosed *"customers form negative impressions from social media where negative reviews about our brand is posted by many, existing customers or potential ones, and those whose expectations may not have been met ... you knowand negative reviews spread like wild fire in social media.....negative content and posts, even word of mouth is usual in social channels where exaggerated experiences. Fake reviews are posted by many just to spread negativity about our brand....so what's the remedy? (smiles) Ozio's has its presence in social media to connect with customers and few social sites such as FB is linked with our CRM to monitor the negative reviews.....although it's a herculean task it helps to ease the situation to some extent.*

Q2) Does CRM as a business strategy in Ozio help in customer satisfaction? Please elaborate

M1 *Yes, definitely, by all means. CRM is the only platform that allows closer interaction with the customers, personalise the conversation, build rapport, and encourage emotional based relationship'.Look! customer enquiries are resolved by our CRM representatives who are the first point of contact for the customers.....CRM as a dedicated tool helps to maintain a systematic process of responding to customers in a prompt manner without any delay..... CRM*

is an effective tool that helps to resolve customers' complaints which is often too complex to be resolved by a salesperson at the Ozio store.

CRM enhances customer experience...." I'll explain you how, Look! A customer visiting a store to verbally communicate with the store personnel or communicating online would always expect someone to be friendly, show concern, and care this beautifies luxury and adds value to the experience they have with our brand" " If my memory doesn't betray me I would share a small experience...I've come across a Chinese customer, a young lady who usually made online purchase, received the merchandise just to return it in 3-4 days' time complaining that the items were not delivered according to her specifications, especially the clothing doesn't fit her and this often became massive complaintsso a dedicated CRM specialist, preferably a female employee was assigned to this customer to deal with her concerns in a personalised wayso a dedicated CRM specialist, preferably a female employee was assigned to this customer to deal with her concerns in a personalised way....now each time this customer made an online purchase our CRM specialist would take her through every detail of the items she chose, including intrinsic details such as fabric, craftsmanship, size and fittings and this made her (customer) happy.....she used to have a pleasant experience as someone from Ozio was dedicated towards herand was one the most satisfied customer...." "therefore, CRM leads to better customer experience and build good customer relationship which are ingredients of high customer satisfaction".

M2 'Our CRM offers a systematic process of complaints log where customers can escalate their complaints to the customer care personnel, and then to the senior levels, if it is not resolved'. The customers could log on to the complaints management system (CMS) on the website and post their complaints straightaway to the customer relationship officer if not satisfied with the resolution provided by the customer care personnel..... We ensure that the complaints of almost every customer is resolved to their full satisfaction and those involved with resolving customer complaints aim to achieve 'customer delightit's a part of our mission to go an extra mile to help the customer in a manner that delights himEach time a complaint is closed from the customers' end, a customer satisfaction survey is conducted through the CRM tool and customer satisfaction scores (CSat scores) are always high... (after a careful thought)...hmmm.. 'I can proudly say that we never had detractors so far'..

M3 "See, customer complaints are very frequent in the hospitality sector and therefore the need to maintain an effective CRM system which we possess.... CRM is crucial to address customer complaints in the best way possible so that such complaints are not repeated.....(pause) Ah! a very satisfied guest today can start yelling tomorrow for a minor service gap and things may go out of control if the issue is not handled tactfully" It is well trained CRM personnel who take escalations, log the complaint and initiate a complaint management system. From a different angle, CRM also helps to gain access to useful customer data from the different touch points based on which the customer groups are segmented according to their demographic or behavioural profile and marketing strategies tailored to serve the respective groups. Customers getting customised services according to their expectations are more likely to be satisfied. CRM assures that customers voice is being listened to.... what I mean is interacting with the customers is not enough, we need to show concern

and a dedicated team is there to assure customers' WE ARE LISTENING' and this is a very satisfying experience for customers.... A personalized service offered through CRM where customers can speak whole heartedly and the same is reciprocated by us is the key to customer satisfaction in its own way customers of luxury products are too sensitive, but then, not price sensitive but what they are wearing. will it bring magnificence to their personality, make them stand out in the crowd, and raise their status, that's luxury for them, and these customers want to discuss this with us, not with the sales person, but someone who shows great care and attention, listens to them, acknowledges and gives importance to every minute details they share, they expect satisfaction with every purchase which is aided by our dedicated CRM experts”.

Q3) What kind of marketing mix strategy is adopted by the company to foster customer satisfaction?

M1 “Each element of the marketing mix is categorically designed to make sure it satisfies customers, and this is done very carefully in a luxury brand, but in my opinion product and price are the two main ingredients and the association between the two is equally important..... I have experienced customers consciously or sub-consciously develop a psychological luxury stature of the price range maintained by Ozio, as a luxury brand . (takes a deep breath).....hence we strive to charge the right price from the customers”.....” offering lower price than their expectations and the customers' eagerness to pay is likely to harm the brand value.....and the other way round may not give enough justification to customers to make a purchase”.... offering lower price than their expectations and the customers' eagerness to pay is likely to harm the brand value.....and the other way round may not give enough justification to customers to make a purchase” .Look ! we aim at setting the right price for the right kind of product that needs to be made available on time and this ensures customer satisfaction as customers of luxury do not mind paying higher price for the right items neither expect competitive pricing... ..” (takes a deep breath)... maintaining product attributes in luxury fashion is a pre-requirement and key attributes that our products include are quality, scarcity, heritage, non-utility/superfluous, and integrity ... at Ozio we made sure the product range irrespective of its price met their attributes to ensure that the customers derived value for money and subsequently satisfied with every purchase they made’.

*M2 “marketing of luxury brands like ours entails specific mixes including **persona, placement, performance, and paucity** apart from the usual marketing mix.....see persona is of special importance to us. persona of Ozio is the result of its unique projection, and consistency across the different customer-touch points and marketing communication through the ads’anow (and now) as far as placement as a mix is concerned it is associated to store location, presentation of the salesmen/customer service personnel, meanwhile as far as placement as a mix is concerned, store location, in-store ambience and customer experience heightens customers brand experienceas far as performance as a mix is concerned importance is given to be the delivery of a distinctive experience of Ozio as a luxury brand... as far as performance as a mix is concerned importance is given to be the delivery of a distinctive*

experience of Ozio as a luxury brand ‘Our performance is at two levels, at the product level and at an experiential level.....in the former case (product level), we ensure that the product range is capable of satisfying the functional characteristics as well as the delivering on its physical attributes, design excellence, precision, craftsmanship, unique design, excellent quality, best fabric, and innovation....See at an experiential level it is necessary that the emotional value of Ozio as a brand was much ahead of what the product represented. Now as far as paucity is concerned over-revelation and mass distribution of the luxury range usually dissolves the luxury character of a reputed brand and hence, we have to maintain the customers’ perception that it is scarce..... We have some limited-edition products which are customised through the innovative capabilities, priced at very premium rates, largely personalised for niche customers seeking elegance and made available during special occasions only.....so what matters is not only the usual marketing mix of price, product, promotion, place and the extended ones what you call (pause) .. process and people, but the marketing mix in luxury is different and what counts are persona, placement, performance, and paucity...Yeah! These things matter and are crucial for enhancing the level of customer satisfaction for luxury brand like ours ...”

*M3 Customer services are at the heart of our marketing mix and I personally believe efficient services are the most important ingredient of customer satisfaction’ while the marketing mix comprises of a set of elements I’d concentrate on the extended mix, but not leaving aside product and place to which much importance is givenproduct should be differentiated and distribution should be limited as you must be aware of limited edition premium items meant for people with a classy taste for elegance.....okay, keeping product quality and limited availability aside, I would emphase on elements of ‘**process**’ and ‘**people**’ in the marketing mix, the importance of maintaining a well-trained workforce to run the process of daily business operations and customer services. Our main focus is to maintain exceptional quality of services at all levels and processes which is possible only if well trained staffs were there..... ‘We at Ozio ensure that customer services was prompt and responsive on which the customers can rely upon....the customer services staff are well trained on soft skills, customer service skills, and knowledgeable about handling different types of customers ...customers seek extraordinary quality, fabric and design that they may not have experienced before, some customers expect very systematised process, flawless services and marketing personnel who can live up to their expectations....therefore, at a stage what becomes important is our peoples’ behaviour towards them integrated with the operational process of conducting transactions such as purchase, billing, after sale servicesthese mixes customised in the right way leads to higher customer satisfaction.*

Q4) Does CRM as a business strategy help to retain customers? Please elaborate

M1- GOOD QUESTION! Look the best way is to keep the customers happy and this is possible by offering them the best quality services and CRM makes this possible’. comprehensive information gained from our customer relationship management largely helps to pay close attention to customers’ problems and any signs of an impending customer departure, and

knowledge about this is gained by identifying variables such as the purchase frequency, service calls, type of complaints customers make NowLook ! CRM helps to closely view signals of customers intending to switch over to a different service provider and then take immediate action to convince customers to stay before they left. The manager also commented that ‘we follow a practice of running the sales report for the last six months and such data is obtained from CRM...any customer, or customer groups who had not made any purchase for a long period are most likely to leave the organisation and hence the marketing personnel follows up with them. So, the very purpose of CRM is to retain customers by building trust-based relationships and gaining their custom for long term, may be for life-term (laughs) so that’s it”

M2- CRM at Ozio provides us with key insights into the purchase history of customers and accordingly we target our offers and make them most relevant and appealing to the customers.... this increases customer satisfaction and make it easier to retain the satisfied customers there are several other ways in which CRM can be helpful in retaining customers. see the most profitable customers, especially those making higher purchases from the company are incentivised so that they can be retained..... I would like to tell you that our CRM is as good as a customer database which helps to track customers who yield for us the most revenue by making frequent purchase or purchase in large bulk I would like to tell you that our CRM is as good as a customer database which helps to track customers who yield for us the most revenue by making frequent purchase or purchase in large bulk... the use of such customer information helps the us to design lucrative perks or incentives to the profitable customers, or the most loyal ones, and retain them by creating high switchover cost.....See this helps to budget both, time and resources, and retain customers that were the biggest potential for return.

M3- “CRM is instrumental in creating personalised offers for the customers, engage them, and boost customer retention.....”see, it is essential to engage each and every customer irrespective of the purchase frequency, the bulk of purchase made when quantified, and the how much profitable a customer is to the company.....customers should be engaged through CRM,I believe in making personalised offers for every loyal customer based on CRM intelligence....and it is essential to listen to them, create engagement which automatically increases the chances of retention.....”.

Q5) How is service quality related to marketing strategies and practices at Ozio? How does it relate to customer satisfaction and retention?

M1 – Oh so you want me to discuss about our quality of services and how it is embedded without our marketing practices, and then its outcomesYes, service quality has to be embedded in the marketing principles and policies of an organisation to sustain the competitive pressures’ ...the buyers of luxury products in our brand Ozio are very particular and conscious about the quality of the services combined with every purchase they make. Our customers, most of them were the rich and affluent, usually time-bound and didn’t mind paying higher for

prompt delivery of their orders.....I'll talk about responsiveness here and you know customers hate being kept waiting even it was for mere 5-10 minutes and they should be as time is precious! For both online and offline purchase, customers expect prompt delivery of the merchandise, prompt billing, and similar expectations they had for merchandise return or 'after sale services. the marketing strategies, especially from the 'services marketing' perspective the services were supposed to be prompt without causing any delay. Prompt services, on time delivery, and assurance that the same level of service would be provided every time the customer visits the store is essential to maintain utmost customer satisfaction. "better services quality ensure high customer satisfaction, which no doubt created high switch over cost for the customers to change their preference for brands, and consequently helped to retain customers".

M2 - Now look, marketing is a broad concept, are you talking about the service dominant logic of marketing?" Of course, 'service quality is an essential part of the services marketing at Ozio and dominantly included in the service delivery to ensure better customer experience, co-creation of value, and thereby maintain an unmatched value proposition....." "Ozio's marketing services was built on the basis of customer centricity and this necessitated that the staffs were equipped with the right skills, right knowledge, right behaviour and temperament to serve the clients to their best satisfaction"We as service provider our sales personnel, customer services, CRM representatives are trained effectively in terms of being knowledgeable, courteous, and tactful in delivering services and keeping customers satisfiedalso "each and every customer is important irrespective of what they purchase, how they purchase, and the quantity they purchase and it is our primary duty to see everyone received the same level of services – i.e. differentiated service quality to create customer delight', and these customers are most likely to return to the store as a satisfied customer.....it is easy to retain satisfied customers especially those who are satisfied with the level of services being offered.

M3 – In response to this question of yours I would link service quality the extended marketing mix such as physical evidence, people and process who would like to visit a messy store?' who would like to purchase if the buying process or making payments is unsystematic? and who would like to talk to rude salesperson? (laughs) that's why service quality forms an intrinsic part of the service mix.....Look! the tangible view of Ozio store entails decoration, cleanliness, ambience and the way customer facing staff maintain a tidy dress code and pleasant appearance. Our employees are adequately trained and directed how they should deal with customers in different touch points starting from the initial contact until the final transaction is complete, and thereafter each time the customer visits our store.

Q6) Are satisfied customers more likely to remain loyal to the company? What marketing efforts are directed towards customer retention? Please elaborate

M1- *Definitely, Yes! No doubt, one of the major implications of customer satisfaction is customer loyalty and the signs of loyal customers are repeat purchase, low intention to switch over to competitor brands, and suggesting others to choose the brand to which they are loyal”and these are the factors that make our marketing efforts very successful.....Look the loyal ones are less price sensitive and do not mind paying extra if the prices for the products or service are increased to some extent.(pause)... Look the loyal ones are less price sensitive and do not mind paying extra if the prices for the products or service are increased to some extent. ‘It’s the age of relationship marketing and CRM tools are the most dominant tools for customer retention and its use helps to understand customers, identify their changing needs and behaviour, track their purchasing patterns and accordingly design the marketing activities that is customised for specific target segments’.and I can proudly say that our CRM representatives are well trained on delivering excellent customer services while maintaining trust based long term relationship with the customers so that they do not go elsewhere.*

M2- *Higher the customer satisfaction, higher is the chance that they would make another purchase from the same store in future ... and satisfied customers become advocates to the brand recommending the company to family and friends and others..... obviously we can’t expect loyalty from dissatisfied customers!”The key to customer loyalty was relationship marketing and the tool was customer relationship management’.marketing should involve ethics right from the marketing planning stage, to the development of products, packaging, and customer segmentation, brand positioning and creation of the marketing mix elementsthe product quality, price, and distribution, process of product and service delivery should all incorporate a fair and transparent play’.Customers of luxury products such as ours are generally rich, affluent and highly educated who understand what foul play is and thereby they may quit purchasing from a company if they sense some kind of unethical practices going on ...so we strongly emphasise on ethical marketing that could help in customer retention apart from the usual CRM approach ...”*

M3 - *the tendency of satisfied customers to remain loyal to the organisation is always higher than the dissatisfied onesand that’s since ages in the marketing world and I strongly believe that the key to customer loyalty and retention is customer satisfaction....I’d also place importance on marketing innovation ...now see the usual marketing activities, including sales promotions, marcomm (explained this as abbreviation of marketing communications)and marketing mix are common to almost every business firm intending to achieve higher customer satisfaction.....at the same time it can’t be denied that it was necessary to achieve customer delight going ahead of customer satisfaction and this is possible through service innovation, yet again, going ahead of service quality.....at the same time it can’t be denied that it was necessary to achieve customer delight going ahead of customer satisfaction and this is possible through service innovation, yet again, going ahead of service quality....the concept of customer*

satisfactions seems to fade away in the current economy and given way to customer delight and the level of satisfaction Ozio is gives can be matched easily by the nearest competitor'.....see modern customers are in quest for innovative products and services could switch over suppliers at any time...in my views meeting customer expectations was not enough in the current marketing age but it is essential to exceed their expectations to achieve their long term custom, loyalty, and retentionand I won't deny that innovative capabilities of customer relationship management can be developed or increased by integrating it with social media , and smartphones in today's marketing environment so that customer needs can be better understood, offer customised solution to their problems in real time, and build personalized relationships that can facilitate better customer retention.

Q7) As a fashion (luxury) does sensory marketing result in better customer satisfaction? Does the company follow it? Does it also help in customer retention? Please elaborate

Mi- Hmmm, that's interesting...sensorial marketing is definitely a part of our (Ozio) marketing strategy; however, we are yet to leverage the full benefits of such innovative marketing practices.....and create a positive appeal" Look! Customers who visit our stores not only expect superior quality products but also enjoyment and happiness.....buyers of luxury are the ones seeking much pleasure and emotional satisfaction out of their shopping experiences"It calms, de-stresses, energises, provides relaxation, and improves customers' mood and therefore influence their decision-making in a positive way..... (pause) customers of luxury items are usually the rich and affluent and hence time-bound and a serene atmosphere with good music, aroma, nice paintings on the wall, and similar factors have a positive influence on customers' waiting timethe sense of touch strengthens brand identity, sense of sound attaches meaning to a luxury brand, while taste represent an array of experiences that a customer has with the brand such as how it looks, sounds, smells and feels, and these factors are inherently satisfying. Obviously, satisfied customers are likely to be more loyal and continue giving their custom to get consistent experience and chances of switch over is less.....does it answers your question?"

M2 ...I'd clearly say that sensory marketing is one of the main sources of competitive advantage for a fashion retailer with physical brick and mortar store....we use the different neurotic stimulations of vision, touch, sound and smell to provide customers a unique experience that they do not get during the online purchase... (pause). it helps to incite powerful and provocative emotions that is persuasive and convincing and satisfying at the same time". (after some time).....our sensory marketing campaigns consist of elements that has a favourable influence on customers' senses and ensure that their cognitive, behavioural and emotional responses favour brand awareness while creating a positive image for the brand.....I'll explain you with a simple example, lets' say, touch which doesn't mean that the customer should have a good feeling after touching the fabric available but also the packaging, the hand-shake that should give them a pleasing experience and they feel comfortable.....now see for every luxury item that we sell at Ozio, the customers prefer to touch the product, have a close look at the item, go for a trial, and so on therefore,

it is necessary to create a vibrant environment which has positively appeal to their senses.....otherwise even the best of our products may look dull”(long pause)... Obviously a visitor at the store will have a more satisfying experience if the atmosphere is emotionally appealing and inclusive rather than dull and shabby that doesn't match with the luxury being sold.....the sense of touch and physical examination of the merchandise this way ensured that customers are satisfied with the purchase they make, i.e. value for money. However, how far sensory marketing helped to retain customer was an area that the marketing department had not concentrated much upon.....

M3 – “Ozio store stands out from its surrounding environment and grabs customers' attention due to the visual stimulation, emotional appeal, and the personal touch that is extended.....My personal opinion and experience is that customers of luxury products are strongly attached to music'and playing the right music according to the type of customers that matches their age, lifestyle, and taste is more effective, although it's very challenging...without any doubt”.. see the type of music, the tempo, the genre combined with a beautiful aroma largely determines the length of time a customer would willingly spend and the speed at which a customer navigates around the luxury products....” (after a thought)at Ozio store we prefer sober yet peppy music, dim lighting, and comfortable seating arrangements if customers want to rest” ...hmmm for customer satisfactionnow, see there are specific elements of sensory marketing that create a positive appeal in the minds of the customers leading to increased satisfaction and good experience with the brand.....suppose an elderly customer is offered a comfortable chair to sit while a young customer finds his favourite number playing are likely to feel more satisfaction than it would have been otherwise and would be more eager to visit the store.....this is a satisfying experience for the customer who would preferably stick to our brand and help us in retaining them...”

Q8) What kind of marketing tactics actually result in negative customer impression and dissatisfaction? How do you overcome them? Please elaborate

M1- Oh, that's so straightforward (laughs) while marketing efforts are directed towards positive customer experience and satisfaction, often customers develop negative impression about our brand and products ...” .. Look! marketing communications such as sudden pop ups and display ads, and often banner ads are found to be intrusive by customers which is obvious and they resist.....however our intention of such communicative ads is to make customers awareness of the fresh offerings or arrivals at the store rather than to intrude into their privacy or important work..... there has been many massive customer complaints in the past for unwanted advertising content, literature, or promotional messages being posted to the customers via the communication platforms that the customers used – such as social media.....however, you know, such online ads were very common on the website but did not work well with Ozio in terms of gaining customer advocacy or satisfaction.

M2 – “Sales promotions that are often ‘too pushy’ and meant to convince customers to make a purchase are often objectionable by customers However, these are part of the marketing strategies wherein the salesmen are assigned with soft targets to acquire new customers, sell or cross-sell different products to the existing customers.....often the marketing personnel try to persuade customers to make a purchase of a newly launched item that needs to be sold through aggressive sales promotion; however, we ensure that our marketing campaigns are manned by ethics and strict protocols”. there is a very thin line of demarcation between sales and managing customer relationships and disclosed that customer relationships were maintained to ensure that the customers did not switch over to competitors and made purchase from our brandsometimes sales promotions were considered too pushy by customers, even the most loyal ones, and this created negative impression about the brand.

M3 -tailoring or customizing the marketing strategies according to the explicit needs of customers or customer groups was very challenging ... (deep breath) especially when customer demands, orientation, and attitudes are continuously changing””I can tell you from my experience that customers have a tendency to share any negative experiences with the company on social media, often exaggerated, and circulate it extensively among the masses, despite a satisfactory resolution given to them.....social media marketing is to remain connected with the customers, ‘listen to them’ and allow them to be loud, but they are louder than what is expected (laughs)....often with the liberty to write anything and circulate it among masses with just a few mouse clicks’.even the most loyal customers spread unfavourable word of mouth reviews on social channels that spoke any issues they had with the company while the good experiences were subduedsee the spread of negative word of mouth content, often exaggerated, sometimes fake, and threatening are frequently posted by customers on anonymity and the spread of such content is not easily traceable as social media communication is not traceable neither easy to monitor’.spread of negative word of mouth content, posts and reviews are the main reasons for negative impact on other customers who view them, and it is next to impossible to control these issues...”

APPENDIX D- Ethics Form

Ethics approval application form (UEC1.1)

Pre-screening questions:

(Please read the UWS and your School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship before answering these questions, which will help you decide whether or not you need to make a full ethics approval application for your work).

Does your work involve human participants? YES

Does your work involve the use of personal data? NO

Does your work involve the use of animals? NO

(For this purpose, animals are defined as captive or temporarily captive living vertebrates or cephalopods. If such work is already licensed under the terms of the Animals Scientific procedures act (ASPA) then no further ethics approval is required)

Does your work involve risk to the investigator that is not adequately mitigated by proper application of the University's health and safety policies and procedures? NO

If you have answered **YES** to **any** of the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project.

If you have answered **NO** to **all** of the above questions your research/scholarship would be Class 1 as defined in the UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship and so you do not need the approval of a School Ethics Committee for your work.

1. Name of Principal Investigator: Mr Hassan Hassanein

2. School: Business and Enterprise

2b. If you answered “other” above, please provide details below:

3. Position of Principal Investigator: Postgraduate student

4. Name and contact details of collaborators: None

5. Name of Supervisor/Director of Studies: Dr. Paul Reynolds
(for student applications only)

5a. Position of Supervisor/Director of Studies: DBA supervisor / lecturer
(for student applications only)

5b. School of Supervisor/Director of Studies: Business and Enterprise
(for student applications only)

6. Title of the study: The impact of CRM as an effective marketing strategy on customer satisfaction and retention in luxury retail: A case study of Ozio

7. Primary purpose of the study: Postgraduate dissertation

If you answered “other” to this question, please provide details below:

8. Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee? NO

If the study has been considered by another ethics committee, please provide data

9. Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study:
(word limit 1000 words. A full study protocol should be attached to your application)

Designing an appropriate methodology to carry out a research study is a crucial factor, especially in social science research. Establishing an appropriate methodology involves evaluating a range of research methods, approaches and

strategies that are considered relevant for the study and choosing the most suitable ones that will assist in the collection and analysis of data to resolve the identified problems (Holden and Lynch, 2004). Research methodology incorporates a holistic approach to carry out the entire process of a study, beginning with the choice of theoretical underpinnings and techniques of data collection and analysis, and extending to develop objective-based solutions to the identified problems (Rajasekar et al. 2006). Framing the right methodology implies choosing the most appropriate elements that focus on the problems to be investigated, or finding solutions to previously identified problems, depending on the nature of the investigation. However, it is important that the choice of research methodology is consistent with the research objectives/questions, the context of the study and theoretical approaches (Thomas, 2010).

The current research aims to analyse the impact of business strategy (independent variable) on important constructs such as customer satisfaction, customer retention (dependent variables) and to provide commendations to mitigate the negative impact on clients. In order to achieve this aim, it has been demarcated into a range of objectives and questions that underpin the research questions. The research methodology designed for the current study intends to collect data to meet the following objectives -

- To evaluate the underpinning business strategies, and customer retention and customer satisfaction models, thereby gaining knowledge by a thorough review of the existing literature
- To examine the importance of marketing strategies, especially CRM, that favour customer retention and satisfaction in Ozio
- To critically evaluate the marketing frameworks and business strategies that help to mitigate the negative impact on customers of Ozio
- To identify the positive and negative influences of marketing strategies on the business and customers perspectives of Ozio
- To recommend how the negative influences of these marketing strategies can be overcome and better customer retention strategies can be implemented in Ozio

Depending on the nature of the chosen topic, the identified problems, complexities involved in the investigation and type of data required, the methodological plan incorporates the philosophy of pragmatism to conduct 'mixed-methods' for data collection and analysis (Harwell, 2011). The research approach is deductive, in that it helps to adequately test the theories discussed in the literature review by testing empirical data and assumptions. The type of investigation, particularly the research design chosen, is 'descriptive' in that a structured and formal enquiry is conducted, based on clearly formulated aims and objectives (Perumal, 2014). Quantitative data

collection involves conducting a survey by distributing structured, closed-ended questionnaires to the customers of Ozio, while qualitative data collection involves interviews conducted from managers of the same company.

10. How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- | | |
|--|-------------------------------------|
| Independent external review | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within a company | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within a multi-centre research group | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within the principal investigator's institution | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within the research team | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review by supervisor/director of studies | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |
| Other | <input type="checkbox"/> |

If you answered "other" above, please provide details below:

11. Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

The sample size will be restricted for the large population abroad. However, it is intended a purposeful sample of 300 would be expected. It may be more, because the questionnaire would be administered in multiple social networking websites.

12. Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

Accumulated data will be calculated by standard data calculator with a nonparametric test using MS Excel.

13. Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

YES

13a. Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

NO

If you have answered **YES** to the question above, please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues:

14. Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)? **No**

If you have answered **Yes** to the question above, please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this:

15. Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures? NO

If physically invasive procedures are to be used what hazards are associated with them?

16. Please identify any other ethical considerations with the proposed study.

None

17. Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator? **NO**

If you have answered **YES** to the above question, please provide an explanation/justification of this deception:

18. Will research participants be debriefed after their participation? NO

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide details of when this debriefing will take place, who will do it and how it will be done:

19. What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

Questionnaire: 5-7 Minutes

Interviews: 20-45 Minutes

20. Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

(you should include details of how potential participants will be identified, approached and finally recruited)

In terms of questionnaire, participants will be chosen from abroad.

Regarding to the interviews, it will be at the managerial retail level.

21. What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

Standard procedure and anonymity of accumulated data can only be accessed by supervisor and external examiner.

22. Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

Access to the data can only be gained by the supervisor and external examiner.

23. Will informed consent be obtained from study participants? YES

If you have answered **YES** to the above question, please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

It will be provided and attached in the interview and analysis part of the research after it has been conducted. Additionally, verbal permission will be asked from the participants to contribute. In terms of interviews, the participants will be asked to participate and given time about 2 weeks to make their decisions to interview or not. Also, the questionnaires will be sent to the participants by via social networking websites which is convenient and costs effective. There will be a consent box in the questionnaire, whether they like to participate or not.

If you have answered **NO** to the above question, please justify your decision not to obtain consent from your participants.

24. How long will potential participants have to decide whether or not to take part in the study?

15 days (approx.)

25. Will participants be informed that they can withdraw from the study at any time? YES

26. Will participants be from any of the following groups?

Children under 16

- Adults with learning disabilities
- Adults who are unconscious or severely ill
- Adults with a terminal illness
- Adults in emergency situations
- Adults with mental illness
(particularly if detained under the mental health act)
- Adults with dementia
- Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
- Those who could be considered to have a particularly
dependent relationship with the investigator
- Other
- None of the above

If you answered “**other**” above, please provide details:

If you intend to include participants from any of the above groups, please outline how you will mitigate the risks involved:

27. Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study?

(e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

No

28. Will study participants be paid to take part? Choose an item.

If you have answered **YES** to the above question, please provide details of the payments involved:

No

29. Where will the proposed research take place?

UK.

30. How will the costs of the study be met?

By the researcher himself.

31. Please indicate which supporting documents you are submitting with this application:

- | | |
|---|--------------------------|
| Participant information sheet (PIS) | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Consent form | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Copy of the protocol | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Letters to participants | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Letters to parent/guardians/gatekeepers etc | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Letter or ethical committee approval or other approvals | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Risk assessments | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Other relevant materials (please specify below) | <input type="checkbox"/> |

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

The requirement for forms is at present not considered necessary. If they do turnout to be necessary, it will be forwarded to PGR.

Signature of the principal investigator(s):

Hassan Hassanein

Date: **16/02/2017**

Signature of the supervisor/director of studies:

Personal information withheld.
.Signature is of Dr. Paul Reynolds